

Selected methods and potential applications in Learning Sites

Deliverable D3.1

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1. GES4SEAS Project Summary

Human activities at sea (e.g., maritime transport, extraction of living and non-living resources, etc.) and coastal areas (e.g. agriculture, leisure and recreation, etc.) have expanded considerably, leading to an increased level of pressures and subsequent degradation of ocean health and, ultimately, human health. Single and cumulative impacts of these activities are likely to increase, driven by human demands and enhanced by climate change.

Human activities evolve following socio-economic drivers leading to pressures, which often are studied in isolation from each other even though their impacts on marine ecosystems can interact, making the effects cumulative (e.g. synergistic, antagonistic or a combination). Knowledge on these interactions and their cumulative effects in the marine environment has increased in recent years, but huge challenges still remain to be solved. Thus, there is little predictability with which to inform decision-making processes, especially on ecological tipping points, which, if exceeded, could lead to a point of no-return for the system. In this context, an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach to the management of human activities at sea and on land should ensure that the combined pressure of such activities is kept within levels compatible with the requirements of Good Environmental Status (GES) (within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive – MSFD), against a background of climate change. This means that the capacity of marine and coastal ecosystems to respond to human-induced changes is not compromised, enabling the sustainable use of marine goods and services by present and future generations.

Thus, **the main objective of GES4SEAS is to inform and guide marine governance in minimizing human pressures and their impacts on marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, while maintaining the sustainable delivery of ecosystem services.** This will be achieved through developing an innovative and flexible toolbox, tested, validated, demonstrated and upscaled, in the context of adaptive EBM approach. The toolbox will allow competent authorities to assess and predict the effect of multiple stressors (including climate change) and pressures from human activities, at the national, sub-regional, regional and European level. Ultimately, this will ensure they achieve GES, and support different policies at national, European and global levels (e.g. Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), Biodiversity Strategy 2030, United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)).

Stakeholders and the key competent authorities (including national, regional and European levels) are integrated in a Practitioner Advisory Board (PAB) to co-create and validate the toolbox and the EBM approach. This will result in a real problem-solving approach with iterative and incremental development steps.

GES4SEAS will also rely on existing multi-actor networks to involve and engage with stakeholders. This multi-actor approach will ensure that the research and deliverables are relevant to marine managers all around the world. Lastly, it is important to highlight that the toolbox will be tested and demonstrated at 11 Learning Sites (LSs) covering all European regional seas (and also overseas), and environments. Thus, it is expected that GES4SEAS will achieve Technological and Societal Readiness Levels 6. This will be achieved by the participation of 20 partners, covering the four European regional seas and Canada.

It is expected that GES4SEAS will:

- Operationalize integrative and holistic solutions for EBM, based upon a software toolbox for analyzing, assessing and mapping cumulative pressures, GES and ecosystem services.
- Provide evidence (and training) to key stakeholders of the benefits of using the toolbox that will be developed in GES4SEAS for assessing the environmental status of marine waters and the ecosystem services considering the effects of multiple pressures so opt for using it.
- Ensure that the EBM approach and guidelines for the management of Invasive Alien Species (IAS), harmful algal blooms (HABs) and jellyfish, and the approach for monitoring top predators are used by end-users.
- Investigate, using models, the best ways to obtain thresholds of GES/non-GES status and tipping points (system breaking points).
- Reach and engage a wider society, and specifically young people and educators, on key messages stemming from this project, so GES4SEAS contributes to societal ocean literacy and responsible behaviours.

2. Deliverable 3.1. Summary and objectives

Work Package (WP) 3 of GES4SEAS aims at developing and parameterising cause-consequence models in collaboration with WP2 (“*Developing the conceptual framework and knowledge base for ecosystem-based management*”). When developed, codes and interfaces will be made available for use by stakeholders (linking to WP1 “*Stakeholder engagement: setting the scene*” and WP6 “*Enhancing societal understanding of ecosystem functioning and human health through ocean literacy and dissemination*”), considering the need to be useful for local and regional Learning Sites (LSs) and to develop tailored solutions for areas with different amounts of data (WP5 “*Learning sites: Testing and synthesis*”).

In this WP, we aim to demonstrate how integrating a range of models and analyses can allow examining the combined effects of a range of pressures impacting environmental status, providing these tools to WPs 4-5.

Specifically, the WP3 is divided in 4 tasks:

- *Task 3.1. Capacity to deliver ecosystem services and links to GES* (led by Stichting Wageningen Research, WR).
- *Task 3.2. Testing tipping points and thresholds* (lead by Aarhus Universitet, AU).
- *Task 3.3. Investigating effects of measures on mitigating impacts* (led by The Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, CEFAS).
- *Task 3.4. Building analytical capacity* (lead by Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, CSIC).

This deliverable includes the main advances of WP3 during the first year of the project, with special emphasis on the two milestones that are associated with the WP: M3.1: “*Decision tree released*” [Task 3.1] and M3.2: “*Revision of methods to test tipping points and thresholds*” [Task 3.2]. We also provide a summary of steps taken under Task 3.3 and the planning of capacity-building events under Task 3.4.

Task 3.1 Capacity to deliver ecosystem services and links to GES

This task aims to set the scene and provide a way to include Ecosystem Services and how an assessment of ecosystem services links with that of Good Environmental Status (GES). Building upon the work done in previous EU projects linking human activities-pressures-impacts/state/ecosystem services, and the conceptual framework (including climate scenarios) of WP2, Task 3.1 works from the gap analysis and knowledge base developed in WP2, selecting methods and modelling techniques to quantify the linkages between pressure/state, and between state and the capacity to supply ecosystem services

through ecosystem functioning. This understanding will be implemented in WP4 tools and may be used to identify tipping points and thresholds in T3.2 (see section dedicated to Task 3.2) and subsequent analysis in several LSs (WP5).

Practical guidance (M3.1: Decision tree released) is provided in this deliverable to LS participants and future end-users to facilitate the application in marine ecosystems with different amounts of data. During the first year of the project, we identified several LSs that intend to apply tools related to the capacity to deliver ecosystem services and links to GES (see section dedicated to Task 3.4).

This task aims to investigate, through spatial and temporal analyses, the potential of multiple (cumulative) pressures (such as warming, ocean acidification, overfishing, eutrophication and HABs) to lead to tipping points in ecosystem state (i.e. abrupt non-linear changes potentially leading to regime shifts) and capacity to supply ecosystem services (such as oxygenation of water and nutrient provision supporting breeding and nursery habitats). The final goal is to develop and use a well-suited approach to detect and predict tipping points from the data from different LSs. Under this task, we formulate conceptual models for cumulative pressures that may potentially lead to tipping point responses and investigate ecosystem resilience and conditions conducive to such responses with data from the LSs (WP5).

In this deliverable, we review mathematical and statistical methods for identifying thresholds and early warning signals (M3.2: Revision of methods to test tipping points and thresholds). During different project meetings, we also identified potential datasets that can be used to apply these methods. During the first year of the project, we have identified several LSs that intend to apply tools for identifying and testing tipping points and thresholds (see section dedicated to Task 3.4).

2.3. Task 3.3 Investigating effects of measures on mitigating impacts

This task aims to develop scenarios to predict pressures and footprints in the future (including scenarios of climate change until 2050 and its effects, and particular cases that will consider sex segregation issues, see some examples in D2.1), and their potential impact on environmental status. Under the task, we investigate the effect of measures on the mitigation of impacts over different ecosystem components (with attention to top predators, and also on differing vulnerability to cumulative impacts by sex), ecosystem functioning, and ecosystem services (full consideration of the EBM) within LSs (WP5) using combinations of selected tools (including those in T3.1-3.2). We seek to identify precautionary and robust thresholds that can contribute to mitigation measures and assess various sources of uncertainty surrounding these within a context of cumulative impacts.

During the first year of the project, we have identified several LSs that intend to apply tools for investigating the effects of measures on mitigating impacts (see section dedicated to Task 3.4).

2.4. Task 3.4 Building analytical capacity

This task aims to promote the analytical capacity and capability of participants and stakeholders to apply selected tools of WP3. We aim to organise specialized courses within WP-dedicated activities (such as summer schools, dedicated specialized courses and online courses on applying our approaches) in collaboration with WP1 and WP6.

The aim is that project participants and stakeholders are able to use the tools and models to evaluate the capacity to deliver ecosystem services, identify and test their thresholds, and investigate scenarios of cumulative change, including climate change, in their LS.

In this deliverable, we provide information about the mapping of capacity-building needs identified by the LSs during the first year of the project, and the first activities organised during 2023 and 2024. These activities are directed at building capacity around specific tools identified in Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3., and complement further activities organized from other workpackages (such as WP2 and WP4). To ensure the participation of LSs in identifying potential methods to be used, feedback from participants during 3 online workshops and a physical workshop (spring 2023 and the first annual meeting of the project in May 2023) have been considered.

3. Overview of methodological strategy

3.1. Task 3.1 Capacity to supply ecosystem services and links to GES

Following the aim of this task, we have identified Cumulative Impact Assessments (CIA) as the key tool to assess the capacity to supply ecosystem services and achieve GES. As was found in WP2 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023), there are, however, many methods and tools available to do a CIA. Each method has different information requirements, varying from expert-judgement-based to semi-quantitative to fully quantitative and entirely data-driven. Because of that, they vary in terms of their capability to inform EBM. Depending on their knowledge base, LSs may opt for different methods/tools, thereby compromising the consistency in the assessment results and/or preventing appropriate policy advice, but on the other hand, documenting (and learning) the different approaches.

The linkage framework that is at the basis of previous CIA on North Sea biodiversity (Knights et al., 2015; Piet et al., 2015; 2017; 2019; Borgwardt et al., 2019) has been extended with ecosystem services by Culhane et al. (2018; 2019ab) and Piet et al. (submitted, Appendix 1). The proposed CIA method alleviates (some of) these issues as the method can be applied in both data-rich and data-poor LSs.

Similarly, the proposed method to extend this CIA to include ecosystem services can be based on expert-judgement of quantitative information. The latter can best be obtained from foodweb models such as Ecopath with Ecosim or otherwise. The proposed method allows flexibility in the application of different models.

To ensure the participation of LSs in the proposed methods, feedback from participants during an online introduction and a subsequent workshop (spring 2023) was considered.

3.2. Task 3.2. Testing tipping points and thresholds

Following the aim of this task, we have reviewed the literature to identify some of the best methods available for detecting and predicting tipping points using empirical data, including their advantages and limitations. We also delved into the data requirements for these methods to produce reliable results since some LSs are more data-rich than others. Some of the methods presented could already be implemented in the toolbox, while others would require a bit more technical adaptation. Finally, we include an outlook on how some of the predictive methods can be further developed into more holistic techniques.

To ensure the participation of LSs in identifying potential methods to be used, feedback from participants during an online workshop and a physical workshop (spring 2023 and the first annual meeting of the project in May 2023) has been considered.

3.3. Task 3.3 Investigating effects of measures on mitigating impacts

Following the aim of this task, we have collected datasets for case studies and prepared conceptual models to provide a basis for our work. Via expert discussion, we have identified Bayesian Belief Network and Ecopath with Ecosim models as the most appropriate tools in hand to investigate change in ecosystems as a result of human impacts or mitigation by managers.

3.4. Task 3.4. Selected methods and potential applications in LSs

Following the aim of this task, we have organised various activities to identify potential tools to be used under Tasks 3.1 to 3.3, to map the capacity of the group to teach those tools, and the need for capacity building by LSs and participants.

Specifically, three online seminars have been organised in 2023:

- Workshop on *Capacity to Deliver Ecosystem Services and Links to GES*. 4th April 2023.
- Workshop on *Testing Tipping points and thresholds*. 17th March 2023.
- Workshop on *Investigating effects of Measures on Mitigating Impacts*. 12th May 2023.

The three workshops lasted half a day. They included the participation of several partners and were attended by 20 to 40 participants per workshop.

With potential tools and LSs potentially interested identified, we mapped the interest between tools and LSs, and prioritised capacity-building activities to pursue during 2023-2024. The preliminary mapping was presented and finished at the first annual meeting of the project (Denmark, May 2023).

4. Decision Tree to assess ecosystem services (Task 3.1)

In the contemporary milieu of burgeoning environmental challenges, the assessment of natural capital, which supplies ecosystem services benefiting humans, has surged to the forefront of scientific inquiry and policy discourse (Burkhard et al., 2012; Smith et al., 2017; Hooper et al., 2019). This ascendancy is underpinned by the imperatives of climate change mitigation and sustainability, compelling us to scrutinize the intrinsic value of Earth's ecosystems (Costanza et al., 2017). With climate change posing an existential threat, the need to quantify ecosystems' contributions as carbon sinks and climate regulators is indisputable (Duarte et al., 2018). Simultaneously, the sustainability paradigm underscores the indispensable role of ecosystem services in supporting human societies (Wang et al., 2021). The assessment of cumulative impacts on ecosystem services is pivotal, offering a lens into the intricate interplay of myriad anthropogenic stressors on ecological functions (Halpern et al., 2008). Such assessments form the bedrock of informed decision-making, conservation prioritization, and the discernment of ecological thresholds. Notably, the primary approaches for assessing CIA encompass spatial analysis, interdisciplinary integrated assessments, predictive modelling, and scenario planning—offering a comprehensive toolkit for comprehending the cumulative ramifications of human activities on ecosystem services, imperative for guiding conservation and sustainable resource management endeavours (Simeoni et al., 2023).

This guidance is structured around a decision-tree consisting of four steps (Figure 1), where in each step, there is scope for less ambitious and information-heavy approaches, often based on expert judgement, and for more ambitious approaches using quantitative information. Illustrative examples are provided based on the North Sea LS (Appendix 1). Notably, the first two steps are based on/informed by the work in WP2, while the subsequent steps are more specific to this Task.

4.1. Linkage framework

A linkage framework is an assessment methodology tracing sector/activity–pressure–ecosystem component pathways, mapping thus all the possible 'linkage chains' acting on the system under study and scoring them through expert judgement. The method which includes five pressure assessment criteria (e.g., extent of spatial and temporal pressure overlaps with ecosystem component, degree of impact and recovery lag aspects) was first developed by the EU ODEMM project and has been applied to four European Seas (Knights et al., 2015). It was later used and or further developed by the AQUACROSS and ABIOMMED project as well as ICES WGs. The linkage framework should be comprehensive in the sense that it should encompass all relevant impact chains within a given study area that may affect the biota and, through their functioning, the capacity to supply ecosystem

services. To that end, this method works from the CICES (Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services) cascade model (Haines-Young, 2010), which links biodiversity and ecosystems to human well-being through the flow of ecosystem services and where the Capacity to supply ecosystem services is underpinned by the biophysical structure and processes (Liquete et al., 2013). More information on these concepts (cascade framework, ecosystem functioning and capacity) can be found in the background document “Ecosystem services, functions and processes” (Appendix 2).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework used as decision-tree for the assessment of the anthropogenic cumulative threats to the capacity to supply ecosystem services. CIA: Cumulative Impact Assessment. Adapted from Ges4Seas website.

An impact on biodiversity can compromise the Capacity to supply ecosystem services, but this depends on the relations to the biotic groups that make up the biophysical structure. To assess the impact on biodiversity within a LS, we may develop a new linkage framework or adopt an existing linkage framework such as from previous EU-funded projects ODEMM (Knights et al., 2015) or AQUACROSS (Borgwardt et al., 2019) that has been extended to include ecosystem services (Culhane et al., 2018; 2019ab). A typical linkage framework consists of impact chains, which link the activities, pressures and ecosystem components to each other, and, based on these, highlight the main threats to biodiversity

caused by human activities and their pressures, following the DAPSI(W)R(M) approach (Elliott et al., 2017). To extend this linkage framework to include ecosystem services, known linkages between specific biotic (or functional) species groups and ecosystem services can be applied, as Culhane et al. (2018) demonstrated. To that end, we match the ecosystem components that are aligned to the MSFD (EC, 2017) to those biotic groups identified by Culhane et al (2018) as the most relevant units providing marine ecosystem services.

Ecosystem components representing species groups (e.g., fish & cephalopods, mammals or birds) was a straightforward one-to-one match. In contrast, other biotic groups in the MSFD context are represented by the communities associated, e.g., with one or more predominant habitats (e.g., zooplankton with the water column or epifauna with several seabed habitats) or ecosystem functions. Potential issues when constructing linkage frameworks were identified by Piet et al. (2017). For example, subdividing any specific category increases the number of impact chains and, hence, its relative contribution to the assessment outcome. Balanced linkage frameworks are thus essential for the CIA's capacity to provide meaningful results. To support the establishment of balanced linkage frameworks, the following rules are proposed for the main elements of the impact chains, i.e., activities, pressures and ecosystem components (or species groups) that make up the linkage framework:

1. Human activities are sectoral at their basic level. This allows a straightforward link to the socio-economic system and its relevant data, future scenarios or specific stakeholders. In order to inform EBM, these sectoral activities can then be sub-divided into operations if they interact differently (i.e. through different pressures) with the ecosystem and/or are likely to be subject to different management actions. The appropriate MSFD categories and definitions are provided by Smith et al. (2022).
2. The selected pressures should be comprehensive to cover all the potential mechanisms through which human activities can affect ecosystem components. Pressures are key in these assessments, as they represent the mechanism through which human activities interact with the respective ecosystem components. Only direct linkages between stressors (i.e., activities and their pressures) and receptors (ecosystem components or biotic groups) are considered, not indirect effects that may occur through the food web interactions or abiotic components. The appropriate MSFD categories and definitions are provided by Smith et al. (2022).
3. The suite of ecosystem components (or species groups) should be comprehensive because they are expected to represent biodiversity and all its different life forms, i.e., key phyla. They should thus cover ALL the biota of the ecosystem that contribute to its integrity and functioning at an appropriate level of detail. The most basic level ecosystem components

should match what is used in policy documents for their status assessments and conservation. The appropriate MSFD categories and definitions are provided in Smith et al. (2022). An example of a linkage framework is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. An illustration of how ecosystem components are the key node linking the anthropogenic threat (i.e. sectoral activities and their pressures) to the capacity to supply ecosystem services (CtS ES) through the Service Supply Potential (SSP) as well as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive goal of Good Environmental Status (GES). CIA: Cumulative Impact Assessment.

For each of these three elements, the design of the CIA needs to accommodate the information requirements, which can be based on expert judgement, empirical data or model data, to ascertain acceptance by the stakeholders. Highly aggregated elements come with relatively modest information requirements, but stakeholders may desire more disaggregated elements to accept that their sector (industry stakeholders) or species/taxon of concern (policy or NGO stakeholders) is recognisable and adequately represented. As there is often discussion about the appropriate level of detail, hierarchies can be developed that allow each element to be divided into increasingly more detailed sub-elements. However, this comes with the requirement that these should be mutually exclusive and can be aggregated or disaggregated without affecting the CIA results. Further differentiation and detail result in an increasing number of impact chains and, hence, information requirements for parameterisation. A balance needs to be struck between the need for increasingly more detailed sub-elements and the availability of information to distinguish between the sub-elements realistically.

4.2. Cumulative Impact Assessment (CIA)

A number of CIA approaches are presented in GES4SEAS D2.1. (Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Here, any risk-based approach can be applied to the linkage-chain framework developed in the previous step.

The risk estimate provides the (relative) weighting for each impact chain. The proposed Impact Risk and method to calculate it has the advantage that it allows information from both expert judgment and quantitative data and that it provides a metric that can intuitively be understood (i.e., decrease in abundance (numbers, biomass) from undisturbed situation). It is essentially a risk-based approach where the key term, Impact Risk (IR), is calculated from estimates of Exposure and Effect Potential

Figure 3 Calculation of Impact Risk from Exposure and Effect Potential which, in turn, can be estimated from respectively the spatial distributions of the stressor (i.e. activities-pressure) and receptor (i.e. ecosystem component) and population dynamics parameters resilience and resistance if quantitative information is available. If lacking, these can be estimated from the boxed terms using categorical scores based on expert judgement (Piet et al., 2023).

Conform the MSFD, the ecosystem components included in the CIA should cover species groups (birds, mammals, reptiles, fish and cephalopods), pelagic- and benthic habitats. Following this MSFD structure, an ecosystem component may thus consist of only one functional biotic group covered by species groups (e.g. birds) or an aggregation of biotic groups covered by habitats (e.g. sublittoral sediment covering bacteria, epifauna, infauna, macroalgae, macrophytes and microphytobenthos). Moreover, the biotic groups determine through their functioning the capacity to supply ecosystem services (Culhane et al. 2018; 2019a,b). To combine the risk estimate per ecosystem component or species group with the Service Supply Potential estimate per functional biotic group, matching the ecosystem components to the biotic groups may be necessary. As described in the previous section

(1.1), to extend the linkage framework to include ecosystem services, the ecosystem components that are aligned to the MSFD (EC, 2017) to those biotic groups identified by Culhane et al (2018) as the most relevant units providing marine ecosystem services. The North Sea LS provides an example of such a cross-linkage table (Table 1).

Table 1. North Sea LS example showing the cross-link between the ecosystem components and the biotic groups used to estimate the impact risk of anthropogenic stressors (i.e., human activities and their pressures) on the Biotic Groups (biotic groups), which through their functioning determine the Capacity to supply ecosystem services. Where there is a match for the biotic groups associated with habitats, this is weighted by the contribution based on habitat extent.

Ecosystem Component #	Extent		Match ecosystem component to biotic group #											
	Contribution	Extent (km ²)	Bacteria	Birds	Cephalopods	Epifauna	Fish	Infauna	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Marine mammals	Microphytobenthos	Phytoplankton	Zooplankton
Deep-sea rock*	0.001	427	X			X								
Deep-sea sediment	0.05	23021	X			X		X						
Sublittoral sediment	0.93	406202	X			X		X	X	X		X		
Circalittoral rock*	0.005	1979	X			X								
Infralittoral rock*	0.0007	298	X			X			X	X		X		
Littoral rock*	0.004	1540	X			X			X	X		X		
Littoral sediment	0.004	1540	X			X		X	X	X		X		
Pelagic water column	1	435008	X			X			X				X	X
Fish & Cephalopods	1	435008			X		X							
Marine mammals	1	435008									X			
Birds	1	435008		X										

* Rock includes other hard substrata.

Note that for this North Sea example reptiles are considered not relevant (and hence not included as ecosystem component and biotic group)

4.3. Service Supply Potential of biotic groups

The studies by Teixeira et al. (2019) and Culhane et al. (2019b) determined their ecosystem services Supply Potential for each biotic group. In these studies, the Service Supply Potential was used to reflect the importance of a biotic group to the supply of ecosystem services and based on a qualitative valuation (i.e., 0, 1, 2) attributed by expert judgement. Using expert judgement-based qualitative weights in this manner can be considered the simplest option. Alternatively, more sophisticated options based on measurable characteristic(s) of the biotic group can be applied to weight the importance of the biotic group-ecosystem services link captured by the Service Supply Potential.

These Service Supply Potential estimates need to reflect that ecosystem services occur both in the ecological and the social systems (Culhane et al., 2019b). For the ecological system, this implies that the supply of ecosystem services is determined by both the amount of biotic groups and their functioning, while for the social system, this implies that human capital is required to turn biotic groups into societal benefits (Elliott, 2023). To estimate the Service Supply Potential per ecosystem services, a distinction is thus required between:

- (1) A strictly ecological system perspective - using quantitative information based on selected metrics (production, biomass) supposed to cover the most fundamental ecological characteristic of the biotic group; and
- (2) a perspective that pre-empt the role of the ecosystem services in the social system - where we anticipate the interaction between the biotic group and the human capital required to produce the societal benefits. This can be covered by expert-judgement-based likelihood of contribution. Although this likelihood of contribution links to the social system, it only considers the ecological contribution and not the societal goods and benefits that are part of the social system.

The North Sea LS provides examples of Service Supply Potential estimations for each of the two perspectives (Appendix 1).

Also, this approach implies that to have a service supply potential, the interaction between ecosystem components and biotic groups is needed. However, CICES 5.1. also considers that ecosystem services may be delivered exclusively from abiotic ecosystem features (e.g., wind energy as a provisioning abiotic ecosystem service or abiotic characteristics of nature that enable active or passive physical and experiential interactions as a cultural abiotic ecosystem service) (see Appendix 2).

4.4. Threats to the capacity to supply ecosystem services

The combination of the CIA (which estimates how the cumulative pressures of all human activities taking place in the marine ecosystem impact each of the ecosystem components that make up marine biodiversity) with the Service Supply Potential (applied to weight the impacts on the ecosystem components to the ecosystem services) derives an estimation of the impacts on the Capacity to supply ecosystem services, for each of the ecosystem services categories. The ecosystem services and their typology can be based on the CICES 5.1 approach (Haines-Young, 2013; Potschin-Young et al., 2018), which is widely acknowledged as the most authoritative reference classification for ecosystem services. Moreover, it is aligned with other ecosystem services classification systems (UN, 2021), such as those used by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA, 2005) and The Economics of Ecosystems

and Biodiversity (TEEB) (Ring et al., 2010) (see also Liqueste et al., 2013). More information on ecosystem services classification can be found in the Background Document “Ecosystem services, functions and processes” (Appendix 2). For the linkage framework, the ecosystem services are distinguished at different levels of aggregation, e.g., Group or Class level, but always comprehensively covering Provisioning, Regulation and Maintenance, and Cultural services (see Table 2).

The different options in the estimation of the Service Supply Potential show the types of *a priori* choices, in terms of the application of available information, that need to be made when calculating how the Capacity to supply ecosystem services for a particular ecosystem is affected by anthropogenic threats. The calculation of the cumulative impacts to supply for each of the different options, in this proof of concept for the North Sea LS, then provides an evaluation of the potential consequences of such choices (Appendix 1). Ultimately, the assessment of the cumulative impacts on the Capacity to supply ecosystem services can be represented in a Sankey diagram (Figure 4) based on the cascade model (Haines-Young, 2010), showing the flows of the relative Impact Risk contributions throughout the linkage framework consisting of Activity-Pressure-biotic group-ecosystem services chains. An R-package to create a Sankey representation will be provided during this project on GitHub (<https://github.com/>) and CRAN (The Comprehensive R Archive Network, <https://cran.r-project.org/>).

Figure 4. Sankey diagram for the North Sea LS, showing how human activities and their pressures impact the biotic groups, their functioning, and subsequently the capacity to supply ecosystem services (ecosystem services). The colours represent the flow belonging to each service: blue/green = Provisioning ecosystem services, yellow = Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services, purple = Cultural ecosystem services).

Table 2. Likelihood of contribution to the capacity to supply ES (according to CICES 5.1) per functional biotic group. The three codes indicate High contribution (1), Medium (0.01), Low (0.001) or none () (Piet et al., 2024).

Section	Division	Group	Class	Bacteria	Birds	Cephalopods	Epifauna	Fish	Infauna	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Marine mammals	Microphytobenthos	Phytoplankton	Zooplankton	
Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Plants cultivated by in-situ aquaculture grown for nutritional purposes							H						
			Fibres and other materials from in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)							H	L		L	L		
			Plants cultivated by in-situ aquaculture grown as an energy source							H	L		L	L		
		Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture for nutritional purposes				H	H	L							
			Fibres and other materials from animals grown by in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		L	L	H	H	L				L			L
			Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture as an energy source					H					L			
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi and algae) used for nutrition								H	H		L	L	
			Fibres and other materials from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)								H	H		L	L	
			Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi and algae) used as a source of energy								H	H		L	L	
		Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for nutritional purposes		L	H	H	H	H				L			L
			Fibres and other materials from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		L	H	H	H	H				L			L
			Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used as a source of energy					H					L			
	Genetic material from all biota	Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	Seeds, spores and other plant materials collected for maintaining or establishing a population							H	H		H	H		
			Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties							H	H		H	H		
			Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the design and construction of new biological entities							H	H		H	H		
			Animal material collected to maintain or establish a population		H	H	H	H	H				H			H
			Wild animals (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties		H	H	H	H	H				H			H
			Individual genes extracted from organisms for the design and construction of new biological entities	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	H			H		H	H	H		H	H	H	
			Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Smell reduction	H	H		H		H							

	Regulation of physical, chemical, and biological conditions	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Visual screening	H	H		H		H						
			Control of erosion rates				H		H	H	H		H		
			Buffering and attenuation of mass movement				H		H	H	H		H		
			Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)				H		H	H	H		H		
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	'Gamete' dispersal		H		H	H							
			Seed dispersal		H			H							
			Maintaining nursery populations and habitats (Including gene pool protection)	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Pest and disease control	Pest control (including invasive species)	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Disease control	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Regulation of soil quality	Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Water conditions	Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration							H	H		H	H	
Cultural	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting	Physical and experiential interactions with the natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions	M	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	M	M
			Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through passive or observational interactions	M	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	M	M
		Intellectual and representative interactions with the natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable scientific investigation or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Characteristics of living systems that enable education and training	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of culture or heritage		H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H			
			Characteristics of living systems that enable aesthetic experiences	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
	Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with the natural environment	Elements of living systems that have symbolic meaning		H	H	H	H		H	H	H			H
			Elements of living systems that have sacred or religious meaning		H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H			H
			Elements of living systems used for entertainment or representation	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Characteristics or features of living systems that have an existence value	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Characteristics or features of living systems that have an option or bequest value	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H		H	H

4.5. The link between the capacity to supply ecosystem services and GES

The approach to assess cumulative impacts on ecosystem services proposed here (Figure 1) and demonstrated for the North Sea LS (Appendix 1) addresses the ecosystem components conforming with the MSFD (EC, 2017) and extends these with the biotic groups identified by Culhane et al (2018) as the most relevant units providing marine ecosystem services. Biotic groups play a key role in connecting the CIA through the Service Supply Potential to estimate the potential threats to the Capacity to supply ecosystem services. Similarly, the ecosystem components are key to link this to the concept of GES and the indicators used to assess progress towards this goal. This has several implications:

- Both the MSFD assessments (based on specific indicators and, sometimes, thresholds for each of the ecosystem components) and the CIA estimate of Impact Risk per ecosystem component provide complementary perspectives on the wider 'status' of the ecosystem component. Therefore, the assumption is that if GES is not achieved for a specific ecosystem component, the Impact Risk from the cumulative pressures is too high. Note, however, that there is no one-to-one relationship here. Higher Impact Risk (and thus lower abundance) of ecosystem components results in a reduced Capacity to supply ecosystem services. Or, in other words, the degree of impact of each ecosystem component, as reflected by the Impact Risk estimate, determines the degree to which the Capacity to supply each ecosystem service is impacted.
- For each of the ecosystem components that are not in GES, it needs to be determined which sectoral activities and which pressures cause the main threats. Mitigating those threats should result in an increased Capacity to supply ecosystem services. However, it may result in a reduction of the input of (a selection of) the human capital required to turn this Capacity to supply ecosystem services into specific societal benefits that contribute to human well-being.

An application, linking marine environmental status with the provision of ecosystem services and human benefits, using as a case study the anchovy of the Bay of Biscay, can be seen in Appendix 3.

4.6. Conclusion and future work

This guidance describes a cumulative impact assessment of human activities and their pressures acting on the ecosystem components that make up biodiversity in combination with an assessment of the potential to supply ecosystem services per biotic group. Application of

the approach will show how the human activities and their pressures impact the ecosystem components and their functioning and subsequently via the biotic groups the capacity to supply ecosystem services. Appendix 1 demonstrates the approach for the North Sea LS. With this guidance and decision tree, the LSs can assess the anthropogenic cumulative threats to the capacity to supply ecosystem services. To that end, a capacity-building workshop has been organised (January 2024) for which all LSs have expressed interest. Several LSs have already applied the first of four steps of the decision tree (Figure 1): 1) Linkage Framework; 2) CIA; 3) Service Supply Potential of Biotic Groups; 4) CIA on the Capacity to Supply Ecosystem Services.. The approach was further elaborated at a SCAIRM session during the annual meeting 2024 in Istanbul and specific questions were addressed. Next workshop for all LS will take place online September 25, 2024 and will focus on step 2, including practical examples as requested by the LSs.

5. Revision of methods to test tipping points and thresholds (Task 3.2)

An ecosystem tipping point involves a threshold past which an ecosystem transitions from one stable state to another (Scheffer et al., 2001). The change in stable state is expected to follow a non-linear bifurcation driven by the accumulation of pressure on the ecosystem over time, which gradually erodes resilience until a small additional increase in pressure is sufficient to cause a shift in ecosystem state (Scheffer et al., 2001; Folke et al., 2004). Once an ecosystem has shifted to an alternative stable state, recovery to the previous reference state tends to be very complex and lengthy (Moreno-Mateos et al., 2020; Hemraj et al., 2022). Natural biological systems are subjected to multi-layered stressors that interact in different ways (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic, or additively) and drive different patterns of ecosystem-level response (Harley et al., 2017). As opposed to single pressure, detecting the non-linear responses of multiple variables under various combinations of interacting pressures remains particularly difficult because of the complexity of interactions between response variables and pressures.

Under the contemporary Anthropocene, cumulative pressures are exerted on marine and terrestrial ecosystems (Halpern et al., 2008; Watson and Venter, 2019). The overlap and complex interactions between these pressures influence the response of the ecosystem (Figure 4). This is because ecosystems seldom respond to only one isolated environmental factor, and two or more stressors can act synergistically or antagonistically to drive changes in ecosystem resilience, causing an accelerated or delayed shift in the ecosystem's stable state. Therefore, based on the pressures and response variables being investigated, it may be difficult to detect tipping points from empirical data. Recent challenges to the concept that thresholds leading to tipping points can be identified from empirical data instead suggest that there are more gradual shifts in response magnitude in relation to increasing pressure, and that bi-modality or multi-modality, even if they existed, are too difficult to identify because of the noisiness of ecological data (Hillebrand et al., 2020, 2023). However, most studies tend to be primarily based on individual environmental drivers and ecosystem components, thus probing the questioning of which ecological dimensions (e.g., ecosystem type, species composition, keystone species or functional groups) and scales exhibit threshold responses and to what extent detecting tipping points from one individual pressure at a time is reliable (Dudney and Suding, 2020; Spake et al., 2022).

Figure 5. Model holistic ecosystem response to multi-layered stressors. A shift in a stable state may be delayed due to multiple ecological mechanisms (e.g., population dynamics, community interactions, functional redundancy, evolutionary mechanisms, extinction debt). However, it is often preceded by a loss of resilience and stability. Recovery to a reference state is generally lengthy and complex, requiring careful ecosystem management. The figure was drawn by the authors for the report.

The problem remains that a certain combination of pressures can drive a shift in a different stable state, while the same ecosystem might not change from a different combination of pressures or a single pressure. For example, the synergistic interaction of increased nutrient and CO₂ concentrations accelerated the expansion of filamentous turfs at the expense of calcifying algae in an Australian rocky reef, while nutrients or CO₂ alone did not have such a drastic effect (Russell et al., 2009). On the other hand, the antagonistic effect of multiple stressors may cause a delay in the tipping point. In a mesocosm experiment, the introduction of the invasive species zebra mussel delayed a shift in ecosystem state due to increased nutrient input by controlling the growing algal biomass (Dzialowski and Jessie, 2009). In addition, the combination of multiple stressors may act synergistically, antagonistically, or additively depending on the intensity of each individual stressor (Maucieri et al., 2023).

These examples show that detecting tipping points in ecosystems from multiple stressors remains complex as it requires some level of incorporation of the interaction between the stressors in a multivariate manner, a consideration that few methods currently incorporate. The other problem is that bifurcation at tipping-points may occur in different ways (e.g., fold bifurcation, pitchfork bifurcation, Hopf bifurcation, or transcritical bifurcation), that is, the shift of an ecosystem from one stable state to another can follow different pathways, including more gradual shifts. In addition, bifurcation may be delayed in relation to the peak of combined environmental stressors (Figure 1)

(Hillebrand et al., 2023). From an ecological perspective, these different pathways and lags can be driven by variation in response due to different levels of community interaction, species-specific responses, the resilience of the ecosystem, functional redundancy within the ecosystem, evolutionary tipping points, or lags driven by extinction debt (Tilman et al., 1994; Folke et al., 2004; Botero et al., 2015; Connell and Ghedini, 2015; Dakos et al., 2019; Céréghino et al., 2022). Altogether, these ecological mechanisms render the multivariate response of ecosystems complex, meaning that using a single or only a few ecosystem variables to identify tipping points is likely to lead to inaccurate and unreliable outcomes.

Another concern is the ability to predict how close an ecosystem is to its tipping point, especially from an environmental management perspective. Ecosystems reach a tipping point when increasing pressures drive a reduction in resilience and stability to a point where a small additional increase in pressure will cause a shift in the ecosystem state. As resilience and stability decrease, the recovery time to the original equilibrium increases, resulting in a “critical slowing down” (Figure 1)(van Nes and Scheffer, 2004; Dakos et al., 2012). Simultaneously, the closer the ecosystem reaches its tipping point, the more the tendency for the ecosystem to show early warning signals (EWS), including higher variance, autocorrelation, and skewness in response (Scheffer, 2010; Lenton, 2011). Past this stage, the ecosystem tips into an alternative state.

Consequently, methods of predicting how close an ecosystem is to its tipping point often involve an estimation of variance, autocorrelation, skewness, or recovery time from small perturbations. However, these are not as straightforward and tend to be data quality/quantity dependent (Andersen et al., 2009; Dakos et al., 2012). For example, variance in ecosystem response close to a tipping point can be reduced if ecosystems become less sensitive to environmental variability or “critical slowing down” reduces the ecosystems’ capacity to follow high-frequency fluctuations (Dakos et al., 2012). In such cases, predicting closeness to a tipping point based on variance becomes less reliable. In addition, evolutionary dynamics such as evolutionary rescue, phenotypic plasticity, trait variation and redundancy, or physiological performance play an important part in driving ecosystem response by influencing resilience to perturbations or delays in response, therefore accelerating or delaying the occurrence of tipping points (Harley et al., 2017; Dakos et al., 2019; Chaparro-Pedraza and de Roos, 2020; Vanselow et al., 2022). Subsequently, to increase the reliability of predicting state shifts, especially from an environmental management perspective, it is important to understand how the ecosystem behaves as a function of combined ecosystem components and pressure interaction.

Current advances in detecting or forecasting major shifts in ecosystem state highlight that a broader ecosystem approach is essential (Dakos et al., 2019; Dudney and Suding, 2020; Kéfi et al., 2022; Hillebrand et al., 2023). There are presently numerous techniques available for detecting or predicting

tipping points from univariate or multivariate ecological data. However, few of these are specifically geared towards detecting or predicting tipping points in ecosystems through the combination of non-linear interactions between multiple ecosystem components and pressures. Considering the challenges linked to complex interactions between the intensities of pressures, and the ever-growing complexity upon inclusion of more ecosystem components and pressures, it is difficult to devise an ideal method that comprehensively and accurately identifies or predicts tipping points from spatial or temporal ecological data. Nonetheless, here, we review the literature to put forward some of the better techniques that come close to the inclusion of multiple variables for identifying or predicting changes in ecosystem resilience and stability that lead to state shifts. We aim to delve into the advantages and limitations of such techniques in providing a holistic approach to evaluating shifts in ecosystem state.

5.1. Go-to techniques for detecting state shifts

Several techniques currently exist for detecting shifts in empirical data that convey thresholds. Among the most applied techniques are segmented type regressions, curve derivative based models (e.g., Gaussian model, Generalized Additive Model (GAM), continuous interaction models, threshold nonadditive formulation), multivariate analysis-based methods (e.g., Principal Component Analysis (PCA)), “significant zero crossings” (SiZer), or boosted regression tree-based methods (and other clustering type analysis). While many of these methods are geared in one way or another towards detecting non-linear shifts in data (either they are fully non-linear or they utilise some type of sequential analysis to identify non-linear breakpoints), they tend to be more applicable for low dimensionality data where fewer variables are more easily managed.

To better utilise data of high dimensionality, techniques such as combined multivariate analysis (Vasilakopoulos and Marshall, 2015), threshold indicator taxa analysis (TITAN; Baker and King, 2010), or Gradient Forest (Ellis et al., 2012) have been developed. However, the common drawback remains their inability to integrate the synergistic, antagonistic, or additive interactions between variables (whether ecosystem components or stressors). Thus, even if multiple variables are used to infer shifts in a stable state (e.g., community shifts), variables are either analysed in a pairwise manner (i.e., different combinations of one predictor against one response variable) or analysed using linear multivariate techniques that still reduce dimensionality (e.g., PCA-based techniques). Therefore, no technique is currently adequately geared to detect thresholds from the combination of non-linear interactions between variables and high-dimensional data.

For example, we delved into 508 papers that seek to detect thresholds that cause a non-linear shift in ecological data using multiple variables. Among these studies that incorporate non-linear methods, 37% sought to determine the effect of a predictor on at least two response variables and 6% used at least two predictors to identify shifts in a response variable. However, all these studies reduce the dimensionality of their datasets before inferring state shifts by analysing pairwise interactions between predictor and response variables or using a dimensionality reduction technique (Figure 6). Therefore, these studies also fail to account for the interactive effects of multiple variables on each other. Similarly, 29% of the total studies simultaneously incorporate multiple predictors and multiple response variables, but all reduce dimensionality and disregard the interactive non-linear interactions between variables. Finally, 17% of these studies were reviews of processes in specific ecosystems or broader reviews, and 11% only looked at one response variable and one predictor. Below, we decipher a few of the most common methods for identifying thresholds of state shift to determine some of their advantages and limitations regarding incorporating non-linear dynamics and inter-variable interaction.

Figure 6. Categorisation of studies that utilise or describe methods for identifying thresholds. Studies were classified based on the dimensionality of data. Some of the most common methods employed are also included in each category. Green arrows show that these methods either reduce the dimensionality of data before formal analysis, or disregard intervariable interactions when running analyses. The figure was drawn by the authors for the report.

Segmented or changepoint regression

Segmented regression is a technique that identifies discontinuities in data. This type of regression can be based on non-linear learning (regression with a “hinge” function where the trajectory of data transitions smoothly (Carstensen & Weydmann, 2012; Ficetola & Denoël, 2009; Toms & Lesperance, 2003). It also has the advantage of identifying the specific value at which the data trajectory changes. The non-linear

method is based on models that allow for a smooth transition between two segments of different slopes (Figure 6a). Several smooth transition models can be applied for this purpose, such as hyperbolic-tangent, LOESS, and others (see Carstensen & Weydmann, 2012; Toms & Lesperance, 2003), and the fit of the models are evaluated by calculating the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

Changepoint regression works similarly but does not identify a change in slope. Instead, it focuses on separating segments of response variable Y where the mean and variance change along predictor X using sequential F tests (Figure 7b). Both segmented and changepoint regressions are commonly used to determine shifts in univariate or multivariate data sets, including multiple ecosystem components or stressors. However, they can only infer shifts in one ecosystem component against one stressor at a time. In the case of multiple variables, one can either alternate between different pairs of ecosystem components and stressors (e.g., Berdugo et al., 2020) or utilise multivariate analysis of ecosystem components to identify shifts of multiple components against time or a stressor. For example, they are commonly used together with Principal Coordinate Analysis or Multidimensional Scaling of ecological communities to determine where along a time series or stressor gradient the community shifts (e.g., Xuan et al., 2019).

Figure 7. Illustration of the segmented (A) and changepoint (B) methods for detecting shifts in empirical data. Segmented regression is generally based on grid-search type algorithms utilising a grid of candidate breakpoint values, while changepoint analysis is generally based on sequential F-test (b). The figure was drawn by the authors for the report.

In either of these alternatives, segmented and changepoint regressions are unable to capture and use interactions between different variables to infer shifts in the state of the variables. In addition, some of the drawbacks of segmented or changepoint regression include the possibility of overfitting or

underfitting depending on the number of target breakpoints, the level of noise in the data, and the non-linearity of the data since the models assume that data can be segmented into smaller linear regressions. Therefore, segmented or changepoint regressions may not always identify the correct breakpoint in the data, and small variations or transformations of the data may cause large differences in threshold identification (Francesco-Ficetola and Denoel, 2009; Matthews et al., 2014; Gkioulekas and Papageorgiou, 2019).

Curve based methods

An alternative, purely non-linear, method for threshold detection involves fitting a curvilinear model to the data and identifying the points at which major changes in trajectory occur. Curve fitting is commonly used for detecting thresholds in different disciplines because of the multitude of possibilities available for fitting different types of datasets. For example, Quadratic, Gaussian, or Weibull functions are often applied in thermal biology to estimate temperature thresholds of the metabolic activity or thermal performance (Angilletta, 2006; Sinclair et al., 2016). On the other hand, Log-logistic type functions are often more appropriately applied in dose-response types of analysis, such as in ecotoxicology or biochemistry (Ritz et al., 2015). Finally, GAMs, or modified versions such as threshold-GAM, are widely used in many ecological contexts for the identification of thresholds from large datasets that may have different types of predictor variables (continuous, categorical, or ordinal), datasets that contain missing values, and datasets with one or more potential turning points (Benedetti et al., 2009; Samhuri et al., 2017; Aspin et al., 2018).

Thresholds from fitted curves can be detected from changes in the first and second derivatives of the curves, which represent the slope and inflexion, respectively. The derivatives can be calculated individually for any curvilinear model and used to identify a threshold. Alternatively, multiple derivatives from different bandwidths of a curvilinear model can be calculated by SiZer (Sonderegger et al., 2009) and plotted on a SiZer map to identify a threshold based on the best fitting model bandwidth. The advantage of pairing curvilinear models with SiZer is that it can accommodate multiple curve functions (e.g., smoothing splines, LOESS, locally weighed polynomial), calculate derivatives from multiple bandwidths, and use a map of derivatives against time or a stressor to find the threshold value from the best fitting curve and calculate a confidence interval. Using curve-based models for threshold detection allows for the application of purely non-linear techniques that can capture different types of relationships between variables and effectively identify a point where the predictor causes a non-linear change in the response variable.

However, the problem regarding the integration of multiple parameters and their combined interactions remains unresolved. This is because, in their current use, curve-based models have

primarily (not always) been applied for one-on-one regressions. Nonetheless, they offer the possibility of extending the analysis to more variables. For example, GAMs can include multiple covariates, although these are primarily weights rather than interactive effects. In addition, GAMs such as threshold-GAM or continuous interaction GAM provide the ability to estimate interactive effects between more than two variables (Ciannelli et al., 2004). Similarly, log-logistic models (dose-response) commonly used in ecotoxicology studies also offer the possibility of deriving the influence of a predictor variable on the effect that another predictor variable has on a response variable, that is, implementing antagonistic, synergistic, or additive effects (Bjergager et al., 2017). While the possibility of incorporating multiple variables exists, the appropriate application of GAMs or dose-response models to infer thresholds from multiple interacting predictor and response variables is yet to be implemented.

Multivariate analysis based

The application of multivariate analysis to detect thresholds allows the use of large datasets with high dimensionality. This, therefore, provides the opportunity to infer shifts in a stable state of a whole community or ecosystem over time or in response to a stressor. However, the first step in this analysis of large datasets with high dimensionality is to use a dimensionality reduction technique, such as Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) or PCA, that maintains the variables of the data but seeks to explain as much of the variation in the data with the fewest variables (Andersen et al., 2009; Van Der Maaten et al., 2009). In PCA, for example, each sample is allocated a PC score, which denotes its position from the first PC line (PC1), the latter passing through the mean of variables in a way that reflects the most variation in the dataset (Abdi and Williams, 2010). The PC1 scores of the samples can then be plotted against time or a stressor to identify whether there is a large change in PC scores over time or along a stressor gradient and where along the temporal or stressor gradient this change occurs. A segmented or changepoint regression is commonly used to identify the time or stressor value where the shift in PC1 scores occurs (e.g., Xuan et al., 2019; Tonno et al., 2021). The majority of ecological studies that aim at identifying thresholds from multivariate data tend to be based on PCA or MDS.

While these methods deliver good estimations of when an ecosystem or community may shift, several issues make them inadequate for estimating interactive and non-linear effects. Firstly, PCA or MDS are strictly linear-based dimensionality reduction techniques, meaning that any non-linear relationship between variables is instantly disregarded. In order to account for non-linear relationships, PCA or MDS may be replaced by other techniques, such as non-linear Canonical Correlation Analysis or Stochastic Neighbour Embedding. Secondly, they focus on the variables that produce the most variation in the dataset. That is, they disregard the effects of some variables and their potential

interactive effects with other variables. As such, they do not represent full variation in the set of variables since only the PC1 scores are generally utilised. Finally, PC1 scores are generally plotted against time or one stressor at a time, meaning that interactive effects of multiple stressors are not accounted for.

5.2. Detection methods that incorporate multiple predictor and response variables

Machine learning methods

The past decade or so has seen an exponential rise in the application of machine learning techniques for vast ecological methods. Naturally, the development of machine learning techniques such as regression trees and random forest have benefitted the methods for detecting tipping points (e.g., Lintz et al., 2011; Ellis et al., 2012). Among the most versatile methods incorporating multiple predictor and response variables in the detection of thresholds and ecosystem state change is the use of gradient forest (Ellis et al., 2012), an extension of random forest aimed at identifying overall ecosystem component compositional changes based on pressure gradients. The method identifies splits in each response variable dataset based on the predictor gradient and synthesizes cross-validated and dimensionless R^2 values and accuracy importance measures from random forests for each response variable. Consequently, it results in a ranking of predictors based on their importance in driving compositional turnover in response variables and indicates where along the pressure gradient such compositional turnover occurs. It can also identify and rank the response variables that are most impacted by the majority of predicted variables. The intensities of the highest-ranked predictors at which most response variables split are considered thresholds that will likely cause the compositions to tip into an alternative stable state. While the method includes multiple response and predictor variables and identifies the predictors that are most influential on driving tipping points, a major drawback of the Gradient Forest is the incapacity of implementing interaction between variables, that is, non-linear interaction between two or more response or predictor variables (as opposed to Boosted Regression Tree, for example, which can integrate interactive predictor variable effects). In addition, the method is based on one-to-one inference of predictor impact on response variables, although the conditional importance (in relation to other predictors) of predictors is considered. In that sense, this method provides an avenue for including multiple variables but fails to implement non-linear interactions and high-dimensional data.

More recently, a multiple-factor model was utilised to incorporate the combined effects of multiple pressures on driving tipping points in phytoplankton productivity and species composition globally

(Ban et al., 2022). The model included ensemble learning and a stacking method used for stressors that combines several individual models to obtain better performance by training the first-level regressors with the training set and then the second-level regressors as a meta-regressor using predictions from the first-level regressors as input (see Breiman, 1996; Ganaie et al., 2022). Ban et al. (2022) also applied Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) algorithms to determine the effect of multiple stressors on phytoplankton production and species composition. MLP models are neural network-based models capable of learning non-linear functions between an input and the output layer, including one or more non-linear layers in between (see Taud and Mas, 2018). Following these models of incorporating the effects of multiple pressures, Ban et al. (2022) then analysed the changes in phytoplankton productivity and species richness trends as a function of multi-stressors over time. The use of MLP or stacking methods opens the way towards better integrating interactive multi-stressor impacts on response variables, even if phytoplankton interspecies interaction is not accounted for here. Unfortunately, another issue remains, i.e., a lack of transparency on how exactly multiple stressors interact.

Combined multivariate method

A commonly applied method for detecting shifts in ecosystem state utilises multivariate plotting (PCA, MDS) of ecosystem components and subsequent plots of the multivariate scores (e.g., PC1 scores) against time or pressure of choice to detect where along the timescale or pressure intensity a major change in PC scores occurs (e.g., Hare and Mantua, 2000; Möllmann et al., 2009; Xuan et al., 2019). This shows whether there is a major shift in the overall composition of the ecosystem components and where this shift occurs along the timescale or pressure intensity gradient. The common problems with this method are (1) its inability to capture non-linear relationships between ecosystem components, (2) distortion effects by reduction of dimensionality, (3) the inability to infer the effect of covarying pressures (two or more pressures) on ecosystem components, and (4) it is mainly graphical, unless it is paired with segmented type regressions.

Nonetheless, assuming a system where (1) and (2) are of low concern, multivariate-based methods have seen a major development in terms of incorporation of the effects of multiple pressures in determining tipping points (Vasilakopoulos and Marshall, 2015). In brief, this is achieved using PC scores obtained from PCAs of response variables (RV PC) and predictors (Pred PC). Independently, shifts in PC scores along a timeline are detected by a sequential regime shift detection method, and the response PC that represents the shift between alternate states and the predictor PCs are incorporated into a GAM and threshold-GAM model to determine the effects of combined predictors on combined response variables; hence, we termed it “combined multivariate method”. The RV PC is plotted against the Pred PC, and different models are fitted (fit of null, linear, quadratic, cubic) at the

alternate states to determine the relationship between RV PC and Pred PC at each state. The estimated position of a tipping point (e.g., which year) can be visualised by adding a line of the best-fitted models to the plot and associating each data point on the graph with its categorical value (e.g., the year). Consequently, the year in which the fitted model shows the largest change (e.g., change in slope or a breakpoint) denotes the year when the combined predictor variables caused a large shift in the combined response variables. Subsequent addition to this method includes the analysis of one- or two-year lags in pressure component as explanatory variables in the GAM and threshold-GAM models to identify whether delays in ecosystem response to pressures are involved (Vasilakopoulos et al., 2017). While this multivariate approach integrates multiple pressures in determining tipping points using multiple ecosystem components, the inherent issues regarding its inability to integrate non-linear relationships between either ecosystem components or pressure remains a limitation. In addition, the multivariability is reduced to univariability because it reduces the variation of multiple response variables and predictor variables to one response principal component and one predictor principal component, which are then used in a one-to-one regression.

Dose-response based method

Dose-response methods are commonly used in biochemistry, ecotoxicology, and microbiology. Their application involves identifying well-defined changes in the response of a substance based on the concentration (dose) of another (Ruberg, 1995; Goutelle et al., 2008). Dose-response analyses are mostly based on log-logistic type regressions that can identify the dose of a substance required to cause a large non-linear shift in the response of another substance. Responses can be continuous, binary, or discrete (Ritz et al., 2015). The application of this method in identifying tipping points using pressure and response variable empirical data can be derived from the determination of Half Maximal Effective Concentration (EC_{50}). EC_{50} represents the concentration of a substance that causes 50% of the maximal response of another. In ecological words, it would represent the pressure intensity resulting in 50% of the maximal response of an ecosystem component (Figure 7). EC_{50} on the log-logistic model is situated where the gradient of the line is the steepest, meaning that a small additional increase in pressure can drive a large change in ecosystem component response, similar to tipping points.

Dose-response can be applied using multiple simultaneously occurring pressures to identify tipping points in response variables. To achieve this, one may plot the log-logistic response of a variable against a gradient of pressure A, given different intensities of pressure B (e.g., 0%, 20%, 40%, 60%; Figure 3) and determine the new EC_{50} of pressure A based on the intensity of pressure B (Figure 8). A threshold for synergy can be considered as the intensity of pressure B that decreases the EC_{50} of pressure A by

another 50% (Bjergager et al., 2017). For example, in Figure 8, 60% additional pressure B decreases the EC₅₀ of pressure A by 50%. On the other hand, adding 20% intensity of pressure C has an antagonistic effect and delays the response of the ecosystem component to pressure A.

Figure 8. Dose-response representation of ecosystem response in relation to interacting pressures at various intensities. The red dotted lines represent a 50% reduction in ecosystem component response driven by interacting pressures (synergistic effect of multiple pressures). The green dotted line represents an antagonistic effect of combined pressures on ecosystem component response. The analysis presented here is based on Bjergager et al. (2017). The figure was drawn by the authors for the report.

The advantage of using dose-response models to identify tipping points is that, theoretically, one can implement a large suit of pressures in a stepwise manner and determine their cumulative impacts at different intensities. In addition, dose-response models allow one to take a more conservative approach by defining a tipping point as the EC₂₅, for example, rather than EC₅₀. Some of the limitations of the dose-response models, however, include the growing demand for data quality and quantity with an increasing number of pressures, whereby one would require splitting data based on intensities of a given pressure and have enough data quality and quantity to reliably calculate the EC₅₀ based on a secondary pressure, and so forth. Secondly, while does-response models can work well with multiple pressures, implementing the response of multiple response variables can remain tricky as that would require some multi-component index (e.g., multifunctionality index, diversity index) but may still be incapable of incorporating non-linear relationships between response variables.

5.3. Incorporating thresholds in determining the effect of multiple pressures on ecosystems

This method is derived from calculating an ecosystem multiservice index (based on multifunctionality index (see below) and determining how that index increases or declines based on the number of pressures that exceed a given intensity threshold (Figure 9; Rillig et al., 2023). The multiservice index (Rillig et al., 2023) is based on a multifunctionality index (Byrnes et al., 2014; Wagg et al., 2014) and can be translated into a multicomponent index by substituting ecosystem functions or services with ecosystem components. The basis of the multifunctionality index is to incorporate the simultaneous provision of different functions in an ecosystem (Manning et al., 2018).

Figure 9. Identification of shift in ecosystem multiservice index based on the number of stressors and their intensities. Coloured lines represent regression lines of the multiservice index against the number of stressors at different intensities (A). The standardized effect of stressors operating at different thresholds is represented by the thick turquoise line (B). The thin turquoise lines represent 99% confidence. When the 99% confidence passes below zero, the combination of stressors significantly reduces the services provided by the ecosystem, indicating a possible state change. The analysis presented here is based on Rillig et al. (2023). The figure was fully redrawn by the authors for the report based on Rillig et al. (2023) (no permission required).

There are several methods for calculating a multifunctionality index, such as average weighed multifunctionality (Byrnes et al., 2014; Maestre et al., 2012), multi-threshold multifunctionality (Soliveres et al., 2016), or the principal component multifunctionality (Díaz et al., 2016; Manning et al., 2018), each having certain benefits or limitations in terms of what is accounted for or disregarded (e.g., equally weighed functions or different levels of contribution from each function). However, fundamentally, they all provide an estimation of the functional state of the ecosystem through the contribution of multiple functions. The estimation of the overall functional state can be translated to an overall estimation of the ecosystem state if functions are replaced by ecosystem components. Therefore, by using a multiservice index and combinations of pressures, it is possible to derive when

an ecosystem has or will change stable state given different combinations of pressure intensities. While this method is based on reduction of soil ecosystem services from multiple stressors, the technique can be adapted to marine ecosystem components and stressors to determine the extent to which the number and intensity of stressors cause shifts in multiple ecosystem components.

To identify the impact of multiple stressors, each exceeding different thresholds of intensity, Rillig et al. (2023) clustered individual stressors into broader groups (e.g., lead and mercury concentrations will be grouped as heavy metals) by standardising and averaging individual stressors to avoid multicollinearity and allow a more fair and weighted assessment of the influence of the number of stressor groups exceeding different thresholds. Assuming that when one or more stressor groups exceed an intensity threshold (e.g., 75% of predefined maximum stressor intensity), the response of the ecosystem can shift, the number of stressor groups in their dataset that passed multiple thresholds (iteratively increasing by 1%; e.g., 1%, 2%, ..., 99%) of maximum stressor levels were then calculated (e.g., 8 out of 8 stressor groups passed 10% maximum intensity, or 5 out of 8 stressor groups passed 45% maximum intensity). To measure the relationship of multiple stressors acting together on ecosystem multiservices, the number of stressor groups passing a given threshold value (e.g., the 5 stressor groups that exceeded 45%) were correlated with the multiservices index using linear regression or Spearman correlation. Each regression was bootstrapped 100 times and deemed significantly influential on the multiservice index when the 95% confidence interval did not overlap with zero (Figure 8). By examining the impact of multiple combinations of pressures at different intensities on a multicomponent index, one is able to identify which pressure combinations and which intensities synergistically or antagonistically change the ecosystem's state (Figure 8).

5.4. Predicting how close an ecosystem is to an alternative stable state

As an ecosystem approaches a tipping point, its resilience and stability decline, and multiple parameters subsequently change (e.g., variance, response to stressors, autocorrelation), causing a critical slowing down. The extent to which these parameters change can be considered EWS of tipping points, that is, an increasing trend in variance, autocorrelation, or response time to a stressor signal that the ecosystem is approaching a tipping point. Effectively measuring and forecasting these EWS parameters, or resilience directly, can estimate how far an ecosystem is from a major shift in a stable state. While increasing variance, autocorrelation and skewness have formed the basis of forecasting tipping points, recent advancements in statistical and computer science have devised new approaches to forecasting tipping points, including from multivariate datasets.

A recent R package formulated by O'Brien et al. (2023a) provides a strong suite of methods for measuring EWS or resilience from multivariate datasets: multivariate EWS, machine learning model, and resilience measures. The Multivariate EWS methods are based on several EWS indicators across either averaged time series, dimension reduction, or others. The averaged time series EWS are derived from Dakos (2018), which estimates community resilience indicators in the presence of correlated environmental stressors. They assumed that changes in environmental stressors follow a stepwise pattern and that at each level of stressor, the stationary dynamics of the community can be measured. Resilience was measured from the sum of all species biomasses in the community to explore the overall change in the community biomass. At each level of stressor, the model was run for 500-time steps to discard transients, and then the mean standard deviation and average autocorrelation were measured from the last 100-time steps. Finally, a community-level index of variability was calculated from the square root of the maximum eigenvalue of the variance-covariance matrix. Dakos (2018) also investigated the use of a single species indicator of overall community shift; however, the reliability of this approach was much less compared to the whole community approach. Therefore, we do not discuss this in detail, but the methods remain available for further exploration and development, and can also be used in the EWS methods package (O'Brien et al., 2023a).

The dimension reduction methods are based on Weinans et al. (2019) and include measuring the minimum eigenvalue of the dominant maximum autocorrelation factor (MAF), the autocorrelation of the first MAF, the autocorrelation of the first principal component, and the variance of the first principal component. While these methods all indicate decreasing resilience, their applications are dataset-dependent. The autocorrelation-based methods are less robust with short time series but perform better with noisy datasets than variance-based methods. Nonetheless, all four methods can be applied in predicting EWS of changing resilience in ecosystems. In addition to averaged time series and dimension reduction methods, measuring the maximum eigenvalue of the covariance matrix of multiple time series (Chen et al., 2019), maximum element of the covariance matrix of the community network (Suweis and D'Odorico, 2014), and the extent to which each time series inform each other (through first-order autoregression or spatial correlation; Quax et al., 2013) are alternative useful methods of determining EWS from multivariate data.

As an alternative to multivariate statistics, machine learning models, such as deep learning modelling that uses coupled long short-term memory and fully convolutional network sub-module routines (Deb et al., 2022), are also available for predicting critical transitions. The idea behind the method involves training a deep neural network upon non-linear mathematical models that encompass different types of stable state transitions: fold bifurcation, pitchfork bifurcation, Hopf bifurcation, and transcritical bifurcation (Scheffer et al., 2012; Kéfi et al., 2013). The overall model can then be used to predict the

type of transition the dataset being analysed is likely to follow the closest. It estimates the probability of the dataset following the different transition types rather than the probability of a tipping point happening. This means that this method can give an indication of the trend of the dataset and which type of stable state transition can be expected.

The final method for forecasting tipping points from complex multivariate datasets involves measuring resilience more directly. The resilience measurement method is grounded on estimating changes in the dominant eigenvalue of an ecosystem’s Jacobian under the empirical dynamic modelling (EDM) framework (O’Brien et al., 2023a; Grziwotz et al., 2023). This involves extracting information about the ecosystem’s stability through time (here, the dominant eigenvalue of the Jacobian through time) from a reconstructed ‘shadow’ attractor (Figure 10). Under Taken’s Theorem, all the time series within a natural ecosystem (e.g., all possible ecosystem components and pressures) can be embedded into one attractor. Since this attractor is created from all the combined time series, it maintains the original fluctuations within each time series but also contains information about the interaction between these time series (e.g., correlations, lags in correlation; Sugihara et al., 2012). Therefore, using such an attractor, one can derive broad information about the whole system (e.g., how the whole combination of time series varies over time).

Figure 10. Dynamic eigenvalue (DEV) based approach of predicting closeness to bifurcation and type of bifurcation that can be expected from a compilation of ecosystem component and pressure data. The approach combines multiple time series (A) into a ‘shadow’ attractor (B) to calculate sequential Jacobian through time. Using a rolling window of Jacobians, DEV values are calculated to identify changes in ecosystem stability through time (C). DEV values can be mapped to the complex plane and thus used to identify the type of bifurcation (D). The analysis presented here is based on O’Brien et al. (2023a) and Grziwotz et al. (2023). The figure was drawn by the authors for the report.

The problem is that empirical data rarely represent all factors within an ecosystem. In this case, the available empirical data can be used to create a 'shadow' attractor, which is simply a version of the original attractor reconstructed using available empirical data. The dominant Jacobian eigenvalue from this 'shadow' attractor can then be used to predict tipping points. To account for system nonlinearity, the Jacobian elements are recovered at any target point $x(t)$ along the attractor using S-maps, which denotes 'sequentially' calculated Jacobians as the system moves along its attractor (see Deyle et al., 2016). The dominant Jacobian eigenvalue is then calculated in a rolling window along the sequentially calculated Jacobians. As the dominant eigenvalue changes through time, it is termed Dynamic Eigen Value (DEV; Grziwotz et al., 2023). When the DEV is below one, the system is stable; when the value increases towards one, the system's stability decreases. Finally, when the DEV passes one, the system is unstable (Figure 9). Therefore, by estimating the DEV, one can determine how close that system is to a tipping point, as the closer the DEV is to one, the closer the system is to bifurcation. This method also provides the ability to detect the type of bifurcation (fold, period-doubling, or Neimark-Sacker bifurcations) likely to occur (Grziwotz et al., 2023). By mapping the DEV to the complex plane, the type of bifurcation can be identified using the 'Real' and 'Imaginary' DEV ($\text{Re}(\text{DEV})$ and $\text{Im}(\text{DEV})$, respectively), whereby $\text{Re}(\text{DEV}) \rightarrow 1$ and $\text{Im}(\text{DEV}) \rightarrow 0$ for fold bifurcation, $\text{Re}(\text{DEV}) \rightarrow -1$ and $\text{Im}(\text{DEV}) \rightarrow 0$ for period-doubling bifurcation, and $\text{Im}(\text{DEV}) \neq 0$ and $|\text{DEV}| \rightarrow 1$ for Neimark-Sacker bifurcation.

5.5. Conclusion

The need for a holistic approach for detecting and predicting shifts in ecosystem stable states has become more evident because of the complex relationships between multiple ecosystem variables and the interplay between ecological mechanisms driving ecosystem response to multi-layered stressors (Botero et al., 2015; Dakos et al., 2019; Hillebrand et al., 2023). However, reflecting the spatiotemporal complexity of ecosystem dynamics, including variation in multiple stressor intensity and their non-linear effects on metacommunity interactions, remains statistically challenging. Nonetheless, several methods have attempted to combine ecosystem variables in a multivariate manner and use the combination to detect shifts in an ecosystem's stable state. While some of these still have been successfully applied to detect thresholds in low-dimensional empirical data, unfortunately, the major limitation of most of these approaches is the lack of inclusion of non-linear relationships between the variables (Table 3). In addition, even if data from a large number of variables is available, all methods reduce dimensionality by using one-to-one regressions, or PCA/MDS, followed by one-to-one regression of PC scores against time or a predictor. Therefore, in order to provide a more holistic approach to determining thresholds and tipping points in ecological data, these two major limitations need to be addressed.

Table 3. Summary of main advantages and limitations of methods for detecting and predicting shifting ecosystem stable state. The table also contains an indication of the type of dataset required for better output from each method.

Method	Advantages	Limitations	Data requirement
Detection			
Machine learning based methods (Gradient Forest, MLP, Stacking regression) (Ellis et al., 2012; Ban et al., 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can capture complex interactions: random forest based. - Dimensionless R2 allows for combining R2 for different components even if measured differently. - No distortion effect of data. - Able to identify the most influential predictors. - Able to identify thresholds based on single or multiple response variables. - MLP can capture non-linear relationships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not efficiently distinguish between effects correlated predictors. - Cannot account for small spatial autocorrelation. - May not work well for a smoother transition in the ecosystem state. - Linear regression based (regression trees and stacking methods). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generally, moderate to large datasets improve the reliability of learning and prediction.
Combined multivariate method (Vasilakopoulos and Marshall, 2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can integrate large numbers of ecosystem components and pressures. - Broad shift in ecosystem state captured even if split is non-linear - Can incorporate lags in the overall response. - May indicate the type of bifurcation depending on the model fit describing the relationship between PCpress and negative-PC1comp. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of dimensionality. - Does not efficiently account for non-linear relationships between individual variables. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Can work with small datasets but more robust detection obtained from larger datasets.
Dose-response method (Bjergager et al., 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Response can be continuous, binary, or discrete, but it works very well when data is linearly separable. - Log-logistic regression is less inclined to overfitting. - Can detect antagonistic and synergistic effects of two or more pressures. -Allows users to be conservative or slack by EC (e.g., users can use EC25 instead of EC50). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires data clustering/separation based on a number of pressures and their intensities. - Data transformation is needed. - Requires a way of combining multiple response variables (e.g., multifunctionality index, diversity index) prior to identifying the effects of stressors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing the number of pressures may require a large dataset of response variables.
Prediction			
EWS based statistics (Dakos, 2018; Weinans et al., 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple measures are available for estimating the level at which EWSs change. - Each method has advantages and limitations, but combining different methods can provide robust estimations of change in ecosystem resilience and closeness to a tipping point. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not account for non-linear relationships between ecosystem components. - Reliability can be strongly influenced by data quality and quantity (e.g., noise, length). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Requires moderate to large datasets, but most importantly, high-quality data, which improves predictability.
Deep learning neural network (Deb et al., 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporates non-linear relationships between variables. - Can be trained on different bifurcation models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can be prone to overfitting. - Difficult to interpret how the model is making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Requires large datasets for training reliable models.

<p>Empirical dynamic modelling-based method (Grziwotz et al., 2023)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can identify closeness to a change in ecosystem state and the type of bifurcation that can be expected. - Can integrate as many variables as one requires. - Preserves for non-linear dynamics between variables. - Preserve original fluctuation in each variable. - Can incorporate lags in the overall response. - S-map method allows for continuous measurement of dominant eigenvalue along combined attractor. - Can predict the type of bifurcation and the closeness to a change in ecosystem state based on resilience and stability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> predictions and to identify any errors in the model. - Restricted to the type of model in which it is trained. -Primarily time-series based. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Variable dataset sizes.
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Deep learning neural networks and EDM are the two methods that most fully incorporate non-linear dynamics between multiple variables and provide the possibility of identifying the type of stable state transition. Deep learning neural networks offer great potential to integrate multiple ecosystem variables because they systematically incorporate complex interactions to predict the change in behaviour of the ecosystem in relation to increasing environmental stressors (Özesmi and Özesmi, 1999; Kulhanek et al., 2011; Millie et al., 2012). However, the major issue with this method is that it provides little explanatory insight into the relative influence of each variable and how predictions are made, although there may be possibilities to ‘dig deeper’ (see Olden and Jackson, 2002). In addition, without multiple preventive adjustments (Özesmi et al., 2006), model overfitting becomes a common problem. Finally, in terms of predictive power, it remains restricted to the models it is trained on. As an alternative to deep learning neural networks, the EDM-based method shows even more potential for integrating multiple ecosystem components and pressures. By combining multiple time series variables into a multidimensional, data-driven, ‘shadow’ attractor and using a dynamic eigenvalue to predict ecosystem state change, this currently seems to be the closest method that fulfils the requirements of a holistic approach, that is, combining non-linear interactions between all ecosystem components and pressures data to understand ecosystem behaviour and shifts in ecosystem stable state. At its current state, this method is primarily based on time series data and adapting it to include intensity-based (e.g., pressure intensity against diversity) or spatial datasets will increase its versatility. EDM-based method using a dynamic eigenvalue seems to be the primary candidate for a holistic approach, even if the approach is time series-based and does not include spatial or pressure

intensities-based modelling. However, EDM alone (i.e., without further estimation of Jacobian and dominant eigenvalue) can also be applied in concordance with other methods that further expand our ability to determine how ecosystems are changing, not just temporally, but also based on the spatial distribution and intensity of ecosystem components and pressures. An indication of this lies in the application of network analysis for determining change in ecosystem state based on fluctuating environmental variables (Tomczak et al., 2013; Hemraj et al., 2017). More specifically, combining EDM-based convergent cross mapping (CCM; Sugihara et al., 2012) and causal neural networks provides the potential of a dynamic model for determining changes in interactions between ecosystem components and pressures, including the trend in the stability of networks. Convergent cross mapping is a method that allows for the detection of causality rather than pure numerical correlation, even in non-separable weakly connected dynamic systems (Sugihara et al., 2012). It incorporates non-linear dynamics and time lags in determining whether variables have a causal relationship. Therefore, it allows for determining real causal relationships between ecosystem components and pressures, information that can be incorporated into building causal neural networks. Such causal neural networks can then be used to predict the structural and temporal stability of ecosystems in relation to the different pressure intensities incorporated in the network (O'Brien et al., 2023b; Zhao et al., 2023). While CCM itself is time series-based, multi-spatial convergent cross mapping (mCCM; Clark et al., 2015), based on spatially replicated data, offers the ability to drop long-term time series for shorter spatial data combined to infer causal effects. Therefore, the combination of CCM/mCCM and causal networks may potentially further improve the detection and prediction of shifts in ecosystem stable states or even be used simultaneously with other methods.

In this review, we delve into several methods that allow us to progress from detecting ecosystem state shifts from univariate datasets to a more comprehensive multivariate approach. The methods presented in this review are certainly not the only ones available for this task, but while they have specific advantages and limitations, they seem to provide the most holistic perspective for detecting and predicting stable state shifts. Nonetheless, an ideal method does not exist that allows for the inclusion of multivariate temporal or spatial datasets while utilising a holistic approach, although EDM-based approaches seem versatile enough to accommodate this task. Overall, we provide a comprehensive view of some of the most inclusive methods that allow for detecting and predicting shifts in ecosystem stable states using multiple variables. These methods can be applied simultaneously to increase the robustness of detections or predictions, but there remains room for further development towards even more vigorous and versatile approaches.

Applications to GES4SEAS Learning Sites

At the GES4SEAS annual meeting in 2023, four case studies were discussed where the potential for tipping points detection or forecasting techniques can be applied. These case studies have different target organisms and habitats and are influenced by different pressures. In addition, the data dimensionalities are different (Table 4). Importantly, the objective of the GES4SEAS tipping point analysis is to identify potential relationships in the complex mosaic of interacting pressures and ecosystem components displaying non-linear responses. Consequently, this task will identify linkages between pressures and ecosystem components for the WP4 toolbox where linearity does not apply.

Combined testing and validation of different techniques in the same LS

In some instances, it may be possible to compare different techniques within the same LS to identify their suitability and compare results. For example, in the instance where data from multiple species is available (e.g., LS6, LS8 and LS 9), there is the potential to use techniques that identify shifts in single species at a time and then compare their results to that of techniques that use the whole community. An example would involve identifying shifts in each of the species using segmented regressions, SiZer, or regression tree-based analysis. Then comparisons of the overall results from these techniques can be made to those that infer shifts in the whole community (random-forest-based community shift, multivariate techniques). Nonetheless, it is important to consider and understand the fundamentals behind the techniques and their suitability to the type of data available. For example, a comparison between changepoint regression and segmented regression on the same data may not convey any relevant information given that these two tests are fundamentally different and developed to identify different types of shifts. On the other hand, comparing the results between segmented regressions and SiZer may provide more relevant information given they were developed for similar data types, even if the ways the methods work are different.

Applying the same technique at different LS

The application of one technique at different LSs can provide a homogeneous examination of tipping points across different areas and a comparison of whether tipping points occur similarly and are caused by similar factors. This may be achieved where similar data are available. For example, this is being undertaken on phytoplankton data from LS2 and LS8. The application of the same technique in different LSs is strongly dependent on the similarity of data type, and in most instances the same data type (e.g., time series of species information with the same metric) is not available. Therefore, this restricts the possibility of applying the same technique.

Moving from testing tipping points in single components to ecosystem approach

In order to take a broad ecosystem-based approach to identifying tipping points, it is important to have access to the right amount of data from different components and pressures from the ecosystem. In many LSs, there are data available and the application of multivariate or random-forest-based techniques are feasible to gain a broader understanding of shift in the overall system. However, the current techniques still contain the drawbacks as highlighted in the review (reduction of dimensionality or being linear). While these techniques are the current state of the art, further development of statistical techniques that enable broad ecosystem-based approaches is still required. Below is a description of the six case studies, including some potential further analysis techniques that can be applied to detect or forecast tipping points.

Table 4. Summary of case study particulars, including ecosystem components of interest, pressures, temporal scale, spatial scale, and possible techniques for analysis.

Partner name and number	Learning Site number	Ecosystem component targeted	Pressures	Time series	Spatial scale	Possible analysis techniques
AZTI (1)	LS 6	<i>Gelidium corneum</i> population	SST, sunlight hours, waves height nutrients, oxygen, turbidity	1986, 1993-2022	Large spatial scale, including depth ranges	Changepoint/segmented regressions, Gradient forest
UAVR (14)	LS 5	Deep water community (no data layer yet)	Climate change, gas hydrate depth	NA	NA	NA
CSIC (5)	LS 6	Sardine and Anchovy populations	Water temperature changes, primary production, fishing extraction, competitor species, and predators	1940-2020	Large spatial scale (Ebro Delta continental shelf)	Changepoint regressions, Random Forest-based methods
UAegean (9)	LS 8	Phytoplankton community	nutrient inputs and pycnocline depth	1980-2022	Saronikos	BACI analysis, possible forecasting techniques
CNRS (19)	LS 11	Coral reef system	Fishing, sedimentation, eutrophication	NA	Island area. Moorea, French Polynesia	Boosted regression trees (BRT).
TUBITAK	LS8 LS9	Macrozoobenthos, macro-algae communities	Nutrients, oxygen, turbidity, temperature change	2014-2022	Güllük Bay (Aegean Sea); Samsun (Black Sea)	Changepoint regression, Multivariate analysis

Case study 1: Loss of *Gelidium corneum* due to harvesting, eutrophication, irradiance, and wave interaction

AZTI (partner number 1) is interested in determining the processes influencing the shift in *Gelidium corneum* cover in the Bay of Biscay and the potential recovery despite multiple pressures. AZTI has access to annual monitoring data of biomass and cover over 1986, 1993-2022, in addition to large spatial and depth coverage. The *G. corneum* population around the Bay of Biscay is impacted by multiple pressures, including environmental (increasing SST, sunlight hours, waves height (since 1986), nutrients, oxygen, turbidity) and direct human impact (extraction, wastewater discharge), and data for these pressures are available. The potential tipping and recovery patterns of the population can be explored using techniques that analyse changes in mean and variance of biomass and cover. While the relationship between some environmental variables and the changes in algal biomass across depth has been done for a subset of the time series (Borja et al., 2018), there remains potential to use techniques, such as gradient forest, to determine to what extent these environmental variables, climate regime shift in the Bay of Biscay (Chust et al., 2022) or human pressures drive a shift in biomass or cover.

Case study 2: Deep Sea biodiversity and methane gas release

UAVR (partner number 14) will focus on developing data layers for deep-sea biodiversity analysis, that is, at depths of 500 to 5000 m. These are communities that are sustained through chemosynthesis and other processes. Chemosynthesis is being threatened by climate change through impacts on gas hydrate stability zone thickness. More specifically, methane gas hydrate is likely to be destabilised, which would cause methane gas release in the deep sea in LS5 (Deep Atlantic-Mediterranean transition) and disrupt the chemosynthetic-based communities. In addition, deep-sea trawling may impact the seafloor and enhance the release of methane. The current extent of this phenomenon is unclear; however, the potential threat to deep-sea biodiversity is high. UAVR is interested in using its biodiversity and climate change data to detect tipping points in deep-sea communities. An additional extension of this could involve the prediction of tipping points based on variability in biodiversity data, climate change, and methane gas hydrate stability data.

Case study 3: Historical analysis of the socio-ecological system associated with the Ebro Delta purse seine fishery

Tipping point detection methods are being applied by CSIC (partner number 5) to identify the causes of sardine and anchovy population change over time. CSIC has access to large temporal-scale data on

sardine and anchovy populations. These datasets can be used with temporal detection methods such as segmented or changepoint regressions that allow for the detection of when significant changes in mean and variance in population occurred over time. In addition, CSIC has access to spatiotemporally varying pressures, including water temperature changes, primary production, fishing effort, competitor species, and predators. Access to these datasets allows for the use of more comprehensive methods, such as regression tree-based methods, to tweak out the major causes of changing fish populations.

Case study 4: Influence of nutrients and pycnocline on phytoplankton community, biomass, and traits

UAegean (partner number 9) has large temporal data on phytoplankton species and traits, along with data on pressures, including nutrient inputs and pycnocline depth changes due to atmospheric heating. UAegean is interested in identifying which ecological dimensions (e.g., ecosystem services, species composition, biomass) are likely more susceptible and what processes may cause tipping points in these ecological dimensions. So far, UAegean has not applied any model or analyses, but possibilities would include determining temporal shifts in biomass and species composition, followed by the determination of possible causes, as well as before-after-control-impact analysis. In addition, the potential for forecasting tipping points from pressures can be explored.

Case study 5: Predicting drivers of local coral reef regime shifts

Coral reefs are complex ecosystems that are constituted of different regimes (or states). Through the analysis of regime shifts in local coral reefs, CNRS (partner number 19) will look into the shifts from coral-dominated regimes towards a less desirable algae-dominated regime. A predictive model of reef regimes (presence/absence of coral/algae dominated regime) will be built at a high spatial resolution to disentangle the relative contribution of environmental and anthropogenic drivers in explaining observed local patterns. This will allow to identify tipping-points between states by applying different scenarios of anthropogenic drivers.

Case study 6: Changes in the Macrozoobenthos and Macro-Algae communities in response to nutrient levels modifications

TUBITAK (partner number 13) has been collecting temporal data on macrozoobenthos, macro-algae, physical, and nutrient data. TUBITAK has been coordinating a national monitoring program (DEN-IZ) since 2014. The nature and the extent of pressures on biodiversity and the effects of the pressures were determined with the Monitoring Program. The macrozoobenthos and macro-algae communities

has been affected by different pressures in the Güllük Bay (e.g fish farms, riverine input, tourism) and the coast of Samsun province (e.g urban and industrial wastewater discharge, riverine input, port). TUBITAK is studying on identifying ecosystem tipping points and ecosystem shifts by examining the relationship of the data with these pressures. The availability of these datasets facilitates the utilization of the change point regression and multivariate analysis approaches, to identify the primary factors contributing to fluctuations in macrozoobenthos and macro-algae communities.

6. Investigating effects of measures on mitigating impacts (Task 3.3)

For Task 3.3, we will attempt to gather spatial-temporal information per case study on the activity-footprint of human activities, including energy extraction and generation (i.e., the location of man-made structures such as oil and gas platforms and fixed wind turbines), aggregate extraction, water treatment, maritime transport, tourism and fishing. These data will be used alongside environmental data, utilising the common scenarios of climate change for European regional seas from EU project FutureMARES, which includes temperature, salinity, oxygen, and primary production, to model the response of marine ecosystems through the use of a Marine Ecosystem Model (MEMs): Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (Christensen and Walters 2004), making use of the Ecospace spatial-temporal model, and of the spatial-temporal framework (Steenbeek et al., 2013) and the Habitat Foraging Capacity (HFC) model (Christensen et al., 2014). The novel capabilities of Ecospace allow the analysis of many human activities and climate change elements to evaluate the effects of those, and of potential mitigation measures on those impacts (De Mutsert et al., 2023). The pressure-footprint of activities and their impacts on ecological components will then be modelled using scenario testing, i.e., altering activity levels. Mitigation measures can then be explored, including spatial protections (marine protected areas), fishing at sustainable levels or nutrient reductions.

Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs) are probabilistic graphical models that represent a set of variables and their conditional dependencies via a directed acyclic graph (Barton et al., 2012). A great benefit of the BBN approach is that uncertainty is captured inherently through the use of probability distributions for each variable and can cascade through the network. However, such models, especially dynamic models, can be difficult to create. The first step is to identify pressures and linkages between functional groups in an ecosystem and prioritise them to highlight key pathways to model with a BBN since it is difficult to include many nodes within a BBN (Figure 11 and Figure 12).

BBNs have also been developed recently to incorporate EwE projections (Uusitalo et al. 2022), which bring together the knowledge and understanding of a great range of species interactions from a process-based quantitative and dynamic model (EwE). BBN models offer the flexibility to link to pressures and impacts that are not well-modelled within the EwE framework (e.g., impacts on breeding colonies of seabirds in the terrestrial domain), and the approach of Uusitalo et al. (2022) integrates the projections of an EwE model within a linked meta-model. We aim to use linked BBN-EwE models, where possible, to examine the uncertainty of model projections and enable the evaluation of risks from human activities.

Figure 11. A conceptual diagram with many linkages between key species in the North Sea and pressures (nutrient inputs, mortality of seabirds at turbines, fishing pressure) from human activities, where the metrics considered have data available from either OSPAR.

Figure 12. Prioritised linkages between key species in the North Sea and pressures (nutrient inputs, mortality of seabirds at turbines, fishing pressure) that may form the basis of a Bayesian Belief Network.

Furthermore, EwE outputs can be incorporated in established frameworks to link ecosystem components to services, as demonstrated in T3.1 for the North Sea case study (Piet et al. 2024). Here, the rate of production and biomass of biotic groups were derived from aggregated functional group outputs from the North Sea EwE model. The production rates are considered the preferred flow-type proxy metric to represent the Ecosystem Service Supply Potential for most Ecosystem Component - Ecosystem Service linkages, with the exception of cultural services where biomass was preferred since the service depends on the simple presence of a component in the environmental setting (see T3.1). A major benefit of including model outputs in an Ecosystem Service assessment such as this is that when model scenarios are tested for specific purposes such as fisheries management or nutrient reductions, the Ecosystem Service assessment can be updated with new production and biomass values and thus provide wider information for managers.

6.1. Applications to GES4SEAS Learning Sites

Case studies are being explored in the North Sea, Celtic Sea, Baltic Sea (Gulf of Bothnia and Kattegat) and Western Mediterranean Sea, while additional LSs may join during 2024 (including a tropical coral reef ecosystem learning site that includes diverse stakeholders from management bodies in French Polynesia). A case study for the Black Sea in relation to gas exploration and water discharge from the Danube has been discussed. The possibility to develop BBNs is being pursued for the southern North Sea and Celtic Sea LSs to complement the existing Baltic Sea model. Currently, data are being prepared in advance of the planned workshop on BBN (Task 4.4) and, notably, partners working on these LS also have EwE models available, which may be linked to BBN to model scenarios in the future. Once developed, the differing range of outputs from EwE and BBN will be discussed in relation to the relevance to management of one modelling approach over the other.

A collaborative plan to test the utility of EwE models is in development and will focus of the trade-offs between fishing, marine protected areas, the introduction of man-made structures, reduction in nutrients and/or noise from shipping. A single modelling protocol will be agreed and implemented for EwE models of the North Sea, Baltic Sea and Western Mediterranean Sea by GES4SEAS partners. Furthermore, the workplan is being discussed with ACTNOW partners in relation to the scenarios being developed by that project to investigate cumulative effects of pressures. This collaboration will continue the work started by GES4SEAS and allow further contrasts between a larger range of ecosystems and model types.

7. Selected methods and potential applications in Learning Sites - Building analytical capacity (Task 3.4)

Crossing the information between potential tools to implement under WP3 and interest in applying them by LSs provides a first mapping of capacity-building needs within the GES4SEAS project (Figure 13).

	Baltic - SYKE	Baltic-Atlantic (kattgat) - AU	Atlantic (North Sea - Netherlands) - WR	Atlantic (Celtic Sea) - MI	Atlantic - Medit. transition - UAVR	Western Medit. - CSIC	Medit. (mostly adriatic) - ISPRA	Aegean Sea - HMR	Aegean Sea - TUBITAK	Black Sea - NIMRD	Black Sea - TUBITAK	Whole Europe - NIVA	French Polynesia - CNRS	AZTI
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS5	LS6	LS7	LS8	LS8	LS9	LS9	LS10	LS11	CS1
WP3.1. Capacity to deliver ecosystem services and links to GES														
SCAIRM + WKASCAPES	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Others	Green	Green												
WP3.2. Testing tipping points and thresholds														
Statistical Breakpoint analyses	Blue	Green	Blue		Red	Red	Red	Blue	Red	Red	Blue			Blue
Ecopath with Ecosim	Blue		Green	Blue	Red	Blue			Red	Red	Red			Red
Ecospace	Blue		Green	Blue	Red	Blue			Red	Red	Red			Red
Others												Red	Red	
WP3.3. Investigating effects of measures on mitigating impacts														
Bow-tie	Red	Red	Green	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red			Blue
BBNs	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red			Red	Red	Red		Red	Blue
Ecopath with Ecosim	Blue		Blue	Blue	Red	Green			Red	Red	Red		Red	Red
Ecospace	Blue		Green	Blue	Red	Green			Red	Red	Red		Red	Red
SCAIRM + WGCEAM	Red	Red	Green		Green	Red		Red	Red	Red	Red		Red	Red
Others	Blue											Green	Green	

Figure 13. Matching WP3 tools and Learning Sites (LSs) for each task: in blue (LS can develop without help), in red (LS can develop with help), in green (LS can teach to others).

Based on these results, the organisation of capacity-building activities from WP3 during the second half of 2023 and the first half of 2024 are as follow:

Workshop on Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) and Ecospace

Location and dates: Barcelona, Spain, 11-15 December 2023

Local organisers: Marta Coll, Chris Lynam & Jeroen Steenbeek

Workshop on Capacity to Deliver Ecosystem Services and links to GES

Location and dates: online, 15-19 January 2024, presential during the annual meeting 2024 and online in September 2024

Local organisers: GerJan Piet & Jacqueline Tamis

Workshop on Bayesian Network modelling

Location and dates: Viikki, Finland, week of 11-15 March 2024 (dates to be confirmed)

Local organisers: Samuli Korpinen, Riikka Puntila-Dodd & Laura Uusitalo

In addition, two activities are aimed for 2024:

Workshop on tipping points and thresholds

Location and dates: Bremerhaven, Germany 22 -25 April 2024

Local organisers: Jacob Carstensen & Deevesh Ashley Hemraj

Workshop on Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) and Ecospace

Location and dates: Barcelona, Spain, November 2024

Local organisers: Marta Coll, Chris Lynam & Jeroen Steenbeek.

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9. Appendices

Appendix 1. A Cumulative Impact Assessment on the marine capacity to supply Ecosystem Services

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Abstract

Ecosystem services link the status of biodiversity and its functioning to societal goods and benefits contributing to human wellbeing. As such, they can play a key role in preserving the environment and managing natural resources and ecosystems to conserve nature's contributions to people. Identification of the main threats acting on the natural environment, and how these may impact its capacity to supply ecosystem services, is fundamental to the maintenance of these services. To that end, we present a novel approach based on a cumulative impacts assessment that 1) covers all relevant human activities and their pressures, 2) links impacts to the biotic groups that make up biodiversity and 3) provides an estimation of the Service Supply Potential based on the functioning of these biotic groups. Key proxy metrics to estimate this Service Supply Potential were identified from a literature review and quantified using a food web model (Ecopath with Ecosim). In addition to this quantitative information, the assessment of the capacity to supply ecosystem services was supplemented with expert judgement-based information to reflect the societal preferences that drive the allocation of human capital and turn these services into societal goods and benefits. As a proof of concept, the method was applied to the North Sea ecosystem. Results showed that, overall, the capacity of the North Sea to supply Cultural ecosystem services was most threatened, with an average potential decline of 50% compared to an undisturbed situation. This was followed by the Provisioning ecosystem services with 46% and the Regulation & Maintenance with 38%. The main anthropogenic threats (excluding climate change) to the North Sea capacity to supply ecosystem services come primarily from fishing contributing to 51% of the overall threat. Of the remaining 18 sectoral activities another 23% was contributed by mining, non-renewable energy, tourism, and agriculture.

Keywords: Natural capital, Nature's contributions to People (NCP), Risk-based approach, North Sea, Ecopath with Ecosim

1 Introduction

Ecosystem recovery and the sustainable exploitation of marine resources are important for the conservation of nature's contributions to people (e.g. Meadows et al., 1972; MA, 2005; IPBES, 2018). Ambitions to quantify nature's contribution to people (NCP) has given rise to the concept of 'natural capital', a concept that explores the flows of ecosystem services in the context of human benefits, and how management scenarios may be able to sustain or improve flows in the future. Ecosystem accounting is a key analytical tool to provide insights for managing natural capital (EEA, 2018). The System of Environmental-Economic Accounting - Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA) (UN, 2014) adapts the concepts developed for the

estimation of ecosystem services, such as the cascade model (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011), and can be placed within the conceptual framing of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) (Díaz et al., 2015). Within this framework, the ecosystem asset is a key concept that refers to the individual spatially defined statistical units (spatial perspective), the ecological functional units (the ecological perspective) and the supply or producing units that deliver ecosystem services and associated benefits (the societal benefit perspective). In an accounting context, the concept of ecosystem capacity embodies the link between the ecosystem asset extent and condition, and the ecosystem services supply and use (UN, 2021). This study therefore focusses on the concept of ecosystem capacity.

The complex problems we are currently facing, such as climate change and biodiversity loss, require integrated assessments of all anthropogenic threats and ecosystem-based management, supported by inter- and transdisciplinary science that considers the whole social-ecological system (Biggs et al., 2012; Liqueste et al., 2013; Maes et al., 2012; Mee et al., 2015). This requires the development of approaches that bridge the gap between the ecological system and the social system. Ecosystem services are such a concept as they are being used in the cascade model (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011) to link biophysical structure, processes, and functions (together making up the environmental system) with their goods and benefits and how these are valued in the socio-economic system (Burdon et al., 2022; von Thenen et al., 2020; Drakou et al., 2017; Guerry et al., 2015). Potential threats to biodiversity and ecosystem integrity thus affect the capacity of ecosystems to supply ecosystem services (Müller and Burkhard 2007, Quintessence 2016) and their contribution to human well-being (Costanza et al. 1997, Mace 2014). As such, the future developments of environmental assessments are usually limited to estimating impacts on biodiversity, and there is a large need to bridge the gap with the social system through the application of ecosystem services. These extended assessments would then cover all aspects of sustainability, i.e. environmental, social, and economic, thereby improving their relevance for ecosystem-based approaches to management (Berkes, 2012; Borgström et al., 2015). It is expected that such extended assessments would better guide advancements towards, and assess trade-offs between, diverse co-occurring objectives such as those that require us to safeguard human and ecosystem health, enable food security, support the sustainable growth of marine economies, and expedite biodiversity recovery (Judd and Lonsdale, 2021).

In this study, our focus is on the assessment of the ecosystem capacity to supply ecosystem services (CtSES), thus focussing on the ecological system and, specifically, the ecological functional units, i.e. biotic groups (the assets in an accounting context), that produce the ecosystem services. This focus suggests that the goods and benefits and hence the socio-economic system are excluded from this assessment. However, we assert that a proper assessment of the CtSES cannot avoid to consider the expected goods and benefits these ecosystem services are supposed to supply as these determine the potential interactions of the biotic groups with the built, human, and social capital in order to provide those good and benefits (Burdon et al., 2022; Elliott, 2023). After all, ecosystem services are intended to link ecosystem structure and functioning to human well-being through those good and benefits (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011). To identify the threats that may impact the CtSES, we apply a Cumulative Impact Assessment (CIA) (Culhane et al. 2019ab; Piet et al., 2023) which estimates how the cumulative pressures of all human activities impact the biotic groups that make up marine biodiversity, with an estimate of the Service Supply Potential (SSP) (Teixeira et al., 2019; Culhane et al., 2019ab) representing the relative contributions of the biodiversity components in terms of their functioning. This SSP can be quantified using a set of proxy

metrics from a review of indicators intended to operationalize ecosystem services assessments (von Thenen et al., 2020).

Changes across food webs, through direct and indirect interactions between species, the environment, and human use, are key to understand and account for ecosystem dynamics in management decisions (Belgrano et al., 2019). Food web modelling approaches, such as Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (Christensen and Walters, 2004; Coll & Steenbeek 2017; Horn et al., 2021), are used to provide information on ecosystem dynamics (Craig and Link, 2023). In the context of this study, EwE quantifies the functioning of the various biotic groups in terms of their contribution to the supply of ecosystem services. The biotic groups that make up marine biodiversity are central to this CIA method, as they connect the impact from human activities and their pressures through their SSP to an overall assessment of the cumulative impact on the CtSES. The assessment is conducted for the North Sea as a proof of concept, but the method outlined in this paper can be applied in any marine ecosystem where comparable information is available. In less data-rich situations the application of expert-judgement to estimate specific parts of the method (e.g. SSP), is always an option. The current study uses the cascade model to define and explore several options for the estimation of SSP and how these may affect the outcome of the assessment to provide guidance for the development of the knowledge base required to assess the cumulative impacts on the CtSES.

2 Material and methods

The approach to assess the CtSES is illustrated in Figure 1 showing that it is based on an understanding of how all the different anthropogenic stressors interact with the biotic groups as represented in the so-called linkage framework. A cumulative impact assessment, i.e. SCAIRM (Spatial Cumulative Assessment of Impact Risk for Management) (Piet et al. 2023), is then applied to estimate the risk that those biotic groups are impacted while the SSP represents the contribution of the functional biotic groups to the CtSES. Together this provides an estimation of the cumulative impacts of all anthropogenic stressors on the CtSES.

Figure 1. Outline of the material and methods where the Cumulative Impact Assessment on the Capacity to Supply Ecosystem Services is calculated from the combination of the existing North Sea SCAIRM method and an estimation of the Service Supply Potential of the functional biotic groups. The North Sea linkage framework is represented in Figure 6, the estimation of the Service Supply Potential is elaborated in Table 1.

3 Linkage framework

To assess the impact of human activities on North Sea biodiversity, we adopted an evolving linkage framework which forms the basis of previous CIA (Knights et al., 2015; Piet et al., 2015; 2017; 2019; Borgwardt et al., 2019), with its latest iteration described by Piet et al. (2023). This linkage framework consists of impact chains linking human activities, via pressures, to ecosystem components in order to assess the main threats to biodiversity. The ecosystem components are aligned to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (EC, 2017) for policy relevance. For the purposes of this assessment this linkage framework was extended to include ecosystem services using known linkages between specific biotic (or functional) species groups and ecosystem services from Culhane et al. (2018; 2019ab). To that end the ecosystem components were matched to the biotic groups identified by Culhane et al. (2018) as the most relevant ecosystem services providing units. This was straightforward for the species groups (e.g. fish & cephalopods, mammals or birds), but involved several connections for those

ecosystem components which are essentially communities associated to habitats in the MSFD (e.g. phytoplankton or zooplankton with the pelagic water column and benthic invertebrate infauna with several seabed habitats).

A key requirement for a CIA, and hence this linkage framework, is that it should comprehensively encompass all of the relevant activities and pressures that may affect all ecosystem components/biotic groups that make up biodiversity and the ecosystem services it supplies. The selected activities, pressures, and ecosystem components/biotic groups with applied typologies are adequately described in the previous CIA studies on which this study builds (Knights et al., 2015; Piet et al., 2015; 2017; 2019; Borgwardt et al., 2019; Culhane et al., 2019) but are also shown in the Supplementary Material (SM1). The ecosystem services and their typology were based on CICES 5.1 (Haines-Young, 2013; Potschin-Young et al., 2018; Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018), which is the de facto standard reference classification for ecosystem services. Moreover, it is aligned with other ecosystem services classification systems (UN, 2021), such as those used by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA, 2005) and The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) (Ring, 2010). For the linkage framework, the ecosystem services are distinguished at the Class level resulting in 45 types of ecosystem services comprehensively covering Provisioning, Regulation & Maintenance, and Cultural services (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018)). Every biotic group that can be expected to contribute to the supply of a specific ecosystem service group is then linked to it using Culhane et al. (2018ab) without any consideration of its relative contribution. In a subsequent step, this relative contribution is weighted through its SSP.

4 Cumulative Impact Assessment

For the CIA of the ecosystem and its components, i.e. biotic groups, we applied the SCAIRM model (see Supplementary Material SM2) as this is probably among the most sophisticated risk-based approaches available for CIA and has the advantage that impact is expressed as the “potential change in state compared to an undisturbed situation” (Piet et al., 2023) which can be easily transferred to an understanding of how the CtSES may potentially change. The model is developed for the North Sea and consists of 23,744 impact chains that link 106 human activities and their operations through 28 pressures (see Supplementary Material SM1) to a set of eight ecosystem components consisting of species groups and habitats according to the MSFD (EC, 2008) which were then matched to the 12 biotic groups (see Supplementary Material SM3 for cross-linkage). This model estimates the cumulative Impact Risk as a potential change in state, expressed as a relative change in equilibrium abundance of each ecosystem component compared to an undisturbed situation.

5 Service Supply Potential

The present study works from the cascade model (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011) which links the environmental system and its biophysical structure, i.e. biodiversity, to the socio-economic system and its goods and benefits contributing to human well-being through the flow of ecosystem services. Some studies distinguish within the environmental system between the *capacity* underpinned by the biophysical structure and processes which determine the functioning, and which then turns into the (flow of) *services* if they can be expected to contribute to the goods and benefits (Liquete et al., 2013; Potschin-Young et al., 2017; von Thenen et al., 2020) (see Table 1). Thus, in estimating the SSP we distinguish the capacity, in terms of its biophysical structures, processes and functions, from the ecosystem services where only those biotic groups are considered that are known to be part of, or have contributed to, the goods and benefits according to the links identified by Culhane (2018ab) (Table 1, Option S1). The relative contribution of those biotic groups to the supply of ecosystem services is then

determined by their structural or functional characteristics in relation to the nature of those goods and benefits as represented by appropriate metrics (Option S2) as well as their likelihood to contribute based on current societal preferences (Option S3).

Cascade model		Selection Criterion	SSP estimation	Option
Environmental system	Capacity	Biophysical Structure	Capacity of all possible linkages is determined by their biophysical structure as represented by the Biomass key proxy metric	
		Processes and Functions	Capacity of all possible linkages is determined by their functioning as represented by the Productivity key proxy metric	
	Services	Selection of biotic groups known to be part of, or have contributed to, the goods and benefits	SSP only based on the selected biotic groups according to Culhane et al. (2018) as represented by the filled cells in Table 3	S1
		According to their structural or functional characteristics as represented by their appropriate key proxy metric, i.e. Biomass or Productivity, depending on the nature of those goods and benefits	SSP only based on the selected biotic groups according to Culhane et al. (2018) weighted by their functioning as represented by the appropriate key proxy metric (Table 2)	S2
		Societal preferences determined by biotic group characteristics	SSP only based on the selected biotic groups according to Culhane et al. (2018) weighted by their likelihood of contribution based on current use. See Table 3	S3
		Ultimate estimation based on the combination of the above		S4
Socio-economic system	Goods & Benefits	Not considered in this study		

Table 1. Options for the estimation of the Service Supply Potential (SSP) per biotic group to contrast the default is the assumption that SSP is equal (=1) across all possible linkages. These options' sources of information are based on interpretations (Martinetto et al., 2020; Von Thenen et al., 2020) of the cascade model (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011) which now runs from top (biodiversity as the basis) to bottom. The Capacity to Supply ecosystem services is determined by the SSP in the environmental system.

Simply applying the linkage framework and subsequently only looking at the threat posed to each of the biotic groups, would suggest that all selected biotic groups contribute equally to the CtSES of specific ecosystem services. As this is known not to be the case, we worked from Teixeira et al. (2019) and Culhane et al. (2019b) to determine the biotic groups with a Service Supply Potential (SSP) for specific ecosystem services (S1 in Table 1) but instead of the expert judgement-based qualitative valuation used there (i.e. 0, 1, 2; to reflect the importance of a biotic group's contribution to the supply of ecosystem services) we developed an alternative, and more quantitative estimation of the SSP. This ultimately estimates SSP from the perspective of a social-ecological system (Culhane et al., 2019b): in the ecological system the supply of ecosystem services is determined by the amount of each of the biotic groups and their functioning but societal preferences determine how human capital is likely to interact with these biotic groups in order to generate the goods and benefits. Any monetary evaluation of these goods and benefits was considered beyond the scope of the present study (Table 1). The calculation of the SSP thus consists of an interpretation of how the *capacity* of the ecosystem, i.e. biophysical structure and their processes and functions of the biotic groups results in the supply of *services* (S2 in Table 1), the likelihood of contribution assumed to be reflected by current use (S3 in Table 1) which together should provide the best estimation of SSP (S4 in Table 1). The biotic group's functioning was estimated using metrics that could be calculated

with existing models. This, however, was not possible for the likelihood of contribution based on societal preferences and thus expert judgment-based values needed to be applied.

To estimate the biotic group's functioning (Option S2 in Table 1) the structured indicator pool developed by von Thenen et al. (2020) to operationalize ecosystem services assessments (see Table 2 and SM4) was used to select appropriate proxy metrics that can be easily estimated. To that end three criteria were applied:

- 1) The metric adequately captures how the functioning of the biotic group contributes to the SSP of a specific ecosystem services,
- 2) The metric can be estimated from information that is readily available and
- 3) The metric is sufficiently consistent among all the biotic groups that contribute to the ecosystem services.

With the principal objective to investigate the impact of human activities on the CtSES, we aimed to estimate SSP (1st criterion) using indicators and indicator themes that represented either "Capacity" or "Services" according to von Thenen et al. (2020), while also ensuring metric selection met the 2nd and 3rd criteria. This resulted in the selection of six proxy metrics that covered the essence of most of the indicators and indicator themes, while being broad enough to facilitate the use of available data and consistency in the estimation among all the biotic groups.

Proxy metric	Information	Corresponding indicators
Production	The rate (e.g. time ⁻¹) of generation of biomass in (a selection of) a biotic group	Primary production (gross, respiration and net), Leaf litter production, Eelgrass productivity, Assimilative/bioremediation capacity, Sequestration potential, algal production rates
Biomass	The mass (e.g. kg) of (a selection of) a biotic group	Biomass of sessile epifauna, Mangrove biomass, Aboveground biomass
Abundance or Density	Count of individuals in (a selection of) a biotic group	Abundance of seagrasses, Density of bioturbators, Abundance of suspension and surface deposit feeder, Depletion in the number of suspension feeders
Extent of habitat	Surface area of a biotic group (e.g. km ²)	Coral extent and condition, Substrate cover, Diversity and abundance of cold-water corals, Extent of selected emerged/submerged/ intertidal habitats, Seagrass extent, Mangrove extent, Number of operational taxonomic microbic units, Plant cover
Presence	The presence or absence of (a specific selection of) a biotic group	Presence of bioturbator organisms, Presence of floodplains/wetlands/estuaries/ mangroves, Benthic invertebrate species, Presence of nitrophilous macroalgae in catchment basin, suspension feeders, degrading microorganisms, biogenic habitat, four coralline algae, seagrass meadow
Composition	The composition of a biotic group in terms of size- or age-classes, traits, species richness or other biodiversity indices	Size-frequency distributions of corals, Submerged and intertidal habitats diversity, Topographic complexity of corals, Benthic biodiversity, Species composition and area covered with wetlands, Feeding modes, Food web structure and robustness (various properties), Functional variation of predatory performance, Marine food chain, Connectivity/diversity/trophic composition, Consumption of organisms by fish/foodchain relationships, Species richness

Table 2: Proxy metrics, the information required from the study area and corresponding indicators from von Thenen et al. (2020). Often these may apply to specific biotic groups. The key proxy metrics applied to estimate the SSP are a selection from this.

The proxy metrics in Table 2 represent the main aspects of the biotic groups in terms of how much their functioning can be expected to contribute to the CtSES. They also cover the distinction used in ecosystem capital accounting between 'assets' and 'flows' (Maes, 2013), where *Production* represents the flow while the others (e.g. *Biomass*) represent the asset in terms of quantity or quality. Our selection of key proxy metrics was based on previous studies, which stated that ecosystem services are often (but not always) best represented by flows (Maes, 2013; Burdon et al., 2022). This resulted in the choice of *Production* as the preferred flow-type key proxy metric to represent the SSP for most biotic group-ecosystem service linkages. The choice of this metric is the consequence of putting more emphasis on the 2nd and 3rd criteria while acknowledging that other indicator themes from the von Thenen et al. (2020) review may be more applicable for the SSP of specific ecosystem services such as those under the division 'Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting'. In addition, we propose several asset-type proxy metrics that are less elaborate to calculate, and therefore more often available, as the fall-back options in case *Production* is not available: *Biomass* was selected as the other key proxy metric as it was considered to represent the CtSES better than *Abundance* of species or *Extent* of habitats which, in turn, are more informative than simply *Presence*. In addition to these metrics, a complementary metric was included that captures the *Composition* of the asset, e.g. in terms of

size- or age-classes, traits, species richness or other biodiversity indices. As the indicators in Table 2 and SM4 show, the biotic group is often represented by an asset-type metric of a specific selection or subset within that biotic group considered to better estimate the capacity to supply a specific ecosystem services through what is essentially the combination of two complementary aspects (i.e. amount and composition) of the asset. For example, the selection of bioturbators within the benthic infauna and epifauna (Beauchard et al., 2023) in the case of ‘Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes’.

For estimation of the SSP by option S2, we worked from the assumption that, for all the Provisioning services and most of the Regulation & Maintenance services, the production of the biotic group is probably the best proxy for its SSP. This was assumed to be different for the Cultural services where the “Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting” services were assumed to be best represented by biomass, whereas the “Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting” services were assumed to be independent from their actual status in the ecosystem as long as they were perceived as still present and for which biomass is also a good enough proxy.

The likelihood of contribution (Option S3 in Table 1) was introduced to reflect a full (High: 100%) or limited (Medium: 1% or Low: 0.1%) contribution of the biotic group to ecosystem services as can be expected based on the key proxy metric alone. For now we applied a common sense approach based on the current and past contributions deemed adequate to reflect that societal preferences are likely to determine the outcome of such assessments and should be explicitly incorporated. Here we assumed that, for the “Biomass” Division of the Provisioning ecosystem services, all biotic groups not commonly fished/harvested/reared/cultivated are assumed to contribute much less (an assumed 0.1%) compared to those that are (i.e. fish, shellfish, cephalopods, macroalgae). This did not apply for the “*Genetic material*” Division of the Provisioning ecosystem services. For all Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services we assumed a distinction between High and Medium/Low was not appropriate and the default 100% contribution (weighting factor=1) was applied. For the Cultural ecosystem services Division “*Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting*” we distinguished between the two ecosystem services Groups. For the Group “*Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment*” we assumed that all biotic groups that are not directly visible (i.e. too small for the naked eye and/or hidden from sight) contributed less (an assumed 1%) than biotic groups that can be observed without a microscope and/or extraction from their environment. For the other ecosystem services Group “*Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment*”, as well as the whole ecosystem services Division “*Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting*”, all biotic groups were assumed to contribute an equal 100%.

Finally, the ultimate and most elaborate calculation of the SSP (Option S4 in Table 1) combines the functioning and likelihood of contribution of the different biotic groups from the perspective of the full social-ecological system.

6 Using Ecopath with Ecosim to calculate key proxy metrics

To estimate the SSP for those biotic group-ecosystem service linkages based on the proxy metrics, i.e. production or biomass, we used the estimates of the functional groups as they occur in the North Sea EwE model and matched the output to the biotic groups used in this ecosystem services context. EwE models the foodweb by quantifying biomass (carbon) and energy flows. It is used globally to simulate the ecosystem impacts of fishing and other activities, possibly under various management scenarios, as well as environmental drivers such as climate change

on the structure and function of marine ecosystems (Christensen and Walters, 2004). The North Sea EwE model was initially built by Mackinson and Daskalov (2007) and subsequently updated and presented to the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) Working Group on Multispecies Assessment Methods (WGSAM) to be used as an ICES advice product (ICES, 2013). The North Sea model was updated for the purpose of this work, bringing simulations to 2020 by updating the underlying time series data. The EwE model comprises 69 functional groups consisting of a single species, multiple species, or an age-stanza of a species that were aggregated into biotic groups ranging from plankton and benthos to fish, seabirds, and marine mammals.

We used the mass-balanced (Ecopath) and time-dynamic (Ecosim) components of EwE to extract estimates of production ($\text{t.km}^{-2}.\text{year}^{-1}$) and biomass (t.km^{-2}) for each functional group in each year of the models duration (1991 to 2020). EwE was identified as an appropriate tool as it can simulate the dynamics of the functional groups as defined in the parallel ecosystem service linkage framework. EwE can provide quantitative estimates for functional groups that are well supported by data as well as those that are more data deficient (which it can acknowledge through parameter uncertainty routines) and it is able to simulate the retrospective and future impacts of cumulative pressures (Craig and Link, 2023). Functional group production rates in EwE are driven by their fishery catch rate, predation mortality, consumption rates, other mortality, migration, and biomass. Biomass dynamics (growth rates) are expressed in Ecosim through a series of coupled differential equations which account for functional group consumption rates (based on the foraging arena concept; Walters et al., 1997), fishing, predation, and other sources of mortality, as well as migration (see Christensen and Walters, 2004). Annual estimates of biomass and production were used to build a range of ‘observed’ or ‘plausible’ metrics for each functional group based on retrospective dynamics and changes in fisheries exploitation.

7 Threats to the capacity to supply ecosystem services

This assessment uses an estimation of Impact Risk to quantify the threat of the anthropogenic stressors (i.e. human activities and their pressures) on the CtSES. To that end, SCAIRM was applied to estimate the Impact Risk per ecosystem component/biotic group which could then be converted using the SSP estimates of each of those biotic groups to an Impact Risk to the capacity to supply each of the specific ecosystem services.

The different options in the estimation of the SSP make explicit the knowledge demands that apply when calculating how the CtSES is affected by anthropogenic threats in any particular ecosystem. This North Sea proof of concept then also shows how the outcome of the assessment of the cumulative impacts on the CtSES is affected by such options. A Sankey diagram is used to depict the flow of Impact Risk through the linkage framework connecting the anthropogenic stressors to the CtSES through “*activity-pressure-biotic group-ecosystem services*” chains.

8 Results

9 Linkage framework

The linkage framework for the assessment of cumulative impacts of human activities on the North Sea CtSES was constructed from the linkage framework in Piet et al. (2023). This framework consists of nodes representing activities, pressures and ecosystem components and all 1005 relevant links between the various nodes within these three levels. The ecosystem components were matched to functional biotic groups and extended with the linkages to

ecosystem services according to CICES 5.1. Table 3 shows that 327 linkages exist between the 12 biotic groups and the 45 ecosystem service classes.

Section	Division	Group	Class	Bacteria	Birds	Cephalopods	Epifauna	Fish	Infauna	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Marine mammals	Microphytobenthos	Phytoplankton	Zooplankton		
Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown for nutritional purposes							H							
			Fibres and other materials from in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)							H	L		L	L			
			Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown as an energy source							H	L		L	L			
		Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture for nutritional purposes					H	H	L							
			Fibres and other materials from animals grown by in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		L	L	H	H	L				L			L	
			Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture as an energy source					H					L				
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for nutrition								H	H			L	L	
			Fibres and other materials from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)								H	H			L	L	
			Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a source of energy								H	H			L	L	
		Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for nutritional purposes		L	H	H	H	H					L		L	
			Fibres and other materials from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		L	H	H	H	H					L		L	
			Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used as a source of energy						H					L			
	Genetic material from all biota	Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	Seeds, spores and other plant materials collected for maintaining or establishing a population								H	H		H	H		
			Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties							H	H			H	H		
			Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the design and construction of new biological entities								H	H			H	H	
		Genetic material from animals	Animal material collected for the purposes of maintaining or establishing a population		H	H	H	H	H					H		H	
			Wild animals (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties		H	H	H	H	H					H		H	
			Individual genes extracted from organisms for the design and construction of new biological entities	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	
	Regulation & Maintenance	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	H			H		H	H	H		H	H	H	
				Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Smell reduction				H	H		H		H								
Visual screening				H	H		H		H								
Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions		Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Control of erosion rates	Control of erosion rates				H		H	H	H		H			
				Buffering and attenuation of mass movement				H		H	H	H		H			
				Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)				H		H	H	H		H			
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	'Gamete' dispersal	'Gamete' dispersal		H		H	H								
				Seed dispersal		H			H								
				Maintaining nursery populations and habitats (Including gene pool protection)	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Pest and disease control	Pest control (including invasive species)	Pest control (including invasive species)	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
				Disease control	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Regulation of soil quality	Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
				Water conditions	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
				Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration								H	H		H	H	

Section	Division	Group	Class	Bacteria	Birds	Cephalopods	Epifauna	Fish	Infauna	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Marine mammals	Microphytobenthos	Phytoplankton	Zooplankton		
Cultural	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting	Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions	M	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	M	M		
			Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through passive or observational interactions	M	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	H	M	M	
		Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable scientific investigation or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Characteristics of living systems that enable education and training	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of culture or heritage		H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H				
			Characteristics of living systems that enable aesthetic experiences	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
	Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Elements of living systems that have symbolic meaning		H	H	H	H		H	H	H				H	
			Elements of living systems that have sacred or religious meaning		H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H				H
			Elements of living systems used for entertainment or representation	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
		Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Characteristics or features of living systems that have an existence value	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
			Characteristics or features of living systems that have an option or bequest value	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H		H	H

Table 3. Existing linkages and their likelihood of contribution to the capacity to supply ecosystem services (according to CICES 5.1) per functional biotic group. The three codes indicate High (1), Medium (0.01), or Low (0.001) contribution. Empty cells indicate no contribution. For option S1 (Table 1) only the none-empty cells apply.

10 Key proxy metrics to estimate the ecosystem Service Supply Potential

Functional group estimates from the North Sea EwE model for each year of the simulation's duration (1991-2020) were extracted to provide average and 95th percentile estimates for biotic groups biomass and production estimates (Figure 2). To that end functional groups as they occur in the EwE model were aggregated into the biotic groups required for this ecosystem services assessment (Figure 2 and Table 4). Data could not be aggregated to provide biomass and production estimates for microphytobenthos, macroalgae, or macrophytes as these biotic groups are not explicitly modelled in the North Sea EwE model. Focussing on the functional groups occurring in the North Sea EwE model: various shark and seabird groups were the least productive, while phytoplankton, zooplankton, bacteria, and benthos (epifauna and infauna) groups were among the most productive groups (Figure 2A). The highest biomass was attributed to individual infauna and epifauna functional groups, followed by copepods and phytoplankton, while various shark and seabird functional groups had the lowest simulated biomass for the North Sea (Figure 2B). When aggregated into biotic groups as used in this ecosystem services assessment the outcome remains largely the same, with phytoplankton and bacteria being the most productive biotic groups and epifauna and infauna supporting the greatest overall biomass (Table 4). The aggregated fish group had the third highest biomass of the biotic groups, greater than the aggregated biomasses of phytoplankton and zooplankton.

Figure 2. Production ($t.km^{-2}.year^{-1}$) and biomass ($t.km^{-2}$) for all functional groups in the North Sea Ecopath with Ecosim model. Points represent estimates of (A) production and (B) biomass in 2020 while the error bars provide the 95th percentile range based on estimates from 1991-2020.

Biotic group	Production ($t.km^{-2}.year^{-1}$)			Biomass ($t.km^{-2}$)		
	AVG	5 th	95 th	AVG	5 th	95 th
Bacteria	1826.2083	1811.2551	1845.4337	1.5518	1.5409	1.5657
Phytoplankton	2156.9977	2144.0576	2173.1074	7.5486	7.4702	7.6629
Zooplankton	159.4789	155.5328	162.4323	19.0738	18.3835	19.7269
Microphytobenthos	21.5699	1% of phytoplankton		0.7549	10% of phytoplankton	

Macroalgae	21.5699	1% of phytoplankton		0.7549	10% of phytoplankton	
Macrophytes	2.1569	0.1% of phytoplankton		0.0755	1% of phytoplankton	
Infauna	407.4324	404.5934	410.7528	289.1771	287.2789	290.4050
Epifauna	100.9244	99.6506	102.5886	216.6299	214.4915	219.4563
Cephalopods	0.2110	0.1893	0.2366	0.0462	0.0407	0.0544
Fish	20.5346	19.1965	22.2360	20.6165	17.7225	23.8122
Birds	0.0023	0.0021	0.0026	0.0061	0.0055	0.0068
Mammals	0.0032	0.0025	0.0043	0.0996	0.0923	0.1063

Table 4. Selected Services Supply Potential metrics per biotic group in the North Sea. For production and biomass the estimated averages as well as their 5th and 95th percentiles are given. When not available from EwE (shaded rows) they were derived from estimates of other biotic groups comparable in terms of their functioning, i.e. phytoplankton.

11 Service Supply Potential

The SSP per biotic group determined by the weighting options (Table 1) were applied in the estimation of the overall North Sea SSP showing that the different weighting options resulted in markedly different relative contributions of the biotic groups (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Contribution of the functional biotic groups to the overall North Sea Service Supply Potential of the three main sections of Ecosystem Services, i.e. Provisioning, Regulation & Maintenance and Cultural, depending on the various options in Table 1.

12 Threats to the capacity to supply ecosystem services

The application of the SCAIRM method in the North Sea context showed which ecosystem components were most threatened and what the main stressors were (Figure 4). 'Fish' and 'Cephalopods' emerged as the most threatened biotic groups, each with an Impact Risk of 94%, followed by the 'Mammals' and 'Birds' with 61% and 54% respectively. Other biotic groups associated with seabed habitats showed Impact Risks in the range of 30-50% and the phyto- and zooplankton associated with the water column habitat showed Impact Risk of approximately 10%. Fishing was the main threat across all biotic groups, contributing 51% to the overall threat. Of the remaining 18 sectoral activities another 23% was contributed by mining, non-renewable energy, tourism, and agriculture. As the cumulative impact risk consists of a total of 228 different and mostly negligible stressors that also differ between biotic groups (between 147 and 203 depending on the biotic group), the least important stressors were aggregated into "Other" such that they always represent less than 30% per biotic group. "Other" is further specified in SM5.

Figure 4. Cumulative Impact Risk per biotic group in the North Sea showing the relative contributions of the main stressors (i.e. Activities and their pressures).

Combining the SSP per biotic group depending on the weighting options (Figure 3) with the Impact Risk estimates per ecosystem component (Figure 4) provided the Impact Risk to the CtSES and how this was determined by the applied in the estimation of the SSP (Figure 5). Overall, the CtS Cultural ecosystem services section was the most threatened with an average Impact Risk of 50% (varying between 45-56% across ecosystem services classes), followed by the Provisioning ecosystem services with 46% (varying between 14-94%), and finally the Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services with 38% (with huge variation between 8-94%) (Figure 5). The variation within each section of ecosystem services is generally large, partly because of the wide range of class-level services covered by each section (see Table 3).

Figure 5. Cumulative Impact Risk on the capacity to Supply each of the three main ecosystem services sections depending on the different weighting options (Table 1) to estimate the Service Supply Potential per biotic group in the North Sea. The error bars indicate the range (minimum-maximum) of the ecosystem services classes within the ecosystem services sections (see Table 2).

The ultimate assessment of anthropogenic threats on the CtSES was based on what was considered the most elaborate weighting option S4 (Table 1) showing how Impact Risk passes through the full linkage framework (Figure 6). The main threats to the CtSES overall came from marine food production: primarily fishing but also aquaculture. While there were minor differences between the three major ecosystem services sections, i.e. Provisioning, Regulation & Maintenance, and Cultural, fishing always contributed more than half of the Impact Risk. The main difference between the major ecosystem services sections can be seen in the ranking of activities, where the third most significant impact (contributing 5-6% to Impact Risk) was agriculture for Provisioning ecosystem services (i.e. through nutrients and contaminants), mining for Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services (i.e. through physical disturbance of the seafloor) and coastal infrastructure for Cultural ecosystem services (i.e. through habitat loss and disturbance).

Figure 6. Sankey diagram based on the most elaborate estimation of SSP (option S4 in Table 1) showing how the human activities and their pressures impact the functional biotic groups in the North Sea and subsequently the capacity to supply ecosystem services (represented at class level, see Table 2). The flows represent Impact Risk, in case of the stressors their contribution to it and in case of the receptors the degree to which they suffer from it. The colours correspond to the ecosystem service sections as in Table 2 and Figure 5.

13 Discussion

This North Sea proof of concept confirmed that the proposed CIA-based method can accomplish a (semi-)quantitative assessment of the cumulative impacts on the CtSES. Its application in other marine ecosystems may require alternative, less data-heavy, information sources for each of the methodological steps. Despite the North Sea being one of the most information-rich marine regions, it still relied on several, often strong, assumptions and/or simplifications. These assumptions are discussed below with suggestions on how to advance toward better future assessments of the CtSES in the North Sea as well as other (and often less data-rich) marine regions.

14 Cumulative Impact Assessment

For the CIA of the North Sea ecosystem and its relevant components, we applied the SCAIRM method (Piet et al., 2023) which has the advantage that it is comprehensive and can also be applied in data-poor situations entirely based on expert judgement while allowing the use of available quantitative information in more data-rich situations. To extend this North Sea assessment to also cover the cumulative impacts on the CtSES, we matched the CIA assessment endpoints, i.e. ecosystem components, to biotic groups weighted with their estimated SSP depending on their functioning in the environmental system and the goods and benefits the ecosystem services are expected to supply in the socio-economic system (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011). For simplicity we only considered the functioning of the biotic groups without any consideration of the habitats in which they occurred as did Culhane et al. (2018). While this would be feasible in the North Sea, it comes with considerable additional requirements for information on different habitat-specific vulnerabilities and functioning to achieve its full potential. The use of biotic groups without habitat specification was deemed to be adequate for the purposes of this study to provide 1) a framework of the assessment of CtSES and 2) a first (semi-)quantitative assessment of the main threats to the North Sea CtSES. These main threats are identified in terms of their contribution to the Impact Risk as calculated by SCAIRM. These Impact Risk estimates should be considered an upper limit of the potential impact which, in order to be precautionary can be assumed to reflect a worst-case situation.

While the SCAIRM method was applied in this North Sea proof of concept, similar but less elaborate CIA exist for many other marine ecosystems (see e.g. <https://www.ices.dk/advice/ESD/Pages/Ecosystem-overviews.aspx>).

15 Service Supply Potential

The SSP adopted from Teixeira et al. (2019) and Culhane et al. (2019) represents the functioning of each of the biotic groups together with their likelihood to contribute to the CtS of each of the specific ecosystem services. In developing an improved estimation of SSP, we distinguished different options that can be applied depending on the availability of information and expertise. The default (Option S1) is based on Culhane et al. (2019) and assumes that SSP is equal across all possible linkages. A first and probably biggest improvement can be achieved through the key proxy metrics representing the functioning that determines the SSP (Option S2). This was based on a review of indicators for ecosystem services assessments by von Thenen et al. (2020). It is striking that most of the indicators in the review cover the least Informative type of metric (i.e. presence/absence), but not surprising as this also comes with the least demands on the availability of information. It appears that, in general, the selection of indicators has been rather haphazard, with indicators often included that do not necessarily represent the biotic group or its functioning, but rather other characteristics such as specific

management actions to protect the biotic groups (e.g. “Extent of MPAs/no-take zones”) or specific environmental variables (e.g. “pH”, “Oxygen concentration” or “Nutrients concentration”) which are at best crude substitutes of the SSP. The appropriate proxy metrics identified in this study, along with the selected key proxy metrics, should help to resolve this. For the selection of the key proxy metrics, we interpreted the ecosystem processes and functions in terms of their contribution to services and ultimately goods and benefits (see table 1) which implied that this could be represented both by the amount (i.e. biomass and/or extent of habitat) as well as a rate (i.e. productivity, e.g. tonnes.year⁻¹). For estimation of the SSP this implied that, for all the Provisioning services and most of the Regulation & Maintenance services, the production of the biotic group was considered the best key proxy metric to represent SSP. For the Provisioning services, this follows from the fact that harvesting of biomass is also a rate and productivity was confirmed to be a key metric in a study of indicators for seafood Provisioning services which identified surplus production as the best indicator (Piet et al., 2017). Harvesting (i.e. fisheries catches) more than the surplus production causes an impact on the asset (i.e. fish spawning stock biomass), thus interfering with future harvests and hence compromising sustainability. The Impact Risk calculated in this study essentially reflects the risk that this occurs. For the Regulation & Maintenance services, production was also assumed appropriate because much of the functioning that drives the supply of these services are linked to production rates of specific biotic groups. One exception is the “Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events” group, as processes like sediment stabilisation, accumulation, and/or wave attenuation are determined by the amount of biomass of notably biotic groups such as macroalgae, microphytobenthos, macrophytes and epifauna and infauna (Hu, 2014; Spalding, 2014; Yallop, 1994). Part of the Cultural services, i.e. the “Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting” which is about the standing stock of the relevant biotic groups was thought to be best represented by abundance or biomass. For the other Cultural ecosystem services, i.e. “Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting”, we assumed presence would suffice despite that the title suggests that the service is entirely decoupled from its current state and (associated) presence in the environment. This should adequately reflect that a depleted natural resource, such as the extinction of a species, would negatively impact this ecosystem services. Composition, such as in terms of species richness, could be an alternative or complementary key proxy metric (see Table 2) but not applied in this study as it could not be calculated by the available foodweb model.

Food webs play a central role in our understanding of ecosystem dynamics, with associated studies providing key information on the linkages and interactions between biotic groups and how these can be impacted by human activities (Belgrano, 2019). Foodweb models such as EwE have been used previously to calculate the type of metrics that can be used to represent the SSP (Horn, 2021; Liqueste, 2016). However, when estimating the SSP for each of the biotic groups we need to acknowledge that their actual contribution may not always be proportional to the selected key proxy metric because their roles, distributions, or other characteristics differ, or simply because not all species or species groups within those biotic groups contribute proportional to what the metric suggests. Moreover, as ecosystem services ultimately lead to goods and benefits that contribute to human well-being (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011), societal preferences may affect the contribution of biotic groups. We attempted to capture this issue with the expert judgement-based estimation of the likelihood that the biotic group contributes to the SSP. These likelihood estimates capture different factors, all assumed to be relevant, but for which there is little evidence to quantify them, or combine them, into weighting factors specific to each biotic group-ecosystem services linkage such that they allow an improved estimation of the Impact Risk on the CtSES. The default likelihood of 1 indicates that all production can potentially contribute to the supply of that service. If there is evidence or

good reason to assume otherwise, as when only part of the biotic group contributes, a likelihood <1 was applied. Fish and benthos are examples where only the production of commercial fish species and benthic crabs, shrimps and Nephrops was included with a likelihood of 1. For seabirds and mammals, the potential to contribute to the provisioning services was assumed to be limited to specific species and mostly local (e.g., whaling in Norway or Faroe Islands) and hence it received an arbitrary low weighting of 0.1%. Because SCAIRM only assesses the direct cumulative impacts on the biotic groups (Piet et al., 2023), the extension to ecosystem services only considered direct links as well. For example the link between marine mammal biomass and cultural benefits was included but not indirect links such as importance of zooplankton or fish as mediators of marine mammal biomass and its associated cultural benefits.

16 Estimating the capacity to supply ecosystem services

Despite the advancements made in this study, estimating the CtSES is still reliant on several assumptions. In this study we attempted to make those explicit through the application of different weighting options in the estimation of SSP. These were by no means intended to be fully comprehensive but they serve to illustrate how assumptions may affect the outcome of the assessment and were therefore primarily intended to initiate a process to further elaborate the underlying issues and drive future developments. One of those issues is conceptual in that from the perspective of a social-ecological system, this exercise would sit exclusively in the ecological system but for the estimation of the SSP we need to make inferences from the types of social and economic goods and benefits obtained and how or where these are acquired, all of which belonging to the social system if strictly interpreted. Instead of considering this contradictory assert this confirms the role of ecosystem services in linking biophysical structure, processes, and functions with the derived social and economic values and benefits (Quintessence, 2016) and hence only confirms their importance as a shared concept in both the ecological and the social systems (Biggs et al., 2012; Maes et al., 2012; Liqueste et al., 2013; Mee et al., 2015). It also underlines the observation by Schirpke et al. (2022) that the assessment of Cultural ecosystem services poses various conceptual and methodological difficulties, including unclear definitions and the challenge of separating services, values, and benefits, which are often strongly interwoven (Bieling, 2014; Hausmann, 2016). Moreover, the choice of weighting options based on a perception of how biotic groups are linked to ecosystem services (S1) or the goods and benefits obtained from those services (S3) could be considered exemplary of the point made by Diaz et al. (2018) that societal preference mediates the relationship between people and the CtSES. The plea is therefore to make such societal preferences explicit when assessing the CtSES.

17 Threats to the North Sea Capacity to Supply ecosystem services

This assessment of the cumulative impacts on the North Sea CtSES has shown that at least in this marine ecosystem the CtSES is severely threatened by the current human activities and their pressures, with about half of the CtSES potentially at risk, varying between 50% of the Cultural ecosystem services, 46% of the Provisioning ecosystem services, and 38% of the Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services but with often huge variation within these broad ecosystem services sections, partly because of the diverse nature of the services included in those sections. Because the SCAIRM method at the basis of this assessment is intended to be precautionary, the actual decrease in the CtSES compared to an undisturbed situation is probably lower. The estimation is also dependent on many assumptions including how the

SCAIRM output can be matched to the EwE biotic groups, the choice of appropriate key proxy metrics for each of the ecosystem services, and other considerations captured in the likelihood estimates and ultimately in the weighting options. Notably the considerations now captured by the likelihood estimates are usually ignored or implicit but were shown to considerably affect the outcome of the assessment and should probably be the first to be further developed to improve the assessment of cumulative impacts on the CtSES.

18 Relevance to the wider context

Ecosystem services play a key role in extending the relevance of CIAs beyond biodiversity and the ecological system. The results from this study help in understanding how the anthropogenic threats may impact the natural capital and the societal goods and benefits it provides (Maes et al., 2012; Mee et al., 2015). As such it is relevant in the context of social-ecological systems thinking and ecosystem-based management aimed not only at the conservation of biodiversity and its intrinsic value but also preserve its capacity to supply goods and benefits, which may represent monetary value. These ecocentric and anthropocentric perspectives should therefore be considered complementary when providing science advice for management. Because ecosystem services are supposed to cross the production boundary and occur both in the marine ecosystem as well as the socio-economic system (Culhane et al., 2019b) it justifies a consideration of societal preferences when assessing the cumulative impacts on the CtSES despite that the cascade model puts it exclusively in the environmental system (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011). This is illustrated by the assessment of the CtS provisioning services in this study showing that without considering societal preferences the results are based on the assumption that half of our seafood comes from plankton (see Option S2 in Table 1 and Figure 3) which is known not to be the case and would thus prevent any uptake of the scientific advice. Moreover, these societal preferences and specific characteristics of the biotic groups (e.g. size of individuals as in Option S3) determine the potential interaction of the CtSES with additional built, human, and social capital (Burdon et al., 2022; Elliott, 2023) and hence will determine how natural capital contributes to the supply of goods and benefits.

For assessments aimed at identifying the main anthropogenic threats impacting the supply of goods and benefits it makes little difference if the 17 ES groups according to CICES are applied as opposed to the 18 NCP reporting categories used by IPBES within the generalizing perspective proposed by Diaz et al. (2018). In both cases the CtS Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services or Regulating NCP can be expected to be least affected by societal preferences (Figure 5). In addition to the more tangible goods and benefits that natural capital may supply, nature's contributions to people (Diaz et al., 2018) also consider the cultural, spiritual, and inspirational values. The assumptions represented in the weighting options (i.e. S3 versus S2) can be considered to reflect the central and pervasive role that societal preferences play in these types of assessments, whether based on ecosystem services or nature's contributions to people.

This assessment method can also be aligned to the concepts used in an ecosystem accounting context (EEA, 2018) where the assets are represented by the biotic groups that make up biodiversity (UN, 2021) with characteristics captured in the condition account and the flows are represented by the selected key proxy metrics assumed to characterize how the ecosystem processes and functioning turn into services (Maes, 2013; Burdon et al., 2022). This method thus shows how cumulative impacts of anthropogenic stressors (as captured in a pressure account) on the (condition of the) ecosystem assets converted into a change of the ecosystem account.

19 Conclusion

This North Sea proof of concept shows that an existing CIA can be extended into an assessment of the cumulative impacts on the CtSES based on a (semi-) quantitative estimation of the functioning of biotic groups. The results show the extent to which this CtSES is threatened by specific stressors which is relevant to guide ecosystem-based management towards a (more) sustainable exploitation of the marine ecosystems. While showcased for the North Sea ecosystem, it can similarly be applied to other marine ecosystems and could even inform such assessments in the terrestrial domain. By improving the integration across scientific domains it allows ecosystem-based management to include all dimensions of sustainability (i.e. environmental, social and economic) and should ultimately improve informed decision making to conserve natural ecosystems and the benefits they provide for human societies.

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Supplementary Material

SM1: Linkage framework

The basis of any assessment is a so-called linkage framework (or conceptual model) consisting of impact chains that connect sectoral human activities and their pressures with the ecosystem components (i.e. species groups consisting of a selection of species) they can potentially impact. The categorisation of these human activities and pressures follow from the typologies given in the tables below. These typologies are from Piet et al. (2023) were adopted and improved from (Knights et al., 2015; Borgwardt et al., 2019).

Table 1.1: Activities and operations typology

Activity	Operation
Agriculture	Cultivation of crops and maintenance of pasture
	Atmospheric emissions, runoff of nutrients due to livestock
Angling and sport fishing	Catch, release and stockings
Artificial reefs	Construction (habitat change, emissions from boats)
	Operations (causing localised changes in hydrography)
Beach replenishment	Habitat change, smothering, contaminants
Yachting/Watersports (without engine)	Operations
Boating/Watersports (with engine)	Boating - General (anti-fouling, ballast water exchange, litter, waste)
	Boating - Mooring/anchoring/beaching/launching (interaction with seafloor)
	Boating - Steaming (collisions)
	Diving - general (anti-fouling, litter, waste)
	Diving - mooring/anchoring/beaching/launching (interaction with seafloor)
	Diving - operations (trampling, spp extraction)
	Diving - steaming (collisions)
	Water sports - mooring/anchoring/beaching/launching
	Water sports - steaming (collisions, atmospheric emissions)
	Collecting (bird eggs, individuals, curios, bait)
	Bird eggs - (trampling, removal of individuals)
	Curios and keeping aquariums - (trampling, removal or release of individuals)
	Peels (boulder turning) - (trampling, removal of individuals)
	Shellfish hand collecting - (trampling, removal of individuals)
Commercial Cruise (large)	Cruise ships
Culverting lagoons	Construction (habitat change, smothering)
	Operations (causing localised changes in hydrography)
Dredging (including capital and maintenance)	Capital dredging - extraction of substrate
	Capital dredging - spoil/waste disposal
	Maintenance dredging - extraction of substrate
	Maintenance dredging - spoil/waste disposal
Ex-situ aquaculture	Water abstraction, waste discharge
Fishing: Benthic trawling and suction/hydraulic dredges	Benthic trawls and dredges - general (e.g. anti-fouling, litter, lost gear)
	Benthic trawls and dredges - mooring/anchoring
	Benthic trawls and dredges - operations
	Benthic trawls and dredges - steaming
	Suction/hydraulic dredges - general

	Suction/hydraulic dredges - mooring/anchoring
	Suction/hydraulic dredges - operations
	Suction/hydraulic dredges - steaming
Fishing: Nets, potting/creeling	Nets - general (litter, lost gear, antifoulants)
	Nets - operational (catch, bycatch, waste products)
	Nets - set up/recovery (interaction with seafloor, atmospheric emissions)
	Potting/creeling - general (litter, lost gear)
	Potting/creeling - operational (catch, bycatch, waste products)
	Potting/creeling - set up/recovery (interaction with seafloor)
Fishing: Pelagic trawls and long-line pelagic	Pelagic trawls - general (anti-fouling, ballast water, litter, lost gear)
	Pelagic trawls - mooring/anchoring (interaction with seafloor)
	Pelagic trawls - operations (catch, bycatch, waste products)
	Pelagic trawls - steaming (atmospheric emissions, collisions)
Flood and coastal defence - Artificial Structures	Construction sea walls/breakwaters/groynes
	Operations (causing localised changes in hydrography)
Forestry	Cultivation of forestry (e.g. irrigation, drainage)
Hunting, including wildfowling and spearfishing	Wildfowling (shooting, lead shot, boating)
In-situ aquaculture	Fin-fish - operational ¹
	Fin-fish - set-up ²
	Macro-algae – operational ¹
	Macro-algae - set-up ²
	Shellfish - operational ¹
	Shellfish - setup ²
Land claim and conversion (including construction and operation)	Construction (e.g. habitat change, smothering, increased turbidity)
	Operations (causing localised changes in hydrography)
Manufacturing: Industry with discharges - operational	Industry with discharges into coastal waters
Marinas and dock/port facilities	Construction (e.g. habitat change, sealing)
	Operations (e.g. litter, light, noise, waste disposal)
Military	Marine dumped munitions
	General (e.g. anti-fouling, ballast water exchange, litter)
	Mooring/anchoring/beaching/launching
	Operations (e.g. seismic activities, sonar)
	Steaming (atmospheric emissions, collisions)
Mining, extraction of materials	Inorganic mine and particulate waste - extraction of substrate
	Inorganic mine and particulate waste - spoil/waste disposal
	Maerl - extraction of substrate
	Maerl - spoil/waste disposal
	Rock/Minerals - coastal quarrying - extraction of substrate
	Rock/Minerals - coastal quarrying - spoil/waste disposal
	Sand/gravel aggregates - extraction of substrate
	Sand/gravel aggregates - spoil/waste disposal
Non-renewable power stations (land-based, coastal)	Construction (jetties and intake wells)
	Operations
Oil and Gas	Construction (e.g. drilling, laying pipelines, oil spills)
	Decommissioning (e.g. oil spills, removal of infrastructure)
	Exploration (e.g. seismic surveys, exploratory drilling)
	Operations (e.g. waste fluids and particulates, oil spills)
Research	General (e.g. anti-fouling, litter, oils leaching)
	Mooring/anchoring/beaching/launching
	Operations
	Steaming
Shipping	General (e.g. anti-fouling, ballast water exchange, litter)
	Mooring/anchoring/beaching/launching
	Steaming
Shore recreational activities	Public beach - general (trampling, litter)
	Seawater swimming pool
Telecoms and Electricity	Operational communications (electromagnetic)
	Laying electric cables
Tidal sluices and barrages	Tidal barrages - construction (e.g. localised sealing of habitat)
	Tidal barrages - operational (e.g. barrier to movement)
	Tidal sluices - construction (e.g. localised sealing of habitat)
	Tidal sluices - operational (e.g. localised changes in hydrography)
Tourist resort	Construction (e.g. habitat change, sealing, smothering)

¹ waste products, anti-fouling, predator control, disease and disease control, infrastructure effects on local hydrography, escapees, litter, anchoring/mooring of boats

² atmospheric emissions for transport of brood stock/juveniles, interaction with seafloor during set-up of infrastructure, loss of gear

	Operations (e.g. effluent discharge, abstraction of water, litter)
Transport (land-based)	Run off from roads, emissions, etc.
Urban dwellings and commercial developments	Construction (e.g. habitat change, sealing)
	Operational (e.g. contaminants e.g. from petrol stations, litter)
Waste management - operational disposal including sewage treatment	Operations (effluent discharge, thermal discharge)
Wave energy	Construction (cable laying - localised habitat change, noise)
	Operations (electro-magnetic cables, localised change in flow of water)
Wind farms	Construction (e.g. installation of turbines on seafloor, laying cables)
	Operations (e.g. active cables on seafloor, moving turbines)

Table 1.2: Pressure typology

Pressure theme	Pressures
Biological disturbance	Extraction of living resources
	Introduction of genetically modified species
	Introduction of Microbial pathogens
	Introduction of non-indigenous species
	Translocations of species (native or non-native)
Chemical changes, chemicals and other pollutants	Changes in input of organic matter
	Ghost nets and other litter causing entanglement
	Introduction of Non-synthetic compounds
	Introduction of Radionuclides
	Introduction of Synthetic compounds
	Microplastics and other litter that may be ingested
	N&P Enrichment
	pH changes
Salinity changes	
Energy	Continuous noise
	Electromagnetic changes
	Impulsive noise
	Input of light
	Thermal changes
Physical change	Abrasion/Damage
	Barrier to species movement
	Changes in Siltation
	Changes to hydrological conditions
	Death or Injury by Collision
	Disturbance (visual) of species
	Extraction of non-living resources
	Smothering
	Total Habitat Loss

SM2: Introduction SCAIRM method

Risk-based approaches have often been at the basis of CIAs for marine management (Stelzenmuller et al., 2018). Such approaches apply either a likelihood-consequence approach for estimating the risk of a rare or unpredictable event (i.e., calamities; Williams et al., 2011), or an exposure-effect approach which is considered more suitable when assessing existing and (more or less) continuous or frequently occurring pressures (Smith et al., 2007 and Knights et al., 2015). The calculation of exposure and effect potential in SCAIRM includes many known concepts often used in the context of environmental risk assessments (see figure 2.1). The exposure in space and time was defined as the likelihood that the receptor (i.e. ecosystem component) is co-occurring with the stressor (i.e. pressure caused by an activity) and hence potentially affected by it (Piet et al., 2021). The effect potential can be assumed conceptually identical to sensitivity (Laffoley et al., 2000), and is a function of its ability to avoid interaction, tolerate or resist change (*Resistance*), and/or recover from impact (*Resilience*) (Tillin et al., 2010). Following Weißhuhn et al. (2018) stating that sensitivity is the susceptibility to hazard, resistance was estimated as a function of hazard

(according to ISO 31000, 2018), magnitude and frequency of the stressor together with the responsiveness of the receptor to that stressor.

The model introduces Impact Risk (IR) as the key concept that allows cumulation across pressures. There is a wealth of categorical risk-based approaches that have estimated IR in various guises (Knights et al., 2015; Piet et al., 2015; 2017; 2019; Borgwardt et al., 2019, Galparsoro et al., 2021, Galparsoro et al., 2022). A roadmap towards a fully quantitative calculation of IR was recently provided by (Piet et al., 2021), who defined IR as the change in equilibrium state (i.e. biomass or abundance compared to undisturbed) of the receptor caused by a stressor. Albeit covering only a few stressor-receptor causal chains, this provided a major advancement from the previous estimates of IR as it now becomes tangible and can be readily understood and interpreted by any recipient of the assessment outcome. In this way, the output allows an interpretation of the assessment outcome, e.g. in relation to IUCN criteria (IUCN, 2012).

Figure 2.1. Calculation of Impact Risk as the key concept that allows cumulation across pressures from Exposure and Effect Potential. These, in turn, can be estimated from respectively the spatial distributions of the stressor (i.e. activity-pressure combinations) and receptor (i.e. ecosystem components) and population dynamics parameters resilience and resistance if quantitative information is available. If lacking, these can be estimated from the boxed terms using categorical scores based on expert judgement.

The SCAIRM method is essentially a risk-based approach where the key term, Impact Risk (IR), is calculated from estimates of Exposure and Effect Potential (Figure 2.1). SCAIRM is designed for application in data-poor and data-rich marine ecosystems as it can be based on respectively categorical expert-judgement scores (Piet et al., 2023) which are semi-quantitative at best but can also be based on fully quantitative information (Piet et al., 2021) if available. An advantage is that this allows the continued application of the method for assessments while there is an ongoing process of piecemeal improvements when better and often quantitative information becomes available. The method is supposed to capture the ‘best of both worlds’ in terms of how it handles data availability: it builds on the comprehensive categorical risk-based approaches (Knights et al., 2015; Piet et al., 2015; 2017; 2019; Borgwardt et al., 2019), but altered them where needed so as to obtain an IR that is conceptually identical to the IR from the quantitative approach so that both can now be harmonized into a single method that has the advantage of (1) being comprehensive and flexible in terms of its application in other ecosystems as the categorical approach allows every impact chain to be easily weighted using the expert-judgement scores, while it allows (2) a gradual transition towards an increasingly more quantitative assessment. The two aspects of risk that together determine Impact Risk are further elaborated below.

Exposure

Exposure usually only reflects the spatial overlap which implies that a default 100% temporal overlap is assumed and hence no seasonal patterns of the stressor or receptor apply. Three options apply for the estimation of Exposure depending on the availability of information:

- If no quantitative information is available then the qualitative Exposure score is based on Extent and Dispersal categories such as in (Borgwardt, 2018), where the extent score reflects the overlap between the activity and the ecosystem component which is then combined with a pressure-specific dispersal.
- If there is information on the spatial distribution of the ecosystem component and quantitative information on the spatial distribution of the activity, i.e. spatial maps, but not of the (dispersal of) the pressure the activity extent is used but complemented with a pressure-specific dispersal based on the buffer according to (Lonsdale et al., 2020) or else the existing dispersal scores.
- Ideally, there is quantitative information available on spatial distribution of both the pressure and the ecosystem component. In that case Piet et al. (2021) applies who distinguishes increasingly more accurate Exposure metrics depending on data availability, i.e. spatiotemporal information on pressure magnitude and ecosystem component density.

Effect Potential

Given the exposure of a receptor to a stressor in a specific unit of space and time, the Effect Potential (EP) describes the degree to which this receptor is likely to be affected

by that stressor (i.e. activity and its pressure) as a change in biomass or abundance relative to an undisturbed situation. The estimation of EP is essentially a function of Resistance and Resilience which, in turn, can be estimated using quantitative information or, if lacking, categorical scores from literature or expert judgement. *Resilience* is the time after impact until full recovery (to the receptor's original undisturbed state) which can be estimated using the receptor-specific expert judgement scores from Knights et al. (2015). For *Resistance* a more elaborate approach was developed which better captures the intricacies that determine resistance hence providing a more realistic score. In this approach resistance contains a behavioural component that, in case of co-occurrence (i.e. in a specific grid cell based on spatial distributions in the specific assessment period as also applied for Exposure), determines whether an interaction event actually occurs. Depending on the nature of the interaction, the (essentially within-grid cell) likelihood of an interaction is determined by (1) the behaviour of the receptor in relation to the stressor, i.e. within the spatial unit(s) used to estimate exposure, and (2) the frequency of occurrence of the stressor (i.e. within the temporal unit of exposure, usually year). Two conceptually different mechanisms can be distinguished that determine, in case of exposure, the nature of the interaction and thus resistance:

- 1) **Intermittent interactions** where EP is determined by the likelihood of interaction and its consequence. The likelihood of interaction is determined by the frequency of occurrence of the stressor and the behavioural response of the ecosystem component to that pressure, i.e. its capacity to avoid interaction. Note this interaction occurs at spatiotemporal scales much smaller than those at which Exposure was estimated. The consequence of an interaction event is subsequently determined by characteristics of the ecosystem component specific to that pressure (captured by the Hazard) and the Magnitude of that pressure. The EP estimation is based on four parameters, i.e. *Frequency* and *Magnitude* of the stressor, its *Hazard* in relation to the ecosystem component and the *Behaviour* of the receptor (ecosystem component) in relation to the stressor.
- 2) **Continuous interactions** where EP estimation only requires two parameters, i.e. *Hazard* of the stressor in relation to the ecosystem component and *Magnitude* of the stressor.

Each of these resistance parameters and how they were scored are further elaborated in annex 2 and Piet et al. (2023). This then allows the interpretation of these concepts in a population dynamics context (Pitcher et al., 2017), where a populations' resistance is reflected in the depletion rate and the resilience in the population growth rate.

SM3. Cross link between SCAIRM ecosystem components and the biotic groups used to estimate the Service Supply Potential (based on Culhane et al., 2018).

Ecosystem Components	Bacteria	Birds	Cephalopods	Epifauna	Fish	Infauna	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Microphytobenthos	Phytoplankton	Marine mammals	Zooplankton
Deep-sea bed	X			X		X						
Circalittoral rock*	X			X		X						
Infralittoral rock*	X			X		X	X	X	X			
Littoral rock*	X			X		X	X	X	X			
Sublittoral sediment	X			X		X	X	X	X			
Littoral sediment	X			X		X	X	X	X			
Pelagic water column	X			X			X			X		X
Fish & Cephalopods			X		X							
Mammals											X	
Birds		X										

* and other hard substrata

SM4. Indicators from von Thenen et al. (2020) matched to the different ecosystem services and the biotic groups as they occur in Table 2 and throughout the paper. The cascade type matches the terms as used in the cascade model (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011).

21 Provisioning ecosystem services

Division / Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Biotic Groups										
			Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobenthos	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine Mammals
Biomass													
Cultivated marine plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Cultured seaweed abundance	Service				X							
	No. of species (plants, algae from aquaculture)	Service				X							
	Plants from in situ aquaculture	Service				X							
	Seaweed stock (area, biomass)	Service				X							
	Quality of seaweed stock	Service				X							
	Abundance/biomass	Service				X							
Fibers and other materials from all biota for direct use or processing													
Reared marine animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Animals from in situ aquaculture	Service							X	X	X		
	Fish and shellfish populations (biomass, abundance)	Service							X	X	X		
	No. of species (animals from aquaculture)	Service							X	X	X		
	Quality of the fish, shellfish	Service							X	X	X		
	Abundance/biomass	Service							X	X	X		
	Fibbers and other materials from all biota for direct use or processing	Service							X	X	X		
Wild marine plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Diverging trends between area and productivity of mangrove forests	Capacity					X						
	Primary production (gross, respiration and net)	Capacity		X	X	X	X						
	No. of species of wild plants, algae	Service				X	X						
	Seaweed stock (area, biomass)	Service				X							
	Wild plants	Service				X	X						
	Wild seaweed abundance	Service				X							
	Quality of the seaweed stock	Service				X							
	Biomass production over stem diameter classes	Capacity					X						
	Fibbers and other materials from all biota for direct use or processing	Service		X		X	X						
	Quantity of raw material	Service		X		X	X						
	<i>Rhizophora</i> spp. mangrove charcoal production	Service					X						
	Quality of raw material	Service		X		X	X						
	Quality of raw materials	Service		X		X	X						
	Generation of sand and mangrove wood	Service					X						
	Quantity of available raw material	Service		X		X	X						
	Macro and microalgae	Service		X		X	X						
Wild marine animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Coral size and substrate cover	Capacity						X					
	Density of fish	Service								X			
	Estimates of species abundance (fish, shellfish, marine mammals and birds)	Service						X	X	X	X	X	
	Fish abundance per site	Service								X			

Division / Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Biotic Groups										
			Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobenthos	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine Mammals
	Fish abundance	Service									X		
	Fish and shellfish populations (biomass, abundance)	Service								X	X	X	
	Fish biomass (standing stock)	Service										X	
	Fish diversity and biomass	Service										X	
	Fish production	Service										X	
	Presence of reef-associated fish	Service										X	
	Relative fish abundance	Service										X	
	Sea food productivity	Service								X	X	X	
	Wild fauna	Service						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Area of marine protected areas	Capacity							X	X	X		
	Area of no-take zones	Capacity							X	X	X		
	Composition and relative importance of predators along a gradient of fishing intensities	Capacity						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Food web structure and robustness (various properties)	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Functional variation of predatory performance	Capacity						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Marine food chain	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Areas to support seafood production	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
	Coral size, substrate cover	Capacity						X					
	Mangrove extent as habitat for fisheries	Capacity					X				X		
	State of the seagrass meadows	Capacity					X						
	Distribution of fish or larvae	Capacity						X	X	X			
	Presence of fry preys	Capacity					X				X		
	Fish stock overexploited, depleted or recovered	Service									X		
	Levels of selected chemical compounds in fish, where such compounds constitute tainting	Service									X		
	Quality of the fish, shellfish	Service							X	X	X		
	Sea food quality	Service							X	X	X		
	Fish food indicator	Service									X		
	Fibbers and other materials from all biota for direct use or processing	Service						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Quantity of raw material	Service						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Sponge diversity and abundance	Service							X				
	Quality of raw material	Service						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Quality of raw materials	Service						X	X	X	X	X	X
	Quantity of available raw material	Service						X	X	X	X	X	X
Genetic material from all biota (including seed, spore or gamete production)													
Genetic material from marine plants, algae or fungi	Presence and diversity of species with potential/actual useful genetic material	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Quality of species with potential/actual useful genetic material	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Genetic materials (DNA) from all biota	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Genetic material from marine animals	Presence and diversity of species with potential/actual useful genetic material	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Quality of species with potential/actual useful genetic material	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Genetic material from organisms	Genetic materials (DNA) from all biota	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

22 Regulation & Maintenance ecosystem services

Division/ Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobent	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine	
Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems														
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Bioremediation capacity	Capacity	X											
	Benthic biodiversity	Capacity			X				X	X				
	Presence of degrading microorganisms	Capacity	X											
	Fecal coliform	Service	X											
	Harmful algal bloom outbreaks	Service	X	X	X									
	Harmful algal bloom outbreaks	Service	X	X	X									
	Presence of pathogens	Service	X	X	X					X				
	Bacterial denitrification within the sediments	Service	X											
	Denitrification	Service	X											
	Denitrification	Service	X											
	Nutrient abatement	Service	X	X	X	X	X							
	Biochemical degradation capacity of COD	Capacity	X											
	Biological oxygen demand	Capacity	X											
	Chemical oxygen demand (COD) and biological oxygen demand (BOD)	Capacity	X											
	Number of dead zones	Capacity	X											
	Oxygen concentration	Capacity												
	Oxygen levels in water and sediment	Capacity												
	Oxyrisk	Capacity	X											
	Toxicity levels within species	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Abundance of suspension and surface deposit feeder	Capacity							X	X				
	Depletion in the number of suspension feeders, submerged vegetation and wetlands to filter water	Capacity					X	X	X	X				
	Distribution of Phragmites Australis	Capacity					X							
	Feeding modes and impact on certain pollutants	Capacity							X	X	X			
	Presence of bioturbator organisms	Capacity							X	X				
	Presence of floodplains, wetlands, estuaries, mangroves, benthic invertebrate species	Capacity			X	X	X		X	X				
	Presence of nitrophilous macroalgae in catchment basin	Capacity				X								
	Presence of suspension feeders	Capacity							X	X	X			
	Species composition and area covered with wetlands (following Ramsar convention definition)	Capacity			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	Particulate organic matter (POM) and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR)	Capacity		X		X								
	Ammonium and nitrate	Service	X	X	X	X	X							
	amount of N and P stored	Service	X	X	X	X	X							
	N-fixation	Service	X	X	X	X	X							
	Nitrogen accumulation	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Nitrogen and phosphorus retention	Service	X	X	X	X	X								
Nitrogen removal	Service	X	X	X	X	X								
Nitrogen removal rate	Service	X	X	X	X	X								
Nitrogen uptake	Service	X	X	X	X	X								
Nitrogen, phosphorus and heavy metals concentration and rate	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Nutrient abatement	Service	X	X	X	X	X								
Nutrients, POPs and HM removals	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					
Plant tissue nitrogen concentration	Service		X	X	X	X								
Quantity of nitrogen and phosphorus fixed by phytoplankton and kelp	Service		X		X									

Division/ Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobent	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine
	Removal of total nutrient content	Service	X	X	X	X	X						
	Seston reduction	Service							X	X			
	Seston uptake or Chl-a removal	Service						X	X	X			
	Total soil nitrogen in a salt marsh	Service											
	Bottom irradiance	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X						
	Function of fish as active or passive transporters and distributors of energy and materials	Service										X	
Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions													
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Extent of selected emerged, submerged and intertidal habitats	Capacity			X	X	X		X	X			
	Presence and elevation of biogenic habitat, e.g., saltmarsh beds; seagrass beds; bivalve, coral and polychaete reefs	Capacity			X	X	X		X	X			
	Change in erosion protection capacity	Capacity											
	Composite indices based on wave regime, tidal range, relative sea level, storm surge	Capacity											
	Composite indices based on extent of selected emerged, submerged and intertidal habitats	Capacity											
	Presence of mitten crab	Service							X				
	Length of natural coastal line	Capacity											
	amount of sediment prevented from erosion per ha of an ecosystem per year	Service											
	Beach profile (slope and width); extent of maintenance and improvement required to provide protection	Service											
	Sediment accretion	Service											
	Sediment accumulation rate	Service											
	Sediment deposition	Service											
	Shoreline erosion rate	Service											
	Composite indices based on wave regime, tidal range, relative sea level, storm surge	Capacity											
	amount of sediment prevented from sedimentation in natural channels used for shipping	Service											
	Health of wetland ecosystem	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Healthy growing coral reefs, mangroves and wetlands	Capacity				X			X				
	Kelp occurrence adjacent to human property	Capacity				X							
	Mangrove extent	Capacity					X						
	Plant cover	Capacity					X						
	Presence of seagrass meadow	Capacity					X						
	Temporal changes in mangrove extent	Capacity					X						
	Vegetation density	Capacity					X						
	Vegetation properties (marsh width, species, biomass production, density, stiffness, height)	Capacity					X						
	Water storage capacity for different intertidal habitats (e.g., sediment, saltmarsh, mangrove)	Capacity			X	X	X		X	X			
	Aboveground biomass	Capacity											
	Composite indices based on wave regime, tidal range, relative sea level, storm surge	Capacity											
	Hydrodynamics (hydroperiod, distance to a sediment supply)	Capacity											
	Rates of tidal and wind-driven currents	Capacity											
	Salinity/freshwater input	Capacity											
	Maximum depth (to calculate maximum wave height)	Capacity											
	Reduction of wave energy by nearshore and intertidal habitats	Service											
	Surge reduction	Service											
Vulnerability index based on relaxation time and return interval	Service												
Wave attenuation	Service												
Wave attenuation	Service												
Changing shoreline	Service												
Seabed morphology	Service												

Division/ Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobent	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine	
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Seagrass seed dispersal rates by fish and birds	Service					X							
	Abundance of seagrasses	Capacity					X							
	Biomass of sessile epifauna	Capacity							X					
	Composite metrics using percent cover of corals	Capacity							X					
	Coral extent and condition	Capacity							X					
	Distribution of Phragmites Australis	Capacity					X							
	Diversity and abundance of cold-water corals	Capacity							X					
	Habitat change	Capacity			X	X	X		X	X				
	Habitat health status	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Mangrove and seagrass extent	Capacity					X							
	Natural size of mangroves and density progression	Capacity					X							
	Presence of four coralline algae	Capacity			X									
	Protected area designated for its diverse habitat and abundant seabird colonies	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Size-frequency distributions of corals	Capacity							X					
	Submerged and intertidal habitats diversity	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Submerged and intertidal habitats,connectivity, diversity, trophic composition, oxygen, turbidity, species distribution.....	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Topographic complexity of corals	Capacity							X					
	Total coral cover	Capacity							X					
	Eelgrass productivity	Capacity					X							
	Mangrove biomass	Capacity					X							
	Annual production of fish juveniles	Service										X		
	Juvenile density	Service										X		
	Juvenile fish density	Service										X		
	Juvenile fish density, foraging efficiency for fish, recruitment	Service										X		
	Postlarvae production per hatchery	Service								X				
	% of nursery areas which are protected	Service										X		
	Area of habitat or density of biogenic habitat creating species "used" or identified as important for nursery or reproduction	Service										X		
	Depletion in the number of oyster reefs, seagrass beds and wetlands to provide nursery	Service			X	X	X		X	X				
	Intertidal biodiversity	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Macrophyte species richness	Service					X							
	Number and diversity of species using the area for nursery or reproduction	Service					X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	Nursery area	Service				X	X		X	X				
	Nursery areas	Service				X	X		X	X				
	Species abundance and richness	Service							X	X	X		X	
	Species distribution	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Structural complexity, nursery and feeding areas	Service										X		
	Connectivity, diversity, trophic composition	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Consumption of organisms by fish/ foodchain relationships	Capacity										X		
	Substrate character	Capacity												
	Occurrence of oxygen concentration < 6 mg/L	Capacity												
Oxygen level in water column	Capacity													
Dependence of off-site (commercial) populations	Service							X	X	X	X	X		
Genetic diversity	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Genetic diversity per population	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Secchi depth	Capacity													

Division/ Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobent	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine
Pest and disease control	Presence/absence/frequency of pests (e.g., algae blooms, foam, sea lice on farmed salmon)	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Quality of pest control species	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Distribution of alien species	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Presence of alien species	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Species richness	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Absence of pathogens	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Control of aquatic disease-bearing invertebrates and plants by fish	Service									X		
	Control of aquatic disease-bearing invertebrates and plants by fish	Service									X		
	Species richness	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Regulation of sediment quality	Density of bioturbators, algal production rates, (1/Secondary productivity) rates	Capacity		X	X	X		X	X	X			
	Number of operational taxonomic microbic units	Capacity	X		X								
	Soil (=sediment) chemical properties (pH, organic carbon, total nitrogen, available phosphorus, potassium)	Capacity											
	Decomposition of dissolved and particulate organic matter by bacteria and fungi in the sediments	Service	X										
Water conditions	Nitrogen and phosphorus aboveground and in soil (=sediment)	Service											
	Nutrient concentration, oxygen concentration	Capacity											
	Nutrients concentration	Capacity											
	Oxygen concentration	Capacity											
	Salinity	Capacity											
	Silica fluxes	Capacity	X	X	X			X					
	Oxygen emitted by primary production and kelp production	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Primary production rate	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Biogeochemical cycles (C, N, P)	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Nitrogen flux	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Environmental measurements: tidal inundation time (g/m ² /h), net flux (g/m ² /h), tidal height, salinity, nutrient concentrations...	Capacity											
	Relationship between fish, bioturbation, bottom conditions and nutrients release	Capacity							X	X	X		
	Assimilative and recycling capacity	Capacity	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			
	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Microbial breakdown and deposit feeders activity in the sediments	Capacity	X						X	X		
Leaf litter production		Capacity				X	X						
Aboveground biomass and dissolved organic matter		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
amount of CO ₂ sequestered		Service				X	X						
Blue C		Service				X	X						
C sequestration		Service				X	X						
C sequestration		Service				X	X						
C stock		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon and nitrogen concentration		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon and nitrogen storage in canopies		Service					X						
Carbon biomass		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon fixed by phytoplankton, mariculture kelp and cultured shellfish		Service		X		X			X				
Carbon flow		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon sequestration potential, carbon biomass		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon sequestration rate		Service	X			X	X						
Carbon stock		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon stock		Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbon stock in the soil		Service	X		X	X				X			
Dissolved organic and inorganic matter		Service											

Division/ Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobent	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine
	Estimates of the global pools of carbon and fluxes between them	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Levels of carbon in different components of the marine ecosystem	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Macrophyte biomass and carbon content	Service				X							
	Net photosynthetic rate	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Permanence of carbon sequestration	Service				X	X						
	Primary production	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Primary production	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Primary production (PP)	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Primary production -uptake; seagrass stock - storage, salt marshes stock - storage	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Sediment carbon density	Service											
	Soil carbon accumulation	Service	X				X			X			
	Standing carbon and nitrogen stock	Service	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Vegetation of carbon storage	Service		X	X	X	X						
	Carbon sequestration potential	Capacity				X	X						
	Evaporation rate	Service											

23 Cultural ecosystem services

Division / Group	Indicator	Cascade type	Bacteria	Phytoplankton	Microphytobenthos	Macroalgae	Macrophytes	Zooplankton	Epifauna	Infauna	Fish	Birds	Marine Mammals
Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting													
Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment	Abundance and diversity of key species of recreational interest	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Extent of marine protected areas, presence of iconic species	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Levels of selected chemical compounds in fish which constitute tainting	Service									X		
	Smell of decomposing algae	Service		X	X	X							
	Visual cover of algal mats	Service		X	X	X							
	Abundance and diversity of key species of recreational interest	Service							X	X	X	X	X
	Extent of marine protected areas	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Presence of coralligenous community or cetacean population	Service							X				X
	Presence of iconic/endangered species	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Status/population estimates of iconic species	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Species, habitats or ecosystems that are being or can potentially be studied to increase scientific knowledge	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Species, habitats or ecosystems that can potentially be studied for educational purposes	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	# of households that consider an area or aspects of an area as cultural heritage	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Species, habitats or ecosystems that can potentially form the core of contributing to a cultural custom, rite or way of life	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Abundance of key species of individual interest	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Uniqueness of a site	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting													
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	No. of Red List and iconic species	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Presence of endangered, protected, iconic and/or rare species or habitats	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Presence of endangered, protected, iconic and/or rare species or habitats	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Species, habitats or ecosystems that can potentially be worshipped or of significance to a religious belief	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Species, habitat or ecosystems that have or can potentially inspire any piece of artwork	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Extent of MPAs	Service				X	X		X	X	X	X
Presence of endangered, protected, iconic and/or rare species or habitats		Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Extent of MPAs		Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Presence of endangered, protected, iconic and/or rare species or habitats		Service				X	X		X	X	X	X	X

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SM1: Applied scores of the aspects of risk

Exposure (based on Dispersal and Extent)

This can be based on the combined extent and dispersal categories in (Borgwardt, 2018), where the extent score reflects the overlap between the activity and the ecosystem component which is then combined with a pressure-specific dispersal (see Figure SM1.0 and Table SM1.1). The dispersal scores were slightly modified in order to align with data-driven approaches and achieve more realistic spatial overlap values. Instead of a dispersal score of 1 in case of high dispersal because “the pressure can disperse beyond the local environment” (Borgwardt et al., 2019), a more realistic score was assumed equal to the Extent category “local”, i.e. 0.37. By simply multiplying numerical scores of extent and dispersal (or frequency and persistence), spatial (or temporal) effects may be either underestimated (when the scores are both small) or overestimated when they are both large. Moreover, no overlap without any dispersal would always result in a 0 score even though a pressure with moderate to high dispersal may result in co-occurrence despite a lack of actual overlap between the marine activity and the ecosystem component, or in case of a land-based activity the position of the river outlet. Therefore, the two scores were considered as chance processes when combining them into an overall spatial exposure score. This can be achieved by scaling the scores of both aspects between 0 and 1 and treat them as dependent chance processes to represent the likelihood of co-occurrence. The combined ‘likelihood’ is subsequently calculated according to a standard probability equal to the sum of both chances minus the product of both chances.

Table SM1.1. Interpretation and estimation of Exposure, as the likelihood that an ecosystem component is co-occurring with the pressure and hence potentially affected by it, based on Extent and Dispersal categories from previous studies, i.e. Knights et al. (2015) and Borgwardt et al. (2019), but with slightly adapted scores. Extent is defined as the overlap between the Activity and the Ecosystem Component. Dispersal as the potential of the pressure to spread and increase its spatial overlap with an Ecosystem Component beyond that of the Extent. Note that in the calculations the scores are expressed as fractions (0-1) but for presentation purposes we have expressed them as percentages (0-100%).

Exposure		Dispersal		
		None	Moderate	High
Extent		0	5	15
No overlap	0	0	5	15
Trace	1	1	6	16
Site	3	3	8	18
Local	37	37	40	46
Widespread Patchy	67	67	69	72
Widespread Even	100	100	100	100

Resistance (based on Hazard, Magnitude and Behaviour together with Frequency)

Table SM1.2. Hazard categories, their scores and how these can be interpreted in a conservation context. Hazard is defined as the relative depletion of the receptor from a single interaction with the stressor at maximum magnitude . Note that in the calculations the scores are expressed as fractions (0-1) but for presentation purposes we have expressed them as percentages (0-100%).

Hazard	Score	Interpretation
Negligible	0.001	No hazard. Similar to undisturbed or pristine
Sublethal low	0.1	Potentially unsustainable at low recovery potential*
Sublethal high	1	Potentially unsustainable at moderate recovery potential*
Lethal low	10	Potentially unsustainable at high recovery potential*
Lethal high	100	Likely to be causing serious or irreversible harm

* Thresholds for potentially unsustainability were based on the Resilience values in relation to sustainability.

Table SM1.3. Magnitude categories, their scores and how these can be interpreted in a conservation context. Magnitude is defined as the average strength of the Pressure in the Exposure area where it is co-occurring with the Ecosystem Component. Note that in the calculations the scores are expressed as fractions (0-1) but for presentation purposes we have expressed them as percentages (0-100%).

Magnitude	Score	Interpretation
Very low (VL)	0.1	Traces of the pressure with no adverse effects. Not different from pristine.
Low (L)	1	Adverse effects expected but $\leq 1\%$ of maximum
Medium (M)	10	Adverse effects $\geq 1\%$ but $\leq 10\%$ of maximum
High (H)	50	Adverse effects $\geq 10\%$ but $\leq 50\%$ of maximum
Maximum (VH)	100	Causing highest adverse effects known for that pressure

Figure SM1.4. Schematic explaining how different behavioral responses determine the likelihood of interaction score.

Table SM1.5. Resistance of a receptor to a stressor, interpreted as what remains of that receptor after 1 year exposure to that stressor, calculated for two interaction mechanisms depending on various parameters. For Continuous interactions these are only Hazard and Magnitude, for Intermittent interactions this is also Behaviour (to the extent that it affects the likelihood of interaction) and Frequency. Frequency represents how often a stressor and receptor interact and can be any number, but here we have only presented three values, i.e. 0.1 (once every 10 years), 1 and 10 interaction events per year. Note that in the calculations the parameter values are expressed as fractions (0-1) but for presentation purposes we have expressed them as percentages (0-100%).

Hazard	Magnitude		Continuous	Intermittent												Behaviour	
				0.5	0.5	0.5	5	5	5	50	50	50	100	100	100		
				0.1	1	10	0.1	1	10	0.1	1	10	0.1	1	10		
															Frequency		
Negligible	0.01	Very low	0.1	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	
	0.01	Low	1	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	
	0.01	Medium	10	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.99	
	0.01	High	50	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.98	100.00	100.00	99.95	
	0.01	Maximum	100	99.99	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	100.00	99.99	99.90	
Sublethal low	0.1	Very low	0.1	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	
	0.1	Low	1	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.99	
	0.1	Medium	10	99.99	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	100.00	99.99	99.90	
	0.1	High	50	99.95	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.98	100.00	99.98	99.75	99.99	99.95	99.50	
	0.1	Maximum	100	99.90	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.99	99.90	99.00	
Sublethal high	1	Very low	0.1	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.99	
	1	Low	1	99.99	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	100.00	99.99	99.90	
	1	Medium	10	99.90	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.99	99.90	99.90	99.00	
	1	High	50	99.50	100.00	100.00	99.98	100.00	99.98	99.75	99.97	99.75	97.53	99.95	99.50	95.11	
	1	Maximum	100	99.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.95	99.50	95.11	99.90	99.00	90.44	
Lethal low	10	Very low	0.1	99.99	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	100.00	99.99	99.90	
	10	Low	1	99.90	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.99	99.90	99.90	99.00	
	10	Medium	10	99.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.95	99.50	95.11	99.90	99.00	90.44	
	10	High	50	95.00	100.00	99.98	99.75	99.97	99.75	97.53	99.75	97.50	77.63	99.49	95.00	59.87	
	10	Maximum	100	90.00	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.95	99.50	95.11	99.49	95.00	59.87	98.95	90.00	34.87	
Lethal high	100	Very low	0.1	99.90	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.99	99.90	99.90	99.00	
	100	Low	1	99.00	100.00	100.00	99.95	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.95	99.50	95.11	99.90	99.00	90.44	
	100	Medium	10	90.00	99.99	99.95	99.50	99.95	99.50	95.11	99.49	95.00	59.88	98.95	90.00	34.87	
	100	High	50	50.01	99.97	99.75	97.53	99.75	97.50	77.63	97.16	75.00	5.63	93.30	50.01	0.10	
	100	Maximum	100	0.01	99.95	99.50	95.11	99.49	95.00	59.88	93.30	50.01	0.10	39.81	0.01	0.00	

Resilience

For resilience we adopted both the interpretation (i.e. time taken for the habitat to recover to pre-impact condition) and the expert judgement scores from Knights et al (2015).

SM1.6. Resilience estimates based on expert judgement (adopted from Knights et al., 2015).

Ecosystem component	Recovery	Time (yr) to Recovery
Littoral rock and other hard substrata	High	1
Littoral sediment		1
Pelagic water column		1
Circalittoral rock and other hard substrata	Moderate	6
Infralittoral rock and other hard substrata		6
Sublittoral sediment		6
Birds	Low	55
Deep-sea bed		55
Fish & Cephalopods		55
Mammals		55
Reptiles		55
	None	100

SM2: Calculation Effect Potential

For the calculation of the Resistance the standard formula of Pitcher et al. (2017) estimates what remains of an ecosystem component relative to an undisturbed situation represented as the carrying capacity (K). This is formulated as:

$$Resistance = \frac{R}{K} = (1 - H * M * B)^F$$

Where

R = Receptor abundance (biomass or density) at the end of a single assessment period

K = Abundance of receptor in an undisturbed situation (=Carrying capacity)

H = Hazard as the relative depletion of the receptor from a single interaction with the stressor at maximum magnitude

M = Magnitude of the stressor in the area of exposure relative to its maximum (i.e. highest possible)

B = Behavioural response of the receptor in relation to the stressor that determines the likelihood of interaction

F = Frequency of interaction (number of interaction events in the assessment period).

In case of a continuous interaction mechanism the behavioural component can be ignored and there is only one (albeit continuous) interaction event (thus *B*=1 and *F*=1). The only exception is the vertical extent in case the stressor does not cover the full vertical extent of the receptor.

Because EP is expressed as the relative depletion (compared to undisturbed) of the receptor *R* in case of exposure, it can be estimated using population dynamics. To that end semi-chemostat dynamics were assumed to model the abundance of the receptor *R* per spatial unit in relation to carrying capacity *K* and based on a recovery rate *r_r* and a depletion rate *r_d* according to:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = r_r * (K - R) - r_d * R$$

By setting this to equilibrium (*dR/dt*=0) and rearranging, the abundance of the ecosystem component *R_{eq}* can be calculated assuming that specific pressure continues at that specific magnitude *ad infinitum*:

$$R_{eq} = \frac{r_r * K}{r_r + r_d}$$

Solving the differential equation above then gives:

$$R(t) = R_{eq} + (R_0 - R_{eq}) e^{-(r_r+r_d)t}$$

Where *R₀* is the abundance at the start of the assessment period and thus prior to the interaction with the stressor. From the estimated *Resistance* during the assessment period, i.e. what remains of the receptor *R* at *t*=1, thus *Resistance*=*R*(1), and assuming no recovery (*r_r*=0) the depletion rate (*r_d*) can then be calculated as:

$$r_d = \ln\left(\frac{1}{Resistance}\right)$$

The estimated *Resilience* was interpreted as the time required to increase the abundance of the ecosystem component from a “sustainably exploited abundance” *R₀* to a “fully recovered abundance” *R_t* in case there is no stressor and *r_d*=0. The recovery rate *r_r* can then be calculated as:

$$r_r = \frac{1}{Resilience} \ln\left(\frac{R_0 - K}{R_t - K}\right)$$

This was further simplified assuming:

- $R_0=0.5K$ (i.e. half of undisturbed) based on the rule that the abundance of a sustainably exploited stock is about half of its undisturbed abundance, something known to apply at least for fish (Tsikliras and Froese, 2019)
- $R_r=0.99K$ because (near) full recovery was achieved at 99% of an undisturbed abundance.

The calculation of the recovery rate can then be simplified into:

$$r_r = \frac{\ln(50)}{\text{Resilience}}$$

For each specific impact chain (i.e. human activity-pressure-ecosystem component) the EP as the relative decrease in equilibrium abundance of that ecosystem component from an undisturbed situation can be calculated as:

$$EP = \frac{(K - R_{eq})}{K} = \left(1 - \frac{r_r}{r_r + r_d}\right) = \frac{r_d}{r_r + r_d}$$

SM3: Aggregation cumulative pressures into an assessment of Impact Risk

The SCAIRM output is basically an aggregation of Impact Risk (IR) across impact chains and thus cumulative pressures. For each specific pressure (P) the sectoral activities (A) and their operations (O) can be considered additive. In contrast aggregation across pressures to estimate IR is calculated as an independent chance following (Reed and Rye, 2011):

$$IR_{EC,P} = \sum_1^A IR_{EC,P,A}$$

$$IR_{EC} = 1 - \prod_1^P (1 - IR_{EC,P})$$

$$IR_{Ecosystem} = \frac{\sum_1^{EC} IR_{EC}}{EC}$$

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Appendix 2 Ecosystem services, functions and processes

Main findings / conclusions

The main findings based on studies in the field of ecosystem services (ES) are listed below.

- The Common International Classification for Ecosystem Services (CICES) is an important frame of reference for ES research.
- CICES and most ES literature are based on and influenced by the cascade framework (Figure 1) proposed by Haines-Young & Potschin (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2010; Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011, 2016). The purpose of the cascade framework is in fact to show the pathway of ES from ecological structures and processes to human well-being (La Notte et al., 2017).
- The cascade framework can be applied in order to link the (change in) status of ecosystem components to the supply of ES by identifying (and quantifying) the underlying structures and processes that contribute to the ecosystem. This framework has already been used within e.g. ODEMM.
- Within the cascade framework, it is important to distinguish functions from processes (also conform ODEMM). The concept of functions not only describes the combinations of structure and processes (i.e. activity involving energy and matter transformation), but at the same time represent the potential that ecosystems have to deliver a service (De Groot et al., 2010; Braat and de Groot, 2012). Within the field of ES, ecosystem functions are considered a subset of processes (De Groot et al., 2002) and can be defined as:
 - the capacity of natural processes and components to provide goods and services that satisfy human needs, directly or indirectly (De Groot et al., 2002)
 - the subset of the interactions between biophysical structures, biodiversity and ecosystem processes that underpin the capacity of an ecosystem to provide ecosystem services (Potschin and Haines-Young, 2016)
- However, although the 'original' approach (CICES) distinguishes between 1) ecosystem structure & processes and 2) ecological functions (see above), more recently abiotic ecosystem outputs were added to the cascade (CICES V5.1). This assumes a direct link between ecosystem structure & processes and ES, without the intervention of ecological functions.
- To avoid confusion when using the cascade, von Thenen et al. (2020) used a version in which these 2 steps ("structure & processes" and "functions") fall into 1 category, i.e. the "ecosystem capacity". The capacity, or the potential of the ecosystem to provide both biotic and abiotic ecosystem output, is defined as: "the interaction of species, structures, substrates, conditions and processes that determine the provision of ES" (von Thenen et al. 2020).
- This approach can be adopted and thereby all ecosystem structures, ecosystem processes and ecological functions together is considered as the ecosystem capacity.

Background information based on a brief literature review

Ecosystem services classification systems

The Common International Classification for Ecosystem Services (CICES), proposed by the European Environment Agency, has become an important frame of reference for ecosystem services research (Maes et al., 2014 in La Notte et al., 2017). CICES and most ecosystem services literature are based on and influenced by the cascade framework (Figure 15) proposed by Haines-Young & Potschin (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2010; Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011, 2016). The purpose of the cascade framework is in fact to show the pathway of ecosystem services from ecological structures and processes to human well-being (La Notte et al., 2017). La Notte et al. (2017) identified two main

challenges with current ecosystem services classification systems: i) the inconsistency across concepts, terminology and definitions, and; ii) the mix up of processes and end-state benefits, or flows and assets.

Prior to the cascade framework (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2010; Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011, 2016), De Groot et al. (2002) provided a systematic typology and comprehensive framework for integrated assessment and valuation of ecosystem functions, of which the main elements are presented in *Figure 14*. The first step towards a comprehensive assessment of ecosystem goods and services involves the translation of ecological complexity (structures and processes) into a more limited number of ecosystem functions. These functions, in turn, provide the goods and services that are valued by humans (De Groot et al., 2002). De Groot et al. (2002) explicitly define ecosystem functions as ‘the capacity of natural processes and components to provide goods and services that satisfy human needs, directly or indirectly’ (De Groot, 1992). They mention that by using this definition, ecosystem functions are best conceived as a subset of ecological processes and ecosystem structures (see *Figure 14*). Each function is the result of the natural processes of the total ecological sub-system of which it is a part. Natural processes, in turn, are the result of complex interactions between biotic (living organisms) and abiotic (chemical and physical) components of ecosystems through the universal driving forces of matter and energy (De Groot et al., 2002).

*) The problem of aggregation and weighing of different values in the decision making process is an important issue, but is not the subject of this paper (see other papers in this issue for further discussion)

Figure 14 Framework for integrated assessment and valuation of ecosystem functions, goods and services (De Groot et al., 2002).

Table 5 Functions, goods and services of natural and semi-natural ecosystems (De Groot et al., 2002)

Functions	Ecosystem processes and components	Goods and services (examples)
<i>Regulation Functions</i>		
<i>Maintenance of essential ecological processes and life support systems</i>		
1 Gas regulation	Role of ecosystems in bio-geochemical cycles (e.g. CO ₂ /O ₂ balance, ozone layer, etc.)	1.1 UVb-protection by O ₃ (preventing disease). 1.2 Maintenance of (good) air quality. 1.3 Influence on climate (see also function 2.)
2 Climate regulation	Influence of land cover and biol. mediated processes (e.g. DMS-production) on climate	Maintenance of a favorable climate (temp., precipitation, etc) for, for example, human habitation, health, cultivation
3 Disturbance prevention	Influence of ecosystem structure on dampening env. disturbances	3.1 Storm protection (e.g. by coral reefs). 3.2 Flood prevention (e.g. by wetlands and forests)
4 Water regulation	Role of land cover in regulating runoff & river discharge	4.1 Drainage and natural irrigation. 4.2 Medium for transport
5 Water supply	Filtering, retention and storage of fresh water (e.g. in aquifers)	Provision of water for consumptive use (e.g. drinking, irrigation and industrial use)
6 Soil retention	Role of vegetation root matrix and soil biota in soil retention	6.1 Maintenance of arable land. 6.2 Prevention of damage from erosion/siltation
7 Soil formation	Weathering of rock, accumulation of organic matter	7.1 Maintenance of productivity on arable land. 7.2 Maintenance of natural productive soils
8 Nutrient regulation	Role of biota in storage and re-cycling of nutrients (eg. N,P&S)	Maintenance of healthy soils and productive ecosystems
9 Waste treatment	Role of vegetation & biota in removal or breakdown of xenic nutrients and compounds	9.1 Pollution control/detoxification. 9.2 Filtering of dust particles. 9.3 Abatement of noise pollution
10 Pollination	Role of biota in movement of floral gametes	10.1 Pollination of wild plant species. 10.2 Pollination of crops
11 Biological control	Population control through trophic-dynamic relations	11.1 Control of pests and diseases. 11.2 Reduction of herbivory (crop damage)
<i>Habitat Functions</i>		
<i>Providing habitat (suitable living space) for wild plant and animal species</i>		
12 Refugium function	Suitable living space for wild plants and animals	Maintenance of commercially harvested species
13 Nursery function	Suitable reproduction habitat	13.1 Hunting, gathering of fish, game, fruits, etc. 13.2 Small-scale subsistence farming & aquaculture
<i>Production Functions</i>		
<i>Provision of natural resources</i>		
14 Food	Conversion of solar energy into edible plants and animals	14.1 Building & Manufacturing (e.g. lumber, skins). 14.2 Fuel and energy (e.g. fuel wood, organic matter). 14.3 Fodder and fertilizer (e.g. krill, leaves, litter)
15 Raw materials	Conversion of solar energy into biomass for human construction and other uses	15.1 Improve crop resistance to pathogens & pests. 15.2 Other applications (e.g. health care)
16 Genetic resources	Genetic material and evolution in wild plants and animals	16.1 Drugs and pharmaceuticals. 16.2 Chemical models & tools. 16.3 Test- and essay organisms
17 Medicinal resources	Variety in (bio)chemical substances in, and other medicinal uses of, natural biota	Resources for fashion, handicraft, jewelry, pets, worship, decoration & souvenirs (e.g. furs, feathers, ivory, orchids, butterflies, aquarium fish, shells, etc.)

	Functions	Ecosystem processes and components	Goods and services (examples)
18	Ornamental resources	Variety of biota in natural ecosystems with (potential) ornamental use	
	<i>Information Functions</i>	<i>Providing opportunities for cognitive development</i>	
19	Aesthetic information	Attractive landscape features	Enjoyment of scenery (scenic roads, housing, etc.)
20	Recreation	Variety in landscapes with (potential) recreational uses	Travel to natural ecosystems for eco-tourism, outdoor sports, etc.
21	Cultural and artistic information	Variety in natural features with cultural and artistic value	Use of nature as motive in books, film, painting, folklore, national symbols, architect., advertising, etc.
22	Spiritual and historic information	Variety in natural features with spiritual and historic value	Use of nature for religious or historic purposes (i.e. heritage value of natural ecosystems and features)
23	Science and education	Variety in nature with scientific and educational value	Use of natural systems for school excursions, etc. Use of nature for scientific research

In TEEB, ecosystem services are defined as “the direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to human well-being” (De Groot et al., 2010). The typology of ecosystem services in TEEB is shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Typology of ecosystem services in TEEB (De Groot et al., 2010).

	Main service types
	PROVISIONING SERVICES
1	Food (e.g. fish, game, fruit)
2	Water (e.g. for drinking, irrigation, cooling)
3	Raw Materials (e.g. fiber, timber, fuel wood, fodder, fertilizer)
4	Genetic resources (e.g. for crop-improvement and medicinal purposes)
5	Medicinal resources (e.g. biochemical products, models & test-organisms)
6	Ornamental resources (e.g. artisan work, decorative plants, pet animals, fashion)
	REGULATING SERVICES
7	Air quality regulation (e.g. capturing (fine)dust, chemicals, etc)
8	Climate regulation (incl. C-sequestration, influence of vegetation on rainfall, etc.)
9	Moderation of extreme events (eg. storm protection and flood prevention)
10	Regulation of water flows (e.g. natural drainage, irrigation and drought prevention)
11	Waste treatment (especially water purification)
12	Erosion prevention
13	Maintenance of soil fertility (incl. soil formation)
14	Pollination
15	Biological control (e.g. seed dispersal, pest and disease control)
	HABITAT SERVICES
16	Maintenance of life cycles of migratory species (incl. nursery service)
17	Maintenance of genetic diversity (especially in gene pool protection)
	CULTURAL & AMENITY SERVICES
18	Aesthetic information
19	Opportunities for recreation & tourism
20	Inspiration for culture, art and design
21	Spiritual experience
22	Information for cognitive development

The concept of functions within ecosystem services

Braat and de Groot (2012) elaborate on the use of ecosystem functioning within the ecosystem services context. They mention the following: *“The term ecosystem function was originally used to refer to the set of ecosystem processes operating within an ecological system irrespective of whether or not such processes are useful for humans (Odum, 1956). In the late 1960s and early 1970s, some authors started referring to “functions of nature” to denote the work done, space provided, and goods delivered to human societies (Helliwell, 1969; Hueting, 1970; Odum, 1971; Braat et al., 1979). This did cause some confusion as the term functions was still in use in a strictly ecological sense....”*

The concept of functions not only describes the combinations of structure and processes (i.e. activity involving energy and matter transformation), but at the same time represent the potential that ecosystems have to deliver a service (De Groot et al., 2010; Braat and de Groot, 2012). This concept is visualized in Figure 16, which is based on the cascade framework of Haines-Young & Potschin (Figure 15). It is thus important to distinguish ecosystem functions from processes because a lot of activity involving energy and matter transformations takes place in ecosystems (captured in the two ecological boxes in Figure 16) before services are provided and benefits are generated. Braat and de Groot (2012) provide some examples: *“For example primary production (=process) is needed to maintain a viable, reproducing fish population (=function) which can regenerate fish stocks after part of the population is harvested (=provisioning service) to provide food (a “good”); nutrient cycling (=process) is needed for water purification (=function) to provide clean water (=provisioning service). The benefits of the resulting services are manifold. For example, food provides nutrition but also pleasure and sometimes even social identity (as part of cultural traditions); clean water can be used for drinking but also for swimming (pleasure) and other activities aimed at satisfying needs and wants. Thus, the role of woodlands in slowing the passage of water through a catchment is a function which has the potential of delivering a service (water flow regulation which reduces flood risk) if some beneficiary exists to enjoy the benefit (safety). Services are therefore actually conceptualizations (‘labels’) of the “useful things” ecosystems “do” for people, directly and indirectly. It should be realized though that properties of ecological systems that people regard as ‘useful’ may change over time even if the ecological system itself remains in a relatively constant state.”*

Figure 15 The relationship between biodiversity, ecosystem function and human well-being (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2010).

Figure 16 The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) overview diagram. (De Groot et al., 2010), adapted from Haines-Young and Potschin (2009).

The concept of capacity within ecosystem services

Capacity can describe the ecosystem’s potential for delivering both biotic ES and abiotic ecosystem outputs. Von Thenen et al. (2020) define ecosystem capacity as the interaction of species, structures, substrates, conditions and processes that determine the provision of ES. Von Thenen et al. (2020) on the use of capacity and the cascade steps: ...“The original cascade distinguishes between ecosystem structures and processes and ecological functions as the foundation of ES. However, here we adopt the version where these two steps are placed in one category called the “ecosystem capacity” to provide a service (Baro et al., 2016; Liqueste et al., 2013; Potschin-Young et al., 2018). The inclusion of abiotic ecosystem outputs (CICES V5.1) implies a direct link between ecosystem structures and processes, and ES, and thus the exclusion of ecological functions. To avoid using different cascade steps for CICES and CICES extended (abiotic part), we used ecosystem capacity in this study. Capacity can describe the ecosystem’s potential for delivering both biotic ES and abiotic ecosystem outputs.”... (von Thenen et al., 2020).

Vargas et al. (2019) elaborate on capacity within ES: ...“A key innovation in ecosystem accounting is the inclusion and guidance on the spatially explicitly measurement of stocks by assessing changes ecosystems in terms of extent, condition and capacity to supply ecosystem services, and the measurement of flows of ecosystem services (United Nations et al. 2014). Whereas extent reflects changes in ecosystem’s size and location, condition reflects changes in its quality, and capacity reflect changes in the ability of an ecosystem to generate ecosystem services as a function of changes in extent and condition. In practical terms, two aspects can be distinguished from the occurrence of an ecosystem service; capacity and flow, where capacity is the long term ecosystem’s potential to sustainably generate an ecosystem service, and flow is the actual use of the service (Schröter et al. 2014). A clear distinction between capacity and flow is important because the generation of some ecosystem services involves harvest-regeneration patterns and for some ecosystem the generation of ecosystem services can be above its capacity. This is important to assess the overall sustainability of the human activities in such ecosystem. The concept of capacity can be used to assess a sustainable use of ecosystems, as capacity reflects the ability of an ecosystem to sustainably supply a service under current ecosystem condition and uses at the highest yield or use level (Hein et al. 2016; United Nations et al. 2017). Here, the supply of ecosystem services is sustainable when the supply of an

ecosystem service does not negatively affect the future supply of the same or other ecosystem services from that ecosystem. Current ecosystem condition means that the capacity is defined as it is now, neglecting alternative uses and independently from normative and historical baseline reference conditions (Hein et al. 2016). Therefore, by quantifying the capacity of an ecosystem to supply ecosystem services, the maximum amount of ecosystem services that can be supplied in a sustainable way is defined.”.... (Vargas et al., 2019).

...”In principle, provided the estimates are of sufficient accuracy, flows exceeding capacity indicate unsustainable use.”.....(Vargas et al., 2019).

Balzan et al. (2018) describe the following on ES capacity:”The distinction between ES capacity and flow builds on the definition of ecosystem services, which considers these as the contributions that ecosystems make to human well-being. The ES Cascade model develops on this definition and links ecosystems to the human society through a chain of components, namely ecosystem structure and processes, functions, services, benefits and values (Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011). Different indicators have been used to assess and map these different components of the cascade model. In particular, several have distinguished between the ecosystems’ capacity and the flow of ES (Fig. 1). The ES capacity is here defined as the potential of ecosystems to provide services, while ES flow refers to the actual production of the ES (Villamagna et al., 2013). Based on this definition, ES flow differs from ES demand since the flow measurements focus on the contribution of ecosystems to human well-being whilst the ES demand is the expression of the beneficiaries’ preferences for specific ES attributes, such as biophysical characteristics, location and timing of availability, and associated opportunity costs of use. Hence, the ES demand may be larger than the ES flow (Schröter et al., 2014). We further developed this approach to analyse how ES capacity and ES flows vary spatially (Fig. 1), and hence allowing for the identification of different spatial patterns of these two components, which can lead to unsustainable ES uptake.”(Balzan et al., 2018).

Fig. 1. General conceptual diagram linking ecosystems’ capacity and the flow of ES to human wellbeing. Block arrows indicate the relationship between the ecosystem, ecosystem services and socioeconomic systems, while dashed arrows indicate the level of analysis in this study through the identification of interactions, overlap and synergies and trade-offs in ES delivery (Balzan et al., 2018).

Examples of ES studies in the marine environment

The cascade framework of Haines-Young & Potschin (2010) has been followed by many others, for example within the ODEMM project (Böhnke-Henrichs et al., 2013) and a more recent study describing what ecosystem services are provided by the marine environment (Hattam et al., 2015), see Figure 17 and Figure 18, respectively.

Figure 17 Linking ecosystem structure and processes to human well-being applying the example of the service Disturbance Prevention or Moderation in the marine environment (Böhnke-Henrichs et al., 2013) (adapted from De Groot et al. (2010), based on Haines-Young and Potschin 2010).

Figure 18 Ecosystem service production functions cascade for the socio-ecological system of a marine ecosystem (Martinetto et al., 2020).

Armoškaitė et al. (2020) developed an assessment tool to quantitatively describe the contribution of marine habitats and species in the supply of ES and to improve the way complex interrelations are communicated to MSP practitioners (Figure 19).

Figure 19 Linkage diagram depicting the relative importance of species (left-hand side) in the supply of ecosystem services (right-hand side). Contribution of species is quantitatively described as parts of a whole, where the whole is the sum of all ecosystem services (100%). Width of connecting lines reflects strength of links, while weight of bars conveys the importance of elements in the system (Armoškaitė et al., 2020).

The study of Hattam et al. (2015) aims to describe what ecosystem services are provided by the marine environment and to find a classification that is sufficiently generic to be applicable to different marine sites, while being sufficiently flexible to ensure site differences can be explored in detail. They also describe what indicators can be developed for all the ecosystem services identified, for the ecosystem functions that deliver them and the ecosystem benefits they generate. Results of their study is provided in Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7 Proposed classification of marine ecosystem services, their description and relevance to the Dogger Bank. (Hattam et al., 2015) Modified from de Groot et al. (2010) and Böhnke-Henrichs et al. (2013).

Ecosystem service		Description	Relevance to the Dogger Bank
Provisioning services			
1	Food provision:		
	a) Wild capture sea food	All available marine flora and fauna extracted from unmanaged marine environments for consumption by humans	✓, extensive fishing (trawling)
	b) Farmed sea food	Food from aquaculture for consumption by humans	X, no aquaculture in the area
2	Biotic raw materials (non-food):		
	a) Genetic resources	The provision/extraction of genetic material from marine flora and fauna for use in non-medicinal contexts	?, unknown
	b) Medicinal resources	Any material that is extracted from or used in the marine environment for its ability to provide medicinal benefits	?, unknown
	c) Ornamental resources	Any material that is extracted for use in decoration, fashion, handicrafts, souvenirs, etc.	✓, growing market for mammoth and other Mesolithic remains
	d) Other biotic raw materials	Extraction of all other renewable biotic resources	✓, harvesting of sandeels for animal feed and fertilisers
Regulating services			
3	Air purification	Influence of a marine ecosystem on concentration of pollutants from the atmosphere	✓, extent unknown
4	Climate regulation	The contribution of a marine ecosystem to the maintenance of a favorable climate through impacts on the hydrological cycle, temperature regulation, and the contribution to climate-influencing substances in the atmosphere	✓, extent unknown
5	Disturbance prevention or moderation	The contribution of marine ecosystem structures and functions to the dampening of the intensity of environmental disturbances such as storm floods, tsunamis, and hurricanes	X, area too far from the coast
6	Regulation of water flows	The contribution of marine ecosystems to the maintenance of localized coastal current structures	?, unknown
7	Waste treatment and assimilation	The removal of contaminant and organic nutrient inputs to marine environments from humans	✓, extent unknown
8	Coastal erosion prevention	The contribution of marine ecosystems to coastal erosion prevention	X, area too far from the coast
9	Biological control	The contribution of marine ecosystems to the maintenance of population dynamics, resilience through food web dynamics, disease and pest control	✓, extent unknown
Habitat services			
10	Migratory and nursery habitat	The contribution of a particular marine habitat to migratory and resident species' populations through the provision of critical habitat for feeding, or reproduction and juvenile maturation	✓, extent unknown
11	Gene pool protection	The contribution of marine habitats to the maintenance of viable gene pools through natural selection/evolutionary processes which enhances adaptability of species to environmental changes, and the resilience of the ecosystem	✓, extent unknown
Cultural services			

Ecosystem service		Description	Relevance to the Dogger Bank
12	Leisure, recreation and tourism	The provision of opportunities for tourism, recreation and leisure that depend on a particular state of marine ecosystems	✓, limited to some sailing, diving and recreational angling
13	Aesthetic experience	The contribution that a marine ecosystem makes to the existence of a surface or subsurface landscape that generates a noticeable emotional response within the individual observer. This includes informal spiritual individual experiences but excludes that covered by service 17	✓, limited to those who go there
14	Inspiration for culture, art and design	The contribution that a marine ecosystem makes to the existence of environmental features that inspire elements of culture, art, and/or design. This excludes that covered by services 2c, 13, and 16	✓, extent unknown
15	Cultural heritage	The contribution of marine ecosystems to the maintenance of cultural heritage, and providing a 'sense of place'	✓, extent unknown but links to Palaeolithic man
16	Cultural diversity	The contribution of marine ecosystems to social and cultural values and adaptations that pertain to living at coasts and exploiting marine resources	✓, extent unknown
17	Spiritual experience	The contribution that a marine ecosystem makes to formal and informal collective religious experiences. This excludes that covered by services 13 and 14	✓, extent unknown
18	Information for cognitive development	The contribution that a marine ecosystem makes to education, research, and individual and collective cognitive development	✓, extent unknown

✓ : relevant, X: not relevant,?: relevance unknown.

Table 8 Indicators for each of the ecosystem services identified in Table 7 as relevant to the Dogger Bank (Hattam et al., 2015).

Ecosystem services	Generic marine ecosystem service indicators	Measurement (units)- measured over time	Dogger Bank specific indicators	Issues related to assessment criteria
1a: Food provision – wild capture sea food	Fish and shellfish populations, seaweed stock	Biomass (tonnes km ⁻²) or abundance (no. km ⁻²) of fish and shellfish; area (m ²) or biomass (tonnes km ⁻²) of seaweed	Population of nephrops and flatfish species such as plaice, turbot and lemon sole	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Quality of the fish, shellfish, seaweed stock	Species composition, age profile; length profile; percentage affected by disease; mortality rates	Quality of the populations of nephrops and flatfish species such as plaice, turbot and lemon sole	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
1b: Food provision – farmed sea food	Fish and shellfish populations, seaweed stock	Biomass (tonnes km ⁻²) or abundance (no. km ⁻²) of fish and shellfish; area (km ²) or biomass (tonnes km ⁻²) of seaweed	N/A	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Quality of the fish, shellfish, seaweed stock	Percentage affected by disease; mortality rates	N/A	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
2a: Biotic raw material – genetic resources	Presence and diversity of species with potential/actual useful genetic material	Presence/absence of desirable species; diversity of desirable species	Insufficient information to define indicators	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Quality of species with potential/actual useful genetic material	Endemism and uniqueness of species	Insufficient information to define indicators	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts

Ecosystem services	Generic marine ecosystem service indicators	Measurement (units)- measured over time	Dogger Bank specific indicators	Issues related to assessment criteria
2b: Biotic raw material – medicinal resources	Quantity of available raw material	Total quantity available in a fixed area (g/raw material)	Insufficient information to define indicators	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Quality of raw materials	Concentration of raw material (g l ⁻¹ seawater, g m ⁻³ sediment)	Insufficient information to define indicators	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
2c: Biotic raw material – ornamental resources	Quantity of raw material	Biomass available in a fixed area (tonnes km ⁻²)	Insufficient information to define indicators	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Quality of raw materials	Concentration (g l ⁻¹ seawater, tonnes km ⁻² sediment); purity	Insufficient information to define indicators	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
2d: Other biotic raw material	Quantity of raw material	Biomass available in a fixed area (tonnes km ⁻²)	Population of sandeels (same measurement units as for food provision)	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Quality of raw materials	Concentration (g l ⁻¹ seawater, tonnes km ⁻² sediment); purity	Quality of the populations of sandeels (same measurement units as for food provision)	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
3: Air purification	Air–sea flux of pollutants	Modeled or empirically determined pollutant air–sea flux rates and direction (μmol pollutant d ⁻¹ m ⁻² , μg pollutant l ⁻¹ seawater d ⁻¹ m ⁻²)	Insufficient information to define indicators	Role of different components of the marine ecosystem involved in this service is unclear. Lack of knowledge prevents indicator identification
	Distribution of air–sea fluxes of pollutants	Modeled or empirically determined maps of pollutant concentrations (μmol l ⁻¹ m ⁻² d ⁻¹ , μg air pollutant l ⁻¹ seawater m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	Insufficient information to define indicators	
4: Climate regulation	Air–sea and sediment–water fluxes of carbon and CO ₂	Modeled or empirically determined (mg C m ⁻² d ⁻¹ , mg CO ₂ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
	Air–sea fluxes of other greenhouse gases (e.g., dimethyl sulfide, methane, nitrous oxide)	Modeled or empirically determined (μg greenhouse gases m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
	Levels of carbon in different components of the marine ecosystem	Modeled or empirically determined carbon levels: biomass of carbon (g m ⁻²); dissolved organic or inorganic carbon (mg C m ⁻³); suspended organic or inorganic carbon (mg C m ⁻³); buried particulate organic or inorganic carbon (mg C m ⁻²)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
	Permanence of carbon sequestration	Percentage of annual carbon turnover from sediments	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
5: Disturbance prevention and moderation	Capacity of water storage of habitat	Water storage capacity (m ³ /area) for different intertidal habitats (e.g., sediment, saltmarsh, mangrove)	N/A	

Ecosystem services	Generic marine ecosystem service indicators	Measurement (units)- measured over time	Dogger Bank specific indicators	Issues related to assessment criteria
	Reduction of wave energy by near shore and intertidal habitats	Change in wave energy ($J m^{-2}$) attributed to different intertidal and near shore habitats	N/A	
	Changing shoreline	Change in beach profile (slope (gradient) and width (m) and stability) over time determined empirically from photos, satellite, LiDAR, ARGUS camera and modeled	N/A	
6: Regulation of water flows	Salinity/freshwater input	Change in salinity, tidal and freshwater flow rates ($m^3 s^{-1}$)	Insufficient information to define indicators	
	Changing shoreline	Change in beach profile (slope (gradient) and width (m) and stability) over time determined empirically from photos, satellite, LiDAR, ARGUS camera and modelled	N/A	
	Rates of tidal and wind driven currents	Direct measures of flow and currents ($m^3 s^{-1}$) and turbidity ($mg m^{-3}$ or NTU)	Insufficient information to define indicators	
	Seabed morphology	Changes in seabed morphology using side-scan sonar	Insufficient information to define indicators	
7: Waste treatment and assimilation	Absolute levels of waste in the water column	Chemical analysis (contaminant concentrations) and visual analysis	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	Difficult to attribute to specific elements of the ecosystem structure and processes as knowledge is not available
	Presence of pathogens; outbreaks of <i>E. coli</i> infections; hospital admissions	Total coliforms or other pathogens (quantity per milliliter of water)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	Difficult to attribute to specific elements of the ecosystem structure and processes as knowledge is not available
	Benthic biodiversity levels/ratios/no. of sensitive species	Different biodiversity indices	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	Indicates health of system which may indicate capacity for waste assimilation if waste inputs are known
	Toxicity levels within species	Chemical analysis (contaminant concentrations)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
	Number of shellfish area closures		N/A	May not necessarily reflect change in ecosystem service; for example it could reflect changing risk appetite of consumers, producers or regulators
	Harmful algal bloom outbreaks	Remote sensing, water sampling to detect frequency and extent; modeling to determine future frequency and extent	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
8: Coastal erosion prevention	Beach profile (slope and width); extent of maintenance and improvement required to provide protection	Change in beach profile (slope (gradient) and width (m) and stability) over time determined empirically from photos, satellite, LiDAR, ARGUS camera and modelled	N/A	Extent of maintenance/improvement required may not necessarily reflect change in ecosystem service; for example it could reflect

Ecosystem services	Generic marine ecosystem service indicators	Measurement (units)- measured over time	Dogger Bank specific indicators	Issues related to assessment criteria
				changing levels of risk aversion by consumers, producers or regulators
	Presence and elevation of biogenic habitat e.g., saltmarsh beds; seagrass beds; bivalve, coral and polychaete reefs	Volume (m ³ or km ³), or area covered (m ² or km ²), density (biomass or abundance m ⁻²) and elevation of (height above mean seawater level)	N/A	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Presence of mitten crab	Presence of mitten crab (no. per unit area – could be estimated as number of burrows)	N/A	
9: Biological control (checks and balances)	Presence/absence/frequency of pests (e.g., algae blooms, foam, sea lice on farmed salmon)	Count data	As per generic indicators specifically applied to control of pests and HABs that affect fish species utilised by fisheries, mammals, seabirds and other marine organisms occurring in area	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
10: Migratory and nursery habitat	Area of habitat or density of biogenic habitat creating species “used” or identified as important for nursery or reproduction	For example, extent of seagrass, maerl or kelp beds (km ²)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Number and diversity of species using the area for nursery or reproduction	Abundance m ⁻² and species diversity	Spawning: abundance of cod, sandeels, plaice, nephrops; nursery: abundance of sprat, nephrops	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
	Dependence of off-site (commercial) populations	Proximity to dependant populations or their migration routes; size (abundance) and health (viability) of off-site populations	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
11: Gene pool protection	Genetic diversity	Diversity of species and sub-species, phylogenetic distance, Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	Specificity problematic: difficult to distinguish impacts of climate change from other impacts
12: Leisure, recreation and tourism	Sea space available for recreation	Number of km ² of sea with safe water quality available for recreational use	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	May not necessarily reflect change in ecosystem service; for example it could reflect changing levels of risk aversion of consumers, producers or regulators
	Number and quality of beaches	Number and size of blue flag beaches	N/A	May not necessarily reflect change in ecosystem service; for example it could reflect changing levels of risk aversion by consumers, producers or regulators
	Water quality	Chemical analysis (contaminant concentrations) and visual analysis; total coliforms or other pathogens (quantity per milliliter of water)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
	Abundance and diversity of key species of recreational interest	Count data	Species of recreational interest	

Ecosystem services	Generic marine ecosystem service indicators	Measurement (units)- measured over time	Dogger Bank specific indicators	Issues related to assessment criteria
			e.g., harbour porpoise, grey seal, seabirds, fish	
	Area of biotopes of key interest to recreational users	For example, extent of seagrass, maerl or kelp beds (km ²)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
13: Aesthetic experience	Uniqueness of a site	1/(number of sites with similar features)	Insufficient information to define indicators	Uniqueness would increase if all other similar ecosystems degrade
	Abundance of key species of individual interest	Count data	Species of individual interest e.g., harbour porpoise, grey seal, seabirds, fish	
	Area of biotopes of key interest to individuals	For example, extent of seagrass, maerl or kelp beds (km ²)	As per generic indicators scaled to the area covered by the Dogger Bank	
14: Inspiration for culture, art and design	Species, habitat or ecosystems that have or can potentially inspire any piece of artwork	Insufficient information to define indicators	Insufficient information to define indicators	Generic indicators cannot be developed
15: Cultural heritage	Species, habitats or ecosystems that can potentially form the core of contribute to a cultural custom, rite or way of life	Insufficient information to define indicators	Insufficient information to define indicators. Some links to Palaeolithic people	Generic indicators cannot be developed
16: Cultural diversity	Generic indicator cannot be developed	Insufficient information to define indicators	Insufficient information to define indicators	Generic indicators cannot be developed
17: Spiritual experience	Species, habitats or ecosystems that is being or can potentially be worshipped or be of significance to a religious belief	Insufficient information to define indicators	Insufficient information to define indicators	Generic indicators cannot be developed
18: Information for cognitive development	Species, habitats or ecosystems that are being or can potentially be studied to increase scientific knowledge	Number of such species, habitats, ecosystems	Insufficient information to define indicators	Generic indicators cannot be developed
	Species, habitats or ecosystems that are being or can potentially be studied for educational purposes	Number of such species, habitats, ecosystems	Insufficient information to define indicators	Generic indicators cannot be developed

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Appendix 3. Linking marine environmental status with the provision of ecosystem services and human benefits.

This is a summary of a paper submitted to *Ecosystem Services*, written in GES4SEAS by A. Olano, M.C., Uyarra, S. Pouso, and A., Borja (AZTI)

In this study, the cascade framework according to CICES v5.1 (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018) was applied to test if healthy oceans will supply more and better ecosystem services (ES) resulting in socio-economic benefits for humans. The study was divided in two parts: (i) The review and compilation of indicators for the different components of the cascade framework, and (ii) the application of the cascade framework and its indicators to the practical case study of the anchovy fishery in the Bay of Biscay.

1. Review and compilation of marine ecosystem service indicators for the cascade framework

First, a literature review was done to review and compile the indicators for the different components of the cascade framework, focusing on three marine ecosystem service examples: wild fish for nutrition (example of provisioning ES); carbon sequestration by marine environments (example of regulation ES); and recreational marine mammal watching (example of cultural ES). Indicators were classified in 6 types:

- Pressures: Relevant anthropogenic pressures (biological pressures, physical pressures, substances, litter, and energy), defined in the MSFD and coming from different human activities at sea or land based.
- Biophysical structure or process: General biotic or abiotic description of the habitat.
- Function: Characteristics of the living system that come together (processes) to make an ecosystem service possible.
- Service: Ecological outcomes that ecosystem characteristics or processes generate, that can ultimately benefit people.
- Benefit: Physical (products) or psychological benefits that humans get from ecosystem services.
- Value: Economic value of ecosystem services.

Indicators were reclassified to fit the definitions of the different steps of the cascade framework. In total, 415 indicators from 20 articles were extracted and classified: 187 indicators for wild fish for nutrition (provisioning ES), 141 indicators for carbon sequestration by marine environments (regulation ES) and 87 indicators for recreational marine mammal watching (cultural ES). Interestingly, some indicators were identified as having been incorrectly classified by the authors in the literature consulted (36%, 30%, and 37% of the provisioning, regulation, and cultural indicators, respectively). There was a markedly low number of service indicators (12 indicators in total) that contrasted with a high number of biophysical indicators and function indicators. The benefit and economic value indicators found were more numerous for provisioning service (39 benefit and 22 value indicators),

but low for regulating and cultural services, with less than 10 indicators for each. One of the main mistakes in the classification of indicators corresponded to functioning indicators, as many of them (33% for provisioning, 27% regulating and 59% cultural indicators) were classified as biophysical structure and processes indicators. Also, 27 indicators were incorrectly classified as service indicators. The main conclusion of this literature review of indicators was that it is necessary to develop a standardized classification and understanding of the marine ecosystem services. Several confusions exist according to the terminology and the different interpretations of the flow between the environment and the socio-economic system, making the study and management of ecosystem services more complicated.

2. Practical application of the cascade framework: anchovy in the Bay of Biscay

On the second part of the study, the cascade framework and indicators were applied to a practical case study, the anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) fishery in the Bay of Biscay, from 1987 to 2022. This example was considered optimal for the exercise because of the large dataset available, including data for each cascade step indicator, and because of the management adaptation to sustainable fisheries after a historical collapse of the species population in the Bay of Biscay and the fishery closure (Uriarte *et al.*, 2023). This example allowed to check if a non-healthy/healthy environment (before/after the collapse) provides more or less services and benefits, and the role that an adequate management can play in supplying services and obtaining benefits in a sustainable way.

Anchovy is one of the most important fisheries in the Bay of Biscay, both in terms of live weight and value of landings (STEF, 2019). After several years of recruitment failures under a constant and intensive capture regime, the fishery was closed between 2005 and 2009 (Vermard *et al.*, 2008). In response to the collapse, the EU created a long-term management strategy, including management actions, the adoption of a participatory fishery management approach, and changes in the surveys. Nowadays, the Total Allowable Catches (TACs) are set on a management calendar basis following the recruit survey (Uriarte *et al.* 2023).

Based on the reviewed indicators and also considering the available data for the Bay of Biscay, the indicators chosen to apply the cascade framework are included in Table 1.

Table 1: The indicators chosen to apply the cascade framework for the anchovy fishery in the Bay of Biscay.

Indicator type	Selected indicator	Description	Data and source
Pressures	<i>Harvest Rate</i>	The harvest rate is the ratio between landings and total stock abundance	Estimated from the stock assessment with SSB (Ibaibarriaga <i>et al.</i> , 2011).
	<i>Fleet</i>	Number of Spanish and French boats harvesting anchovy.	Data from 1987 and 2020 (ICES, 2021)
Biophysical structure or processes	<i>Upwelling index ($m^3 s^{-1} km^{-1}$).</i>	Upwelling, and the associated turbulence, have been identified in small pelagic fishes, including anchovy, as one of the biophysical processes that can explain the success in	Data from 1987 to 2022 (Ibaibarriaga <i>et al.</i> 2023).

		recruitment (Bakun and Parrish, 1982, Borja <i>et al.</i> , 1998).	
Function	<i>Recruitment at age 0 (t)</i> ³	The most determinant factor that regulates the anchovy population size. Recruitment is the process through which small, juvenile fish advance to an older, larger life stage (Camp <i>et al.</i> , 2020).	Anchovy recruitment 1987-2022 (ICES, 2022).
Service	<i>Spawning stock biomass (SSB) (t)</i>	SSB can be defined as the combined weight of all individuals in a fish stock (usually females only) that have reached sexual maturity and are capable of reproducing. The estimation of SSB is accomplished by applying the Daily Egg Production Method (DEPM) (Lasker, 1985),	SSB 1987-2022 (ICES, 2022).
Benefit	<i>Catch (t)</i>	The indicator for the benefit cascade component was the harvested fish, i.e. the total catch of anchovy landed, in tonnes.	Catches in 1987-2022 (ICES, 2022).
Value	<i>Economic value of catch (€)</i>	The indicator for the economic value of anchovy fisheries was the amount of euros per year, obtained by the fleets of first sale after landings.	(1) Spanish and French fleets as mean annual first sale value 1987-2022 (ICES, 2022). (2) Spanish fleet a mean price (€ kg ⁻¹) was calculated for the Bay of Biscay for the period 1990-2021 (Ministerio de Agricultura, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente of Spain ⁴

The relationship between the harvest rate (pressure 1), the recruitment (function) and SSB (service) was negative and statistically significant for the complete period (1987-2022). Indeed, 21% of the variance of recruitment could be explained by harvest rate and 55% in the case of SSB. Nevertheless, when exploring the pressure effect before and after the anchovy fishery collapse, the relationship was not significant ($p > 0.05$) for either the function or the service components.

Regarding to the relationship between fleet (pressure 2) and the same two cascade components, the relationship is negative and statistically significant for the whole period considered (1987-2020). However, the relationship was positive and significant for the period before collapse (1987-2004) and not significant for the period after collapse (2010-2020). Fleet could explain 23% of recruitment (for

³ “Recruitment at age 1”, in tonnes is the recruitment that can be caught. However, for this study, the indicator used was the recruitment at age 0. To estimate it, natural mortality was applied to the data of age 1, and the tonnes available one year earlier were calculated.

⁴<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/pesca/temas/mercados-economia-pesquera/ESPECIES.aspx>

the complete period) and 7.5% (before collapse), and 28% of SSB (complete period) and 36% (before collapse).

When exploring the links between the different parts of the CICES cascade (i.e., biophysical components or processes – function; function – service; service – benefit; benefit – value), the biophysical components or processes (upwelling index) did not significantly determine the function (recruitment).

When exploring how the function may determine the service (SSB), the relationship between recruitment and SSB was significant and very strong. The cascade components were positively related and, recruitment (at age 0), as independent variable, could explain >80% of SSB, as dependent variable.

The service (SSB, t) affected the anchovy fishery benefit (catch, t) significantly when analysed for the periods before and after collapse. However, this effect was not detected when considering the complete data series. The relationship was positive for both periods, showing a sharp increasing pattern in the case of the before collapse period, when service could explain 70% of the benefit variability. However, after the collapse, the relationship seems to be weaker.

Finally, the relationship between the benefit (catch, t) and value (€) was statistically significant and positive, both for the complete period and the after collapse, but not for the period before collapse.

Before the fishery collapse, a high proportion of the SSB was caught, being the captures in this period more than the 50% of the SSB in tonnes. Between 1987 and 1993 the catch followed the SSB evolution, ranging from the minimum catch in 1989 (10,374 t), with also a minimum value for SSB (observed before), and a maximum for both components in 1994 (catch: 40,087 t) (SSB: 72,428 t). After this, SSB had a decreasing pattern for the next five years (1994-1998) (minimum SSB: 39,486 t, 1995). Catches followed the same pattern as the period before, the captures exceeded the half of the SSB all the years, and decreased in values, reaching the minimum in 1997 (22,337 t). SSB showed an increasing pattern from 1997 to 2000, doubling in some cases the values reached the period before (maximum SSB: 91,838 t); however, the captures maintained the values around 3,000 t during this period. When the SSB started decreasing its values in 2001, catch followed the same evolution reaching a minimum of captures in 2005, with 1,128 t, when the fishery collapsed. In turn, after the collapse, the SSB (service) increased dramatically, but the catches (benefit component) remained at a low level, with a slight increase, and not far from the before-collapse levels, reaching a maximum in 2018, with 30,773 t caught.

Despite these fluctuations in the catches (benefit), the economic value of anchovy landings has been maintained without dramatic changes between 1990 and 1997 (mean value 48 million €). In 1998, even if catch did not increase its values significantly, the value reached its maximum (95.9 million €), before falling to 55.6 million €, in 1999. The next two years (2000 and 2001), both catches and economic value showed a slightly increasing pattern. Even if captures decreased sharply, the following years (2002-2004) the economic value maintained its values around 60 million €. When the fishery

collapsed, the economic value reached its minimum (6 million €). After that, the economic value started to increase, following the captures pattern, and maintaining values of around 40 million €.

The main conclusion for the second part of the study, the hypothesis was demonstrated for the case study, since the links between the cascade steps exist, and a “healthy” environment results in sustainable supply of ecosystem service and benefits. However, the relationships between the cascade components could be much more complex, if several species, components, and indicators are considered at the same time, as well as if we consider not only several cumulative human pressures, but also the climate change effect, in all cases under non-linear relationships.

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